

Report 2013

Trends and Sources of Zoonoses and Zoonotic Agents in Humans, Foodstuffs, Animals and Feedingstuffs

Austria

Including information on foodborne outbreaks,
antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic agents and some
pathogenic microbiological agents

AUSTRIA

The Report referred to in Article 9 of Directive 2003/99/EC

**TRENDS AND SOURCES OF ZONOSSES AND ZONOTIC AGENTS
IN HUMANS, FOODSTUFFS, ANIMALS AND FEEDINGSTUFFS**

**Including information on foodborne outbreaks, antimicrobial
resistance in zoonotic agents and some pathogenic microbiological
agents**

IN 2013

1. Information on the Reporting and Monitoring System

Country: Austria

Reporting Year: 2013

This report was prepared by the Department for Statistics and the Department for Data Management of the area Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment of the AGES. Following Institutions and Laboratories were involved:

Institutions and laboratories involved in monitoring

Authorities		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Central Veterinary Services	Federal Ministry of Health	Data concerning notifiable zoonoses in animals; Revision of the draft of the Trend Report; Approval of the Trend Report for Submission
Food Office	Federal Ministry of Health	Revision of the draft of the Trend Report
DG Public Health	Federal Ministry of Health	Validation of data concerning notifiable zoonoses in humans and food borne outbreaks; revision of the draft of the Trend Report
Feed Office	Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, the Environment and Watermanagement	Revision of the draft of the Trend Report
Provincial Veterinary Services	9 provinces, one Veterinary Service per province	Data concerning notifiable zoonoses in animals
Local/District health authorities	Part of each local administration authority ("Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde"); one physician per district	Collection and entry of the data concerning notifiable zoonoses in humans and food borne outbreaks

Institutes		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Department for Statistics and the Department for Data Management of the area Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment (DSR)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Compilation, validation, preparation, data entry and submission of the Zoonoses Trend Report (Reporting officer, national reporter); Analysis of laboratory results for antimicrobial resistance of <i>Salmonella</i> spp., <i>Campylobacter</i> spp., and <i>E. coli</i> ; Mapping of food and feed data; Creation of xml-files
Statistics Austria	The independent and non-profit-making federal institution, Statistics Austria, provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies. Federal agencies can then implement controlling measures in the scientific community, business and public institutions.	Demographic and livestock census data

Human Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Department for Infectious Epidemiology Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning notifiable zoonotic diseases in humans and food borne outbreaks
National Reference Centre for <i>Salmonella</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans, and antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for <i>Campylobacter</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning campylobacteriosis in humans, speciation of <i>Campylobacter</i> from food and animals, and antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Centre for Tuberculosis, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning tuberculosis in humans

Human Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Center for <i>E. coli</i> including VTEC Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Typing of VTEC from humans, food and animals
National Reference Centre for <i>Listeria</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning listeriosis in humans
National Reference Centre for <i>Yersinia</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning yersiniosis in humans
National Reference Laboratory for Toxoplasmosis, Echinococcosis, Toxocarosis and other Parasitic Diseases; Department of Medical Parasitology; Institute of Specific Prophylaxis and Tropical Medicine; Center for Physiology, Pathophysiology and Immunology	Medical University of Vienna	Laboratory data concerning parasitic diseases in humans
National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning brucellosis in humans and animals
National Reference Laboratory for Rabies, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning rabies in humans and animals

Food Control Institutes		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Official Food Control Laboratories (ILMU)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES; Laboratories in Graz, Innsbruck, Linz, Salzburg and Vienna	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Food Safety Department of the City of Vienna	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs

Food Control Institutes		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Institute for Environment and Food Safety of the State of Vorarlberg	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Carinthian Institute for Food Analysis and Quality Control	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
National Reference Centre for <i>Salmonella</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans, and antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for <i>Campylobacter</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning campylobacteriosis in humans, speciation of <i>Campylobacter</i> from food and animals, and antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Centre for <i>E. coli</i> including VTEC Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Typing of VTEC from humans, food and animals
National Reference Laboratory for <i>Listeria</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning listeriosis in food
National Reference Centre for <i>Yersinia</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning yersiniosis in food

Veterinary Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning monitoring programmes in animals
National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning tuberculosis in animals

Veterinary Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Centre for <i>Salmonella</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans and antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for <i>Campylobacter</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning campylobacteriosis in humans, speciation of <i>Campylobacter</i> from food and animals, antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for Antimicrobial resistance, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Testing for antimicrobial resistance of <i>E. coli</i> from animals
National Reference Centre for <i>E. coli</i> including VTEC Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Typing of VTEC from humans, food and animals
National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning brucellosis in humans and animals
National Reference Laboratory for Trichinellosis in Animals, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, (IVET), Innsbruck	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning trichinellosis in animals
Institutes for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES; Laboratories in Innsbruck, Linz and Moedling	Data concerning investigations in animals; bacteriological investigation in slaughtered animals
National Reference Laboratory for Rabies, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning rabies in humans and animals
Austrian Poultry Health Data (PHD)	Association installed by law, running different programs e.g. <i>Salmonella</i> control and hygiene programs, Control of veterinarians and poultry farmers	Data concerning the Austrian poultry industry

Feed Control Institute		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Institute for Animal Nutrition and Feed, Linz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning feeding stuff
National Reference Centre for <i>Salmonella</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans, and antimicrobial resistance testing

PREFACE

This report is submitted to the European Commission in accordance with Article 9 of Council Directive 2003/99/EC1. The information has also been forwarded to the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

The report contains information on trends and sources of zoonoses and zoonotic agents in Austria during the year 2013. The information covers the occurrence of these diseases and agents in humans, animals, foodstuffs and in some cases also in feedingstuffs. In addition the report includes data on antimicrobial resistance in some zoonotic agents and commensal bacteria as well as information on epidemiological investigations of foodborne outbreaks. Complementary data on susceptible animal populations in the country is also given.

The information given covers zoonoses that are important for public health in the whole European Community as well as zoonoses which are relevant on the basis of the national epidemiological situation.

The report describes the monitoring systems in place and the prevention and control strategies applied in the country. For some zoonoses this monitoring is based on legal requirements laid down by the Community Legislation, while for the other zoonoses national approaches are applied.

The report presents the results of the examinations carried out in the reporting year. A national evaluation of the epidemiological situation, with special reference to trends and sources of zoonotic infections, is given. Whenever possible, the relevance of findings in foodstuffs and animals to zoonoses cases in humans is evaluated.

The information covered by this report is used in the annual European Union Summary Report on zoonoses that is published each year by EFSA.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AGES	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety
BMSK	Federal Ministry for Social Security, Generations and Consumer Protection
EHEC	Enterohemorrhagic <i>E. coli</i>
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EMS	Epidemiological Notification System for human notifiable diseases ("epidemiologisches Meldesystem")
FMH	Federal Ministry of Health
ILMU	Official Food Control Laboratories, AGES
IMED	Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, AGES
IVET	Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, AGES
NRC	National Reference Centre
NRL	National Reference Laboratory
OIE	World organisation for animal health
PHD	Poultry Health Data
TESSy	the European Surveillance System
VIS	Veterinary Information System
VTEC	Verotoxin producing <i>E. coli</i>

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3. Animal Populations

3.1. Information on susceptible animal population

Sources of information

The independent and non-profit-making federal institution, Statistics Austria, provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies. Federal agencies can then implement controlling measures in the scientific community, business and public institutions. The data for this report are available from an online database established by Statistics Austria.

Herds, flocks, holdings, stocks

Cattle: The number of holdings and animals is based on the official database for cattle.

Equids, Pigs, Sheep, Goats and Farmed Deer: The number of holdings and animals is based on the yearly full survey for pig, sheep and goats of the Veterinary Information System (VIS).

Poultry: The number of holdings, flocks and animals is based on the Poultry Health Data. All holdings, flocks and animals are part of the *Salmonella* control program.

Slaughters

Cattle, Equids: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughters (reported by veterinarians), performed by Statistics Austria.

Pigs: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughters (reported by veterinarians), combined with not-examined slaughters (out of pig-random-sample-surveys) performed by Statistics Austria.

Sheep & Goats: The number of slaughters is based on an expert-model carried out by Statistics Austria.

Poultry: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly full survey in main poultry-slaughterhouses performed by Statistics Austria.

Dates the figures relate to and the content of the figures

Data are received from Statistics Austria, only poultry data from Poultry Health Data.

Definitions used for different types of animals, herds, flocks and holdings as well as the types covered by the information

Cattle: BGBl. II Nr. 147/2009 (Statistiken über den Viehbestand)

Swine, Sheep and Goats: BGBl. II Nr. 291/2009 (Tierkennzeichnungs- und Registrierungsverordnung 2009)

Poultry: BGBl. II Nr. 310/2007 (Erstellung der Statistik über die Agrarstruktur und den Viehbestand im Jahr 2007); BGBl. II Nr. 356/2003 (Erhebung der Geflügelschlachtungen in Betrieben mit min. 5000 Vorjahres-Geflügelschlachtungen)

Geographical distribution and size distribution of the herds, flocks and holdings

Pigs: 97.29 % of all pigs are kept in 84.47 % of the holdings that are located in the 4 provinces Carinthia, Lower Austria, Upper Austria and Styria;

Sheep: 72.66 % of the sheep holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 75.52 % of the sheep are kept there.

Goats: 70.25 % of the goat holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 78.03 % of the goats are kept there.

Solipeds: 66.56 % of the soliped holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 70.52 % of the solipeds are kept there.

Deer: 90.05 % of the deer holdings are located in the 4 provinces Carinthia, Lower Austria, Upper Austria and Styria; 89.78% of the deer are kept there.

Cattle: 74.44 % of the cattle holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and Tirol; 77.43% of the cattle are kept there.

Additional information

Nil

Table 1 Susceptible animal populations: number of herds and holdings rearing animals, 2013

	Animals species	date	Unit	Number	comments
in total	Cattle (bovine animals)	01.04.2013	holding	67,496	
in total	Cattle (bovine animals)	01.04.2013	animal	1,961,479	
in total	Cattle (bovine animals)	2013	slaughter animal (heads)	692,369	Post mortem inspection: 623,272 carcasses
	Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)	01.04.2013	animal	620,239	61,710 holdings with calves (under 1 year)
	Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)	2013	slaughter animal (heads)	69,097	
	Cattle (bovine animals) - meat production animals		animal		
	Cattle (bovine animals) - meat production animals		slaughter animal (heads)		
in total	Pigs	01.04.2013	holding	27,366	
in total	Pigs	01.04.2013	animal	2,940,421	
in total	Pigs	2013	slaughter animal (heads)	5,431,798	Post mortem inspection: 5,396,038 carcasses
	Pigs - breeding animals - unspecified - sows	01.04.2013	holding	6,428	
	Pigs - breeding animals - unspecified - sows	01.04.2013	animal	254,927	
	Pigs - breeding animals - unspecified - sows	2013	slaughter animal (heads)	94,841	
	Pigs - fattening pigs	01.04.2013	holding	20,848	
	Pigs - fattening pigs	01.04.2013	animal	1,105,159	
	Pigs - fattening pigs	2013	slaughter animal (heads)	5,336,957	
in total	Sheep	01.04.2013	holding	15,726	
in total	Sheep	01.04.2013	animal	419,390	
in total	Sheep	2013	slaughter animal (heads)	285,823	Post mortem inspection: 140,266 carcasses
	Sheep - animals over 1 year	01.04.2013	holding	15,328	
	Sheep - animals over 1 year	01.04.2013	animal	242,538	
	Sheep - animals over 1 year	2013	slaughter animal (heads)	66,392	
	Sheep - animals under 1 year (lambs)	01.04.2013	holding	12,709	
	Sheep - animals under 1 year (lambs)	01.04.2013	animal	176,852	
	Sheep - animals under 1 year (lambs)	2013	slaughter animal (heads)	219,431	
in total	Goats	01.04.2013	holding	10,352	
in total	Goats	01.04.2013	animal	90,6625	

Animal Populations

	Animals species	date	Unit	Number	comments
in total	Goats	2013	slaughter animal (heads)	54,390	Post mortem inspection: 5,107 carcasses
	Goats - animals over 1 year	01.04.2013	holding	10,127	
	Goats - animals over 1 year	01.04.2013	animal	63,651	
	Goats - animals over 1 year	2013	slaughter animal (heads)	12,709	
	Goats - animals under 1 year	01.04.2013	holding	4,309	
	Goats - animals under 1 year	01.04.2013	animal	26,974	
	Goats - animals under 1 year	2013	slaughter animal (heads)	41,681	
in total	Solipeds, domestic	01.04.2013	holding	15,152	
in total	Solipeds, domestic	01.04.2013	animal	73,961	
in total	Solipeds, domestic	2013	slaughter animal (heads)	1,004	Post mortem inspection:1,004 carcasses
in total	Deer - farmed	01.04.2013	holding	1,547	
in total	Deer - farmed	01.04.2013	animal	35,463	
in total	Gallus gallus (fowl)	2013	slaughter animal (heads)	74,309,000	Post mortem inspection:70,550,177 carcasses
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for broiler production line	2013	holding	56	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for broiler production line	2013	animal	829,850	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for broiler production line	2013	herd/flock	106	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for egg production line	2013	holding	11	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for egg production line	2013	animal	213,007	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for egg production line	2013	herd/flock	24	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - broilers	2013	holding	472	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - broilers	2013	animal	57,672,238	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - broilers	2013	herd/flock	3,581	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens	2013	holding	1,074	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens	2013	animal	9,113,035	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens	2013	herd/flock	2,731	

Animal Populations

	Animals species	date	Unit	Number	comments
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for broiler production line	2013	holding	56	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for broiler production line	2013	animal	829,850	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for broiler production line	2013	herd/flock	106	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for egg production line	2013	holding	11	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for egg production line	2013	animal	213,007	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for egg production line	2013	herd/flock	24	
in total	Turkeys	2013	holding	133	
in total	Turkeys	2013	animal	2,224,558	
in total	Turkeys	2013	herd/flock	356	
	Turkeys - meat production flocks	2013	holding	133	
	Turkeys - meat production flocks	2013	animal	2,224,558	
	Turkeys - meat production flocks	2013	herd/flock	356	

4. Information on Specific Zoonoses and Zoonotic Agents

The World Health Organization defines zoonoses as “those diseases and infections which are naturally transmitted between vertebrate animals and man.” Foodstuffs often serve as vehicles of zoonotic infections. Zoonotic agents include viruses, bacteria, fungi, parasites or other biological entities that are likely to cause zoonoses.

Collection of human cases

Starting with January 1st 2009 a new reporting system, the **epidemiological reporting system** (Epidemiologisches Meldesystem, EMS) has been put in operation at the MOH. The physicians report all notifiable diseases (case based) to the local health authorities which are part of the local administration authorities (“Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde”). The physicians working at the local health authorities (public health officers) have to enter the data of the human cases of all notifiable diseases in the data base EMS including all relevant variables and laboratory results (case based). Also the laboratories enter the results of their laboratory work in EMS via a gateway to streamline the process.

EMS is the one and only database for notifiable diseases in the human sector in Austria. This system is also the standard gateway for reporting to ECDC (TESSy). A short report is also extracted and compiled using EMS which is published nationwide monthly and once a year by the Federal Ministry of Health online on the BMG-homepage:

http://bmg.gv.at/home/Schwerpunkte/Krankheiten/Uebertragbare_Krankheiten/Statistiken/Monatliche_Statistik_meldepflichtiger_Infektionskrankheiten_ab_2010).

Additionally data of primary isolates from patients typed in the national reference centres are available. The responsible reference centres for zoonotic diseases published the numbers of microbiologically typed primary isolates from humans; due to the fact that more than one bacterial strain could be isolated from single patients these figures may differ from the case numbers notified to the Federal Ministry.

In this report it is indicated which data source has been used for the reporting of human cases for each respective zoonosis.

General Information about the Food Sampling Strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2013 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2013“ (BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2012) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2013, approximately 26,000 samples were planned (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples consist of samples of

the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that has to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail or at the producer.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for specific food items (about 60-65 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2013, 8 food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2013 BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2012). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002. (e. g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). Therefore food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures. Therefore Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs indicates the quantity of sampling (number of sample units and size of the analytical unit) regarding to specific microbiological hazards at the stage of products placed on the market within their shelflife and at a specific stage of production (e.g. before and/or after chilling).

4.1. Salmonellosis

4.1.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Human salmonellosis remains a major health problem in Austria. In 2013, the number of notified salmonellosis cases was the second highest reported food-borne pathogen after campylobacteriosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The incidence of human salmonellosis has significantly declined since the peak in 1998/1999. The salmonella-contamination of raw poultry meat has declined from 30 % in 1999 to less than 5.5 % in 2009, and increased in 2012 to 9.3 % and in 2013 to 10 %. The consumption of eggs and egg products that are contaminated with Salmonella is presumably the main cause of human infection (S. Enteritidis).

The number of salmonellosis cases presented in this report (table 2) reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to EMS, n = 1,433 cases. This number shows again a reduction compared to the previous year and reflects the success of interventions aimed at combating salmonella.

As compared to the number of notified cases of campylobacteriosis (see chapter campylobacteriosis), salmonella is the second most important cause for enteric diseases in Austria.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

The incidence of human salmonellosis has significantly declined within the last years. Different foodstuffs (e.g. poultry meat, eggs, or mixed foodstuffs) may pose a certain risk therefore kitchen hygiene is of utmost importance.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

There were EU programs implemented to control the contamination of Salmonella in poultry, most programs involved meat and egg production. The effort of the intervention is directed toward improving the sanitation of breeding flocks and laying flocks, broiler flocks and turkey flocks according to EU legislation.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Continue the efforts already started, especially to improve harmonization of monitoring and control programs along the food chain.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents, which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obligated to send these strains to the respective national reference laboratory for typing and comparative analysis.

4.1.2. Salmonellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of salmonellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following four symptoms:

- Diarrhoea
- Fever
- Abdominal pain
- Vomiting

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of *Salmonella* (other than *S. Typhi* and *S. Paratyphi*) from stool or blood

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriology: Sample material is processed as described in „Richtlinien für die Diagnostik von Salmonellen (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 11-12)“.

At the National Reference Centre for *Salmonella* (NRC *Salmonella*) all isolates are serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le Minor Scheme. And further all *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK. Additionally the antimicrobial resistance testing by disk diffusion method is performed with each isolate.

Notification system in place

Notification of salmonellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 1989 and 1990, human infections with salmonella increased markedly in Austria. After a peak in 1992, the incidence of salmonella illness decreased, but the number of infections has remained at a high level until 2002. Since that year the number of laboratory confirmed cases of human *Salmonella* cases has decreased by 83 % (2002: 8,403 cases, 2013: 1,433 notified cases).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2013, the number of human laboratory confirmed cases of salmonellosis notified to EMS decreased compared to the years before.

The proportion of *S. Enteritidis* isolates out of all *Salmonella* cases decreased in 2013 to 42.4 % (compared to 49 % in 2012). The most frequently identified *Enteritidis* phage types in 2013 were: PT 8 (33 %), PT 4 18%, PT 14b (7%) and PT 21 (7 %). The reduction of salmonellosis cases was mainly due to *S. Enteritidis*, the number of all other serotypes was also reduced compared to the previous years (826 cases in 2013; between 1,200 and 947 cases from 2002 to 2012).

The proportion of *S. Typhimurium* isolates reported decreased to 7.2% (2012: 13.9 %). Most frequent definitive type was DT 193 (24 %). 68 isolates of monophasic *S. group B* (1,4,[5],12:l:-) were found in humans, 72 % of definitive type DT 193.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In 2013, the number of notified human laboratory confirmed cases of campylobacteriosis again exceeded the number of salmonellosis cases. The reduction in the number of human salmonellosis cases is due to EU wide control programs and establishment of goals for the reduction of prevalences of salmonella in laying hen flocks, broilers and turkeys.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria on monthly and yearly basis. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH

Table 2 Salmonellosis cases from humans - serotype distribution (EMS/NRZ), 2013

Serotype	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	imported cases	unknown status
Salmonellosis	1,433	17.0	322	93
S. Enteritidis	607	7.2	150	44
S. Typhimurium	211	2.5	29	12
S. Stanley	92	1.1	10	4
S. 1,4,[5],12:i:-	68	0.8	10	7
S. Infantis	67	0.8	5	4
S. Newport	28	0.3	8	3
S. Saintpaul	17	0.2	2	
S. Indiana	15	0.2	2	
S. Paratyphi B	15	0.2	5	
S. Kentucky	14	0.2	7	1
S. Oranienburg	14	0.2	1	3
S. Agona	13	0.2	5	
S. Montevideo	13	0.2	2	1
S. Virchow	11	0.1	10	
S. Bareilly	10	0.1	2	
S. group B	9	0.1	2	
S. Napoli	9	0.1	2	
S. Bovismorbificans	8	0.1		2
S. Braenderup	8	0.1	3	
S. Kottbus	8	0.1	3	
S. Mbandaka	8	0.1	7	
S. Derby	7	0.1	1	1
S. Senftenberg	7	0.1		1
S. Rissen	6	0.1	4	
S. Schwarzengrund	6	0.1	5	
S. Abony	5	0.1	1	
S. Corvallis	5	0.1	4	
S. Hadar	5	0.1		2
S. Muenchen	5	0.1	1	1
S. Stanleyville	5	0.1	2	1
S. Bredeney	4	0.0	1	
S. Coeln	4	0.0		
S. enterica subsp. diarizonae	4	0.0		
S. enterica subsp. salamae	4	0.0		
S. Mississippi	4	0.0	3	1
S. Thompson	4	0.0		

Serotype	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	imported cases	unknown status
S. Give	3	0.0		
S. group D	3	0.0	1	
S. Javiana	3	0.0		
S. Paratyphi	3	0.0	1	
S. Tennessee	3	0.0	2	
S. Umbilo	3	0.0	1	
S. Weltevreden	3	0.0	2	
S. Albany	2	0.0	1	
S. Bispbjerg	2	0.0	1	
S. Cerro	2	0.0		1
S. Eastbourne	2	0.0		
S. Goldcoast	2	0.0		
S. Havana	2	0.0	1	
S. Lexington	2	0.0		
S. London	2	0.0		
S. Poona	2	0.0	1	
S. Rubislaw	2	0.0		
S. Adelaide	1	0.0		
S. Afula	1	0.0		
S. Ago	1	0.0		1
S. Altona	1	0.0	1	
S. Apapa	1	0.0		
S. Blockley	1	0.0		
S. Brandenburg	1	0.0		
S. Choleraesuis	1	0.0		
S. Cullingworth	1	0.0		
S. Dublin	1	0.0		
S. Durham	1	0.0		
S. Edinburg	1	0.0		
S. enterica subsp. arizonae	1	0.0		
S. enterica subsp. enterica - rough	1	0.0	1	
S. enterica subsp. houtenae	1	0.0	1	
S. Friedrichsfelde	1	0.0		
S. group C - S. group C1	1	0.0		
S. group D - S. group D1	1	0.0		
S. group E	1	0.0	1	
S. Grumpensis	1	0.0	1	
S. Haifa	1	0.0		1
S. Heidelberg	1	0.0	1	
S. Hull	1	0.0	1	
S. Isangi	1	0.0		
S. Isaszeg	1	0.0		
S. Kambole	1	0.0		
S. Kapemba	1	0.0	1	
S. Kedougou	1	0.0		
S. Kenya	1	0.0		
S. Koketime	1	0.0	1	
S. Litchfield	1	0.0		
S. Liverpool	1	0.0	1	
S. Livingstone	1	0.0	1	
S. Manhattan	1	0.0		

Serotype	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	imported cases	unknown status
S. Mikawasima	1	0.0		
S. Muenster	1	0.0		
S. Nigeria	1	0.0		
S. Oslo	1	0.0	1	
S. Panama	1	0.0	1	
S. Sandiego	1	0.0	1	
S. Strathcona	1	0.0	1	
S. Telelkebir	1	0.0		
Salmonella spp., unspecified	30	0.4	9	2

Data source: EMS/NRZ as of April 16, 2014

Table 3 Salmonellosis isolates in humans - age distribution (EMS/NRZ), 2013

age groups	Salmonellosis		S. Enteritidis		S. Infantis		Monophasic S. group B (1,4,[5],12:l:-)		S. Stanley		S. Typhimurium		other serotypes		Unknown serotype	
	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F
< 1 year	18	17	9	5	1	2	0	1	0	1	1		6	8	1	0
1 to 4 years	97	89	46	45	4	1	3	7	7	4	14	19	22	13	1	0
5 to 14 years	110	96	61	55	2	4	4	3	12	2	12	17	17	15	2	0
15 to 24 years	105	96	35	33	3	3	3	6	13	7	18	17	31	27	2	3
25 to 44 years	155	119	48	45	9	6	6	4	13	12	22	12	53	38	4	2
45 to 64 years	140	135	57	56	5	9	6	6	7	6	21	22	41	34	3	2
65 years and older	111	145	45	67	11	7	9	10	4	4	14	22	23	30	5	5
All age groups	736	697	301	306	35	32	31	37	56	36	102	109	193	165	18	12

Data source: EMS/NRZ as of April 16, 2014

Table 4 Salmonellosis isolates in humans – seasonal distribution (EMS/NRZ), 2013

Month	Salmonellosis	S. Enteritidis	S. Infantis	Monophasic S. group B (1,4,[5],12:l:-)	S. Stanley	S. Typhimurium	other serotypes	Unknown serotype
January	72	21	1	2	10	13	22	3
February	59	8	1	1	7	8	33	1
March	67	19	3	5	4	11	23	2
April	69	16	7	5	10	9	19	3
May	105	33	11	2	8	25	24	2
June	122	47	3	8	7	26	30	1
July	176	84	4	4	8	32	41	3
August	205	107	7	9	9	23	47	3
September	214	109	12	16	4	26	44	3
October	150	73	6	4	12	18	34	3
November	120	70	3	6	9	6	24	2
December	74	20	9	6	4	14	17	4
Total	1,433	607	67	68	92	211	358	30

Data source: EMS/NRZ as of April 16, 2014

4.1.3. *Salmonella* spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2013 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2013“ (BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2012) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2013, approximately 26,000 samples were planned (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that has to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail or at the producer.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for specific food items (about 60-65 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2013, 8 food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2013 BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2012). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002. (e. g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). Therefore food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures. Therefore Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs indicates the quantity of sampling (number of sample units and size of the analytical unit) regarding to specific microbiological hazards at the stage of products placed on the market within their shelflife and at a specific stage of production (e.g. before and/or after chilling).

Frequency of the sampling

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Type of specimen taken

Fresh meat, meat preparations, minced meat, etc.

Defintion of positive finding

A positive sample is a sample from which *Salmonella* has been isolated.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriological method ISO 6579:2002 + Cor.1:2004 + Amd.1:2007.

The amount of tested food in general is 25 g. Some exceptions exist, according to the Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005, as indicated in tables 5-8.

All *Salmonella* isolates are sent to the National Reference Centre for Salmonella in Graz and serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK. Additionally all isolates are tested for their antibiotic susceptibility according to EUCAST. In case of an outbreak situation the stored isolates may be further investigated with pulsed-field gel electrophoresis (PFGE) or multiple-locus variable-number of tandem-repeats analysis (MLVA).

Control program/mechanisms

All isolates have to be sent to the National Reference Centre for Salmonella in Graz, where the isolates are further analysed and stored.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Whenever Salmonella is detected the isolates are sent to the National Reference Centre for Salmonella in Graz. Investigation into the source of the contamination is initiated if indicated.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections.

Salmonella spp. was detected in fresh broiler meat samples in 9.8 % (16 out of 163) and in 10.2 % of fresh turkey meat samples (6 out of 59), which is comparable to the results of 2012 (10.3 % positive in fresh broiler meat, 11.1 % positive in fresh turkey meat samples). In two of the remaining 22 fresh meat samples from duck meat, geese meat and unspecified poultry meat Salmonella (9,1 %) have been detected, none of them at processing stage. Analysing the data from broiler meat at sampling stage level, no sample was tested positive for Salmonella at processing plant and abattoir (18 samples tested).

In total 1,033 samples of meat and meat preparations (excluding poultry meat) were tested, with only one positive sample for *Salmonella* (*S. Typhimurium*) in the category "meat from bovine animal, fresh".

In 2013, *Salmonella* were not found in 591 samples of milk, dairy products and cheeses, as in the years 2007-2012. 2,323 samples of different matrices were tested for *Salmonella*, resulting in one positive finding in the category "Spices and herbs" and two positive findings in the category "Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta". 78 samples of egg products have been tested for *Salmonella* without any positive findings. Out of the 114 sample units sampled at packing centres, at retail level, catering or wholesale no sample was tested positive for *Salmonella*.

Relevance of the findings in foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of human infection)

The relevance of these findings is delineated in foodborne outbreaks

Food-borne outbreaks.

Since January 2012 the Outbreak Detection System (ODS) for the early detection of Salmonellosis has been installed in Austria. Within this tool realtime data on Salmonella isolates are utilized to determine a threshold value. If the number of Salmonella cases of the current week exceeds this threshold, a signal indicates a possible outbreak. This signal enables an early start of outbreak investigations.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-012-13: *Salmonella* spp. in food – infant formula – dried – at retail – Surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: March - April

Type of specimen taken

Infant formula dried

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* in 25g

Results of the investigation

Salmonella spp. not detected in 54 samples tested.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Cronobacter sakazakii*

Campaign A-019-13: *Salmonella* spp. in food – other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods – at retail – Surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples were taken at food stalls in front of shopping malls by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: June - August

Type of specimen taken

Several ready to eat snacks, amongst others meat, meat products and sausages from all kind of species, different cheeses and bakery products

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* in 25g

Results of the investigation

Salmonella spp. not detected in 62 samples tested.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *L. monocytogenes*

Campaign A-024-13: *Salmonella* spp. in food – Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme maturated – at catering – Surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at catering by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: May - July

Type of specimen taken

Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine (tuna in open cans, collected in restaurants)

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* in 25g

Results of the investigation

Salmonella spp. not detected in 99 samples tested.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for Histamine

Campaign A-041-13: *Salmonella* spp. in food - Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail, in this campaign at “takeaway” facilities by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September - Oktober

Type of specimen taken

Several ready to eat dishes containing noodles, vegetables, different kind of sauces (including meat from different species)

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* spp. in 25 g

Results of the investigation

Salmonella spp. not detected in 62 samples tested.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *L. monocytogenes* and *Campylobacter*

Campaign A-801-13: *Salmonella* spp. in food – mixed meat and cheese products – at retail – Surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September - October

Type of specimen taken

Meat, red meat – meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat or fermented sausages
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* in 25g

Results of the investigation

Salmonella spp. not detected in 105 samples tested.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *L. monocytogenes* and VTEC

Table 5 *Salmonella* spp. in poultry meat and meat products, 2013

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Agona	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Blockley	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Enteritidis - PT 3	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Infantis	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Kottbus	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Montevideo	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Newport	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Stanley	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Typhimurium - DT 85	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Virchow		
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh	Catering		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
				50	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Processing plant		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
				25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	123	13	0	0	0	12	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	
				EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Slaughterhouse		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
				XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Wholesale		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from duck - fresh		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from duck - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from geese - fresh	Retail		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
				XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
	Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0				
Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh	Processing plant		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
				XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
	Retail		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
				XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
	Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Catering		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0			
				XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
	Processing plant		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
				EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	68	12	0	0	1	6	0	2	2	0	1		
	Retail		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
				AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Wholesale		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Catering	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	Catering		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
				XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
	Processing plant		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
				EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
	Retail		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
AT				single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0						
Meat from turkey - fresh	Catering		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
				EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0			
	Retail		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	45	4	1	0	1	0	0	2	1	0	0			
				EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Meat from turkey - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Meat from turkey - meat preparation - intended to be eaten raw - frozen		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Meat from turkey - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			

Table 6 *Salmonella* spp. in red meat and products thereof, 2013

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Typhimurium</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>Salmonella</i> spp.
Meat from bovine animals - fresh		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0
					50	Gram	2	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	8	0	0	0
					25	Gram	3	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
					XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	1	1	0
25	Gram				1	0	0	0		
Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	5	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0
					10	Gram	8	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0
					EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	0	0
					10	Gram	32	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0
					EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals and pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals and pig - meat products		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals and pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	16	0	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	0	0
					25	Gram	2	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
					XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0
					25	Gram	1	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	7	0	0	0
					25	Gram	8	0	0	0
EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0			
Meat from other animal species or not specified - fresh		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat preparation		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0

Table 6 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 85
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0
Meat from pig - fresh		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	0
			25	Gram	1	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	7	0	0
			25	Gram	11	0	0		
Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0		
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	12	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	137	0	0
			25	Gram	20	0	0		
		XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0
EU	single (food/feed)		10	Gram	1	0	0		
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	5	0	0
			25	Gram	6	0	0		
Meat from sheep - fresh		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	50	Gram	1	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Meat from wild game - birds - fresh		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0
		Game handling establishment	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	6	0	0
			10	Gram	123	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	115	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	4	0	0
		Slaughterhouse	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos)		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0

Table 6 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 85	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	46	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	23	Gram	1	0	0	
				25	Gram	7	0	0		
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	
		campaign A-801-13	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	24	0	0
				EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
				XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
		Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Retail	AT			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	
	EU			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	
	XX			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	
Wholesale	XX			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	
campaign A-801-13	Retail			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	
			25	Gram	6	0	0			
		Game handling establishment	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	38	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	23	Gram	1	0	0	
				25	Gram	92	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	29	0	0	
		Wholesale	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	13	0	0	
		campaign A-801-13	Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
AT	single (food/feed)			25	Gram	31	0	0		
	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0		
		AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	4	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	4	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	19	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	

Table 7 *Salmonella* spp. in milk and dairy products, 2013

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.
Cheeses made from cows' milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses made from goats' milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses made from goats milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	50	Gram	1	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats	campaign A-801-13	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	37	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - made from pasteurised milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream - made from pasteurised milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	29	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy desserts		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy desserts - chilled		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	13	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	26	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	29	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	267	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - made from pasteurised milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	31	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - milk powder and whey powder		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - raw milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Milk, cows' - pasteurised milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Milk, cows' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	0
Milk, cows - pasteurised milk		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Milk, cows - raw milk		Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0
Milk, cows - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Milk, goats' - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Milk, goats - raw milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Milk, sheeps - raw milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0

Table 8 *Salmonella* spp. in other food, 2013

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Enteritidis - PT 4	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Oranienburg	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Typhimurium - DT 99
Bakery products		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0
			Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0
		EU		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
Bakery products - bread		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Bakery products - cakes		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	42	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Bakery products - pastry		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	24	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	116	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0		
Beverages, non-alcoholic		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Cereals and meals		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
Chocolate		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	20	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	90	0	0	0	0
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	37	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0			

Table 8 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 4	Salmonella - S. Oranienburg	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 99
Crustaceans		Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
		XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
Crustaceans - prawns		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
Egg products		Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	300	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	26	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0		
Egg products - dried		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Egg products - liquid		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0			
Eggs - table eggs		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
					300	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Packing centre	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
					50	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
					300	Gram	49	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	29	0	0	0	0
					50	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
					120	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
					300	Gram	25	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0		

Table 8 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 4	Salmonella - S. Oranienburg	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 99
Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured	campaign A-024-13	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	57	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	13	0	0	0	0
Fish - raw		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Catering	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0		
Fish - smoked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
Fish - unspecified		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
XE	single (food/feed)		25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0		
Fishery products, unspecified - raw		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	
Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	
Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	
Foodstuffs intended for special nutritional uses - dried dietary foods for special medical purposes intended for infants below 6 months		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	
Fruits		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	
Fruits - pre-cut		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	
Fruits - pre-cut - chilled		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	
Fruits - products		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	22	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	25	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	
XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0			
Infant formula		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	18	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	
XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0			

Table 8 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 4	Salmonella - S. Oranienburg	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 99
Infant formula - dried	campaign A-012-13	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	31	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	20	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
Juice - fruit juice		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Juice - fruit juice - unpasteurised		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
Juice - mixed juice		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Live bivalve molluscs - mussels		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from deer (venison) - fresh		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Game handling establishment	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
		Retail	XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from deer (venison) - meat products - fermented sausages		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0
Molluscan shellfish - raw - chilled		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Molluscan shellfish - shelled, shucked and cooked		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Mushrooms		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
EU	single (food/feed)		25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0		
Nuts and nut products		Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	55	0	0	0	0
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	35	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	52	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0
XE	single (food/feed)		25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0		
XX	single (food/feed)		25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0		

Table 8 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 4	Salmonella - S. Oranienburg	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 99	
Nuts and nut products - roasted		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
Other food		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
					25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	24	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0
XE	single (food/feed)		25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Other food of non-animal origin		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
Other processed food products and prepared dishes		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	295	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	24	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	28	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	196	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	29	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	
Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0			
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - noodles		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	23	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	36	1	0	0	1	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	50	1	1	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	24	0	0	0	0	
XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0				
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - sushi		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods	campaign A-019-13	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	55	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	
	campaign A-041-13	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	60	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	

Table 8 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 4	Salmonella - S. Oranienburg	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 99
Ready-to-eat salads		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	18	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	94	0	0	0	0
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0		
Sauce and dressings		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	20	0	0	0	0
Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise		Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Seeds, dried		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	20	0	0	0	0
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
XE	single (food/feed)		25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0		
Soups - dehydrated		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Spices and herbs		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	21	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	44	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	34	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	15	1	0	1	0
		Wholesale	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	13	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	0	0	0	0
EU	single (food/feed)		25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0		
XX	single (food/feed)		25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0		
Spices and herbs - dried		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
Sweets		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Vegetables		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Vegetables - products		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0

4.1.4. *Salmonella* spp. in animals

A. *Salmonella* spp. in *Gallus gallus* - breeding flocks

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are only parent flocks in Austria. The permanent monitoring plan performed by a national program takes place at hatcheries and on farm level; each flock is tested regularly as well by the farmer as by the Veterinary Authorities.

If *S. Enteritidis*, *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Infantis*, *S. Hadar* and *S. Virchow* or *S. Pullorum Gallinarum* is isolated from breeding flocks at the hatchery the flock is banned and sampled for confirmation on the farm: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens are pooled.

If a parent flock tests positive for other salmonella serotypes, official veterinarians are required to investigate the source of infection to optimise biosecurity.

Frequency of the sampling

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Every flock is tested at day one

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

1. Routine testing: Every flock is tested at the age of 4 and 12 weeks and two weeks before moving to laying phase or laying unit.
2. Confirmation: If routine testing reveals positive Salmonella test results then follow-up test must be performed from the identical flock.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Monitoring is performed according the national program and takes place at hatchery and on the farm: at hatchery: each flock is tested every two weeks by the industry, and every 16 weeks by the Veterinary Authorities; on the farm: each flock is tested every two weeks by the farmer and 3 times by the Veterinary Authorities (at beginning of production, in the middle of the production period and within the last 8 weeks before slaughter).

Type of specimen taken

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!
Routine testing: drag swabs, pooled faeces.

For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and up to inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: Boot swabs, pooled faeces; in the hatchery: dust, meconium, broken eggshells and hatched eggs.

For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: 5 pairs of boot swabs or 200 to 300 pooled droppings a 1 gram per flock, collection of dust.

For confirmation: For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Breeding flocks: Production period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: 5 pairs of boot swabs, pooled faeces, collection of dust.

For confirmation: For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Case definition

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: *Salmonella* spp. isolated from samples taken

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5+/- 1°C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xld or sm2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the White-KauffmannLe Minor-Scheme. All S. Enteritidis and S. Typhimurium isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Other: See day old chicks

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

Other: See day old chicks

Vaccination policy

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! The national program for parent flocks made vaccination against Salmonella Enteritidis mandatory for all flocks

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). It is in line with CR (EU) No 200/2010. The Austrian program for monitoring and eradication of Salmonella in breeding flocks of poultry was again (already since 2000) approved for the year 2013 by Commission Decision 2012/761/EU of November 30th 2012.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Measures according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation:

- Banning of the incriminated sector of the holding
- Culling of the infected flock
- Disposal of the hatched eggs
- Abolishing of the restriction after cleaning and disinfection
- If necessary prescriptions of GMP to prevent re-infection

Notification system in place

All positive results from parent flocks must be reported to the local authorities and via the Poultry Health Data (PHD) to the Federal Ministry of Health (BMG).

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2013, *Salmonella* spp. was detected in seven parent flocks in Austria. From one meat production flock *S. Enteritidis* was isolated. That reveals an overall prevalence for target relevant serotypes of 0.8 %. Therefore the EU-target was achieved in 2013. Six other flocks were positive for *S. Agona* (1 flock), *S. Nyborg* (1 flock) and *S. Senftenberg* (4 flocks). In one rearing parent flock (meat production line) *S. Senftenberg* was detected before it was moved to the holding(s) of production.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

***B. Salmonella* spp. in *Gallus gallus* - flocks of laying hens**

Monitoring system**Sampling strategy****Laying hens flocks**

Each flock is tested every 15 weeks sampling two pairs of boot swabs, at least one testing per year is done by an official veterinarian (boot swabs, dust samples and faeces for residue testing are taken) according to Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011.

At the earliest 3 weeks prior to slaughter, two pairs of boot swabs must be taken from each flock. Since May 2007, every flock has been tested in accordance to Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011.

Frequency of the sampling**Laying hens: Day-old chicks**

Chickens are tested at day one.

Laying hens: Rearing period

3 times (at day one, week 8 to 12) and two weeks before moving to laying phase or laying unit

Laying hens: Production period

Each flock is tested every 15 weeks with two pairs of boot swabs; an official veterinarian samples every flock at least once a year according to Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011.

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Within 3 weeks before slaughter with two pairs of boot swabs at farm

Laying hens: At slaughter

Other: Not applicable. No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Other: according to the program of the cooperatives voluntary surface swabs (e.g. every eight weeks)

Type of specimen taken

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Laying hens: Rearing period

Boot swabs, pooled faeces

Laying hens: Production period

Boot swabs, pooled faeces in holdings with enriched cages; official controls: additional dust samples and pooled faeces for antimicrobial testing

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Other: two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: At slaughter

Other: no sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Other: Voluntary e.g. surface swabs

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Laying hens: Rearing period

2 pairs of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: Production period

Industry sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock

Official sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock, 25 g of dust and 60 pooled faeces samples

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: At slaughter

No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

No legal requirements, e.g. surface swabs

Case definition

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken

Laying hens: Rearing period

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken

Laying hens: Production period

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs or dust or detection of antimicrobials or bacterial growth inhibitory effect in feces samples

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Laying hens: At slaughter

No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Salmonella spp. isolated from surface swabs

Diagnostic/analytical methods used**Laying hens: Day-old chicks**

Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5+/- 1°C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xld or sm2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the White-KauffmannLe Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Laying hens: Rearing period

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Laying hens: Production period

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Laying hens: At slaughter

Other: no testing

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Other: See laying hens, day old chicks.

Vaccination policy**Laying hens flocks**

The national program made vaccination against *Salmonella* Enteritidis mandatory for all flocks.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place**Laying hens flocks**

Nil

Control program/mechanisms**The control program/strategies in place****Laying hens flocks**

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

All actions according to EU- and national legislation

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Review of the target Serovars

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Laying hens flocks

No class A eggs or culling in case of association with a food borne outbreak; EU regulation No 1237/2007 is in force

Notification system in place

All positive results from laying flocks must be reported to the local authorities and via the Poultry Health Data to the Federal Ministry of Health (BMG).

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2013, 2,731 laying hen flocks were in production. *S. Enteritidis* or *S. Typhimurium* was detected in 22 flocks (0.8 %). The EU-target was achieved in 2013.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

C. Salmonella spp. in *Gallus gallus* - broiler flocks

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Broiler flocks

Within 3 weeks prior to slaughter boot swabs have to be taken. Other programs are not foreseen, only voluntary sampling by the farmer or sampling according to private cooperatives is performed.

Frequency of the sampling

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

no legal requirements, e.g. at day one each flock

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

no legal requirements

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Within 3 weeks before slaughter at farm 2 pairs of boot swabs have to be taken. 10 % of the flocks have to be tested by the competent authority. Commission Regulation (EC) No 646/2007, followed by Commission Regulation (EC) No 200/2012 is in force since 01.01.2009

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Type of specimen taken

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Nil

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Industry sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock

Official sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock, 60 pooled faeces samples (150g)

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

no legal requirements, e.g. pooled faeces

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

two pairs of boot swabs per flock; 10 % of the flocks sampled by competent authority, Regulation EU 646/2007, followed by Commission Regulation (EU) No 200/2012, is in force since 01.01.2009

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Case definition

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5+/- 1°C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xId or sm2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the White-KauffmannLe Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Other: See day-old chicks

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Other: See day-old chicks

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

no testing

Vaccination policy

Broiler flocks

Neither legal requirements nor recommendations

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Broiler flocks

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Broiler flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 200/2012.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Review of the target serovars

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Competitive exclusion strategies take place.

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Competitive exclusion strategies take place.

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Competitive exclusion strategies take place. Logistic Slaughtering is permitted for *Salmonella* spp. positive flocks

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Notification system in place

All positive findings in broiler flocks had to be notified to the local authority and via the Poultry health data (PHD) to the Federal Ministry of Health.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2013, 3,581 broiler flocks were in production. *S. Enteritidis* or *S. Typhimurium* was detected in 17 flocks (0.5 %). The EU-target was achieved in 2013.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

D. Salmonella spp. in turkey - meat production flocks

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Meat production flocks

Within 3 weeks prior to slaughter boot swabs have to be taken. Other programs are not foreseen, only voluntary sampling by the farmer or sampling according to private cooperatives is performed.

Frequency of the sampling

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

no legal requirements, e.g. at day one each flock

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

no legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock; 10 % of the flocks sampled by competent authority, Regulation EU 584/2008, followed by Commission Regulation (EU) No 1190/2012, is in force since 01.01.2010

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Type of specimen taken

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Industry sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock

Official sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock, 60 pooled faeces samples (150g)

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

no sampling

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

No sampling

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock; 10 % of the flocks sampled by competent authority, Regulation EU 584/2008, followed by Commission Regulation (EU) No 1190/2012, is in force since 01.01.2010

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Case definition

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5+/- 1°C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like xld or sm2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the White-KauffmannLe Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

see day-old chicks

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

see day-old chicks

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

see day-old chicks

Vaccination policy

Meat production flocks

Neither legal requirements nor recommendations

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Meat production flocks

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Meat production flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 1190/2012.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Review of the target serovars

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

According to Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005

Notification system in place

All positive findings in turkey broiler flocks have to be notified to the local authority and via the Poultry health data (PHD) to the Federal Ministry of Health.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2013, 356 turkey meat production flocks existed in Austria. *S. Enteritidis* or *S. Typhimurium* was detected in 1 (0.3 %) turkey flock. The EU-targeted was achieved in 2013.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 9 *Salmonella* spp. in poultry breeding flocks (*Gallus gallus*), 2013

Animal species	No of flocks under control programme	Source of information	Sampling strategy	Sampler	Sample type	Analytical method	Target verification	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Enteritidis	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Typhimurium	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Hadar	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Infantis	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Virchow	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. 1,4,[5],12:i:-	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Agona	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Enteritidis - PT 2	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Nyborg	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Senftenberg	<i>Salmonella</i> spp., unspecified
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for egg production line, during rearing period, control and eradication programmes	11	PHD	Objective sampling	Official and industry sampling	A	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	herd/flock	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for egg production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	24	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	A	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	herd/flock	24	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), grandparent breeding flocks for egg production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	0																				
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for broiler production line, during rearing period, control and eradication programmes	59	PHD	Objective sampling	Official and industry sampling	A	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	herd/flock	59	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), parent breeding flocks for broiler production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	106	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	A	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	herd/flock	106	6	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	4	0
<i>Gallus gallus</i> (fowl), grandparent breeding flocks for broiler production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	0																				

QGV: Poultry Health Data; A = animal sample

2) one flock harbouring two different serotypes (S. Mbandaka and S. Senftenberg)

3) four flocks harbouring two different serotypes (S. Mbandaka and S. Nyborg 2 x, S. Montevideo and S. Nyborg, S. Sentenberg and S. Nyborg) and one flock harbouring two different phagetypes (S. Enteritidis PT 23 and PT 8)

4) three flocks harbouring two different serotypes (S. Infantis and S. Give 2 x, S. Montevideo and S. Poona)

4.1.5. *Salmonella* spp. in feedstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Official monitoring based on risk assessment, own check programme by the industry based on HACCP.

Frequency of the sampling

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Assigned sampling plan, random samples are collected based on an official surveillance programme.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Other: See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

Other: See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

Other: See above

Process control in feed mills

Other: See above

Compound feeding stuffs

Other: See above

Type of specimen taken

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Feed material of cereal grain and oil seed or fruit origin

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Fish meal, dried animal by-products for pets

Imported feed material of plant origin

Oil seed meals and cakes

Imported feed material of animal origin

Fish meal, dried animal by-products for pets

Process control in feed mills

Not applicable (n. a.)

Compound feeding stuffs

Feed for farm animals (mainly poultry) and pets

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Sampling is performed according EC-Directive 152/2009/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

See above

Process control in feed mills

See above

Compound feeding stuffs

See above

Definition of positive finding

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Imported feed material of plant origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Imported feed material of animal origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Process control in feed mills

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Compound feeding stuffs

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Bacteriological method: ISO 6579:2002; sample weight: 25 g (samples related to suspected lots or cases are analysed by testing several subsamples in parallel); all isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella are serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Other: as above

Imported feed material of plant animal

Other: as above

Imported feed material of animal origin

Other: as above

Process control in feed mills

Other: as above

Compound feeding stuffs

Other: as above

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

National legislation: BGBl. Nr. 139/1999, as last amendet by BGBl. Nr. 87/2005 (Futtermittelgesetz 1999, § 3) and BGBl. Nr. 316/2010 (Futtermittelverordnung 2010) containing general requirements for feedingstuffs and BGBl. II Nr. 100/2007 (Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007).

EC: VO (EG) 183/2005 (Futtermittelhygieneverordnung) and VO (EG) 882/2004 (Kontrollverordnung) with regard to salmonella monitoring, general requirements for feed material and compound feed, coordinated annual control program

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings

Domestic feed material of plant origin

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

See above

Process control in feed mills

See above

Compound feeding stuffs

See above

Notification system in place

The Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) notifies the local authorities and the system has been in place since 1979. The legal basis of the RASFF is Regulation EC/178/2002.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the last 20 years, the quality of feed has improved due to the increase of numbers of farms, processing plants and retailer using HACCP concepts, traceability of contaminated feed/components of feed and palletizing feed/contaminated feed.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 11 *Salmonella* spp. in feed material of animal origin, 2013

Feed	Sampling Stage	Sampling Unit	Sample Origin	Sample Weight	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp., unspecified
Feed material of land animal origin - blood	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	EU	25g	1	0
Feed material of marine animal origin - fish meal	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	2	0
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	2	0
			EU	25g	1	0
Feed material of marine animal origin - fish oil	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0

Sampling context: Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

Table 12 *Salmonella* spp. in compound feeding stuff, 2013

Feed	Sampling Stage	Sampling Unit	Sample Origin	Sample Weight	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp., unspecified	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Typhimurium</i>
Compound feedingstuffs for cattle - final product - pelleted	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for horses - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs - final product	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	5	0	0	0
	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	2	0	0	0
	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	8	0	0	0
			EU	25g	1	0	0	0
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	58	0	0	0
			EU	25g	6	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs - final product - pelleted	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	2	0	0	0
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	6	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - broilers - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	6	0	0	0
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	6	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - broilers - final product - pelleted	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	0	0
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	2	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	12	0	0	0
	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	0	0
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	13	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens - final product - pelleted	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	3	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - pigeons	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	2	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	5	0	0	0
	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	0	0
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	8	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) - final product - pelleted	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	2	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys - final product - non-pelleted/meal	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	3	0	0	0
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	2	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys - final product - pelleted	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	0	0
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	0	0
Pet food	at processing plant	single (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	0	0
	at retail	single (food/feed)	AT	25g	6	0	0	0
Pet food - dog snacks (pig ears, chewing bones)	at processing plant	single (food/feed)	AT	25g	4	0	0	0
	at retail	single (food/feed)	AT	25g	33	1	0	1
			EU	25g	8	1	1	0
			XE	25g	1	0	0	0
Pet food - final product - pelleted	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	0	0

Sampling context: Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

Table 13 *Salmonella* spp. in other feed matter, 2013

Feed	Sampling Stage	Sampling Unit	Sample Origin	Sample Weight	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Livingstone	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Nyborg	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Oranienburg	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Orion	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Senftenberg
Feed material of cereal grain origin	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Feed material of cereal grain origin - barley derived	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - groundnut derived	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - linseed derived	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	13	1	0	0	0	0	1
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - other oil seeds derived	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - rape seed derived	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	7	0	0	0	0	0	0
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	32	0	0	0	0	0	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - soya (bean) derived	at farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	5	0	0	0	0	0	0
	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	9	1	0	0	0	1	0
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	57	1	0	0	1	0	0
			EU	25g	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - sunflower seed derived	at feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	at processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	5	1	0	1	0	0	0
	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	5	1	1	0	0	0	0
Other feed material - legume seeds and similar products	at retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25g	1	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sampling context: Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

4.1.6. *Salmonella* serovars and phage type distribution

The methods of collecting, isolating and testing of *Salmonella* isolates are described in the chapters above respectively for each animal species, foodstuffs and in humans. The serotype and phage type distributions can be used to investigate the sources of the *Salmonella* infections in humans. Findings of same serovars and phagetypes in human cases and in foodstuffs or animals may indicate that the food category or animal species in question serves as a source of human infections. However, as information of the potential source of infection is not available, conclusions have to be made with caution.

Table 14 *Salmonella* serovars in humans, food and animals (EMS/NRC), 2013

Serovars	humans	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus)	Meat from turkey	Meat from geese	Meat from poultry, unspecified	red meat	Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Spices and herbs	broilers	layers	turkeys
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped	1,433	16	7	2	13	1	2	1	110	65	36
S. Enteritidis	607	-	-	-	1	-	1	-	2	14	-
S. Typhimurium	211	-	-	1	-	1	1	-	15	9	1
S. Stanley	92	-	1	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	9
S. 1,4,[5],12:i:-	68	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Infantis	67	15	2	-	7	-	-	-	37	-	2
Salmonella spp., unspecified	30	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Newport	28	-	2	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Saintpaul	17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3
S. Indiana	15	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Paratyphi B	15	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Kentucky	14	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Oranienburg	14	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
S. Agona	13	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	1
S. Montevideo	13	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	8	2	1
S. Virchow	11	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Bareilly	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. group B	9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Napoli	9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Bovismorbificans	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
S. Braenderup	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Kottbus	8	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	6	1	3
S. Mbandaka	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	9	13
S. Derby	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Senftenberg	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	23	12	-
S. Rissen	6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Schwarzengrund	6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Abony	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-
S. Corvallis	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Hadar	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Muenchen	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Stanleyville	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Bredeney	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Coeln	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. enterica subsp. diarizonae	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. enterica subsp. salamae	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Mississippi	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Thompson	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	1	-
S. Give	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	5	-
S. group D	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Javiana	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Serovars	humans	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus)	Meat from turkey	Meat from geese	Meat from poultry, unspecified	red meat	Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Spices and herbs	broilers	layers	turkeys
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped	1,433	16	7	2	13	1	2	1	110	65	36
<i>S. Paratyphi</i>	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Tennessee</i>	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	2	1
<i>S. Umbilo</i>	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Weltevreden</i>	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Albany</i>	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Bispebjerg</i>	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Cerro</i>	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Eastbourne</i>	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Goldcoast</i>	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Havana</i>	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Lexington</i>	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. London</i>	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Poona</i>	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-
<i>S. Rubislaw</i>	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Adelaide</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Afula</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Ago</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Altona</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Apapa</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Blockley</i>	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Brandenburg</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Choleraesuis</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Cullingworth</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Dublin</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Durham</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Edinburg</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. enterica</i> subsp. <i>arizonae</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. enterica</i> subsp. <i>enterica</i> - rough	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-
<i>S. enterica</i> subsp. <i>houtenae</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Friedrichsfelde</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. group C</i> - <i>S. group C1</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. group D</i> - <i>S. group D1</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. group E</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Grumpensis</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Haifa</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Heidelberg</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Hull</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Isangi</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Isaszeg</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Kambole</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. Kapemba</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Serovars	humans	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus)	Meat from turkey	Meat from geese	Meat from poultry, unspecified	red meat	Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Spices and herbs	broilers	layers	turkeys
Number of <i>Salmonella</i> isolates serotyped	1,433	16	7	2	13	1	2	1	110	65	36
S. Kedougou	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Kenya	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Koketime	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Litchfield	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Liverpool	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Livingstone	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Manhattan	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Mikawasima	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Muenster	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Nigeria	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Oslo	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Panama	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Sandiego	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Strathcona	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Telelkebir	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
S. Anatum	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-
S. group C1, monophasic strain	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-
S. Llandoff	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-
S. Nyborg	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	4	1
S. Worthington	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-

Data source: EMS/NRC Salmonella as of April 30, 2014

Table 15 S. Enteritidis phage types in humans, food and animals (EMS/NRC), 2013

Phagetypes S. Enteritidis	humans	Meat from poultry, unspecified	Other processed food products and prepared dishes	broilers	layers	turkeys
Number of Salmonella isolates serotyped	607	1	1	2	15	0
PT 8	197	-	-	1	3	-
PT 4	111	-	1	-	8	-
PT 14b	42	-	-	-	-	-
PT 21	40	-	-	-	1	-
PT 1	34	-	-	-	-	-
RDNC	34	-	-	1	-	-
not typed	19	-	-	-	-	-
PT 2	15	-	-	-	-	-
PT 5	15	-	-	-	-	-
PT 6	13	-	-	-	-	-
PT 29	10	-	-	-	-	-
PT 3	10	1	-	-	-	-
PT 11	8	-	-	-	-	-
PT 6c	7	-	-	-	1	-
PT 12	6	-	-	-	-	-
PT 15a	5	-	-	-	-	-
PT 21c	5	-	-	-	-	-
PT 35	5	-	-	-	-	-
PT 3a	5	-	-	-	-	-
PT 13a	3	-	-	-	-	-
PT 1b	3	-	-	-	-	-
PT 23	3	-	-	-	2	-
PT 6a	3	-	-	-	-	-
PT 6b	3	-	-	-	-	-
PT 14c	2	-	-	-	-	-
PT 1d	2	-	-	-	-	-
PT 13	1	-	-	-	-	-
PT 20a	1	-	-	-	-	-
PT 32a	1	-	-	-	-	-
PT 37	1	-	-	-	-	-
PT 3b	1	-	-	-	-	-
PT 4b	1	-	-	-	-	-
PT 55	1	-	-	-	-	-

Data source: EMS/NRC Salmonella as of April 30, 2014

Table 16 S. Typhimurium definitive types in humans, food and animals (EMS), 2013

Lysotypes S. Typhimurium	humans	Meat from geese	red meat	Other processed food products and prepared dishes	broilers	layers	turkeys
Number of Salmonella isolates serotyped	211	1	1	1	15	9	1
DT 193	50	-	-	-	-	1	-
DT 104	30	-	-	-	-	-	-
RDNC	30	-	-	-	2	2	1
DT 120	27	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT U302	13	-	-	-	-	-	-
not typed	12	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 1	9	-	-	-	1	-	-
U 277	8	-	-	-	-	-	-
Not typeable	5	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 12	3	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 194	3	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 8	3	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 85	3	1	1	-	-	-	-
U 311	3	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 46	2	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 7a	2	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 99	2	-	-	1	-	-	-
DT 141	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 36	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 41	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 66	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 80	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT U291	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
DT 104H	-	-	-	-	-	1	-
DT 104I	-	-	-	-	1	1	-
DT 166	-	-	-	-	3	-	-
DT 2	-	-	-	-	8	-	-
U	-	-	-	-	-	4	-

Data source: EMS/NRC Salmonella as of April 30, 2014

Table 17 S. Typhimurium, monophasic, definitive types in humans, food and animals (EMS), 2013

Lysotypes S.Typhimurium, monophasic phagetypes	humans	Meat from geese	red meat	Other processed food products and prepared dishes	broilers	layers	turkeys
Number of Salmonella isolates serotyped	68	0	0	0	0	0	0
DT 193	50	-	-	-	-	-	-
U311	11	-	-	-	-	-	-
RDNC	7	-	-	-	-	-	-

Data source: EMS/NRC Salmonella as of April 30, 2014

4.1.7. Antimicrobial resistance in *Salmonella* spp. isolates

Antimicrobial resistance is the ability of certain microorganisms to survive or grow in the presence of a given concentration of antimicrobial agent that usually would kill or inhibit the microorganism species in question. Antimicrobial resistant *Salmonella* strains may be transferred from animals or foodstuffs to humans.

A. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. in humans

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2013 the number of isolates sent to the National Reference Centre for Salmonella declined by another 21% as compared to 2012. The resistance rates increased in 2013.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The resistance rates increased in 2013 due to a rise in the number of multiresistant *S. Typhimurium* (e.g. DT193, DT104L, DT120) and *S. Infantis* strains while the number of fully susceptible *S. Enteritidis* isolates decreased remarkably. High level resistances against ciprofloxacin and third generation cephalosporins (cefotaxime) were still extremely rare in comparison to rates reported within the EU.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

Annual publication of the results in the NRL-S Report (Jahresbericht) and the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES)

B. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. in animals and food

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

All *Salmonella* spp. isolated in veterinary and food laboratories as well as all primary isolates from humans were sent to the NRC-S where the susceptibility testing was performed using the disk diffusion method. In addition to that, *Salmonella* isolates from the control programmes in laying hens, broilers and turkeys (all unique strains isolated from one epidemiological unit) were also subjected to MIC-testing.

Type of specimen taken

For animals and food see chapters *Salmonella* spp. in animal species and *Salmonella* spp. in food.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

For animals and food see chapters *Salmonella* spp. in animal species and *Salmonella* spp. in food.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

All *Salmonella* spp. isolated in veterinary and food laboratories as well as all primary isolates from humans were sent to the NRC-S where the susceptibility testing was performed using the disk diffusion method. According to Commission Decision 2007/407/EC all unique strains isolated in the course of the control programme (identical strains from one epidemiological unit only once) were subjected to microdilution susceptibility testing.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

See chapter salmonellosis in humans; for the MIC testing CLSI standards are used, applying EU-RL (European Reference Laboratory) cut-off values.

Laboratory used for detection of resistance

National Reference Centre for Salmonella, AGES Graz

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

All *Salmonella* isolates were susceptibility tested (disc diffusion) according to EUCAST. Isolates obtained in course of the control programs were tested according CD Nr. 2007/407/EC. See corresponding tables! Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For *Salmonella* this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazole.

Control program/mechanisms

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

Annual publication of the results in the NRL-S Report (Jahresbericht) and the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES)

Table 18 Breakpoints for antibiotic resistance of *Salmonella* spp., 2013

Test method used					
Disc diffusion	x				
E-test					
Agar dilution					
Broth dilution	x				
Standards used for testing		The methods are used for investigation of isolates from			
EUCAST	x	Feedingstuff	x (Dilution method)		
CLSI	x	Animals	x (Dilution method)		
EN ISO 20776-1		Food	x (Dilution method)		
		Humans	x (Diffusion method)		
<i>Salmonella</i>	Dilution method		Diffusion method		
	Resistant >		Resistant ≤		
	Standard for cut-off	concentration (µg/ml)	Standard for breakpoint	zone diameter (mm)	
Tetracyclines					
Tetracycline	CLSI	8	CLSI	11	
Amphenicols					
Chloramphenicol	EUCAST	16	EUCAST	16	
Florphenicol	EU-RL	16	-	-	
Penicillins					
Ampicillin	EUCAST	8	EUCAST	13	
Cephalosporins					
Cefotaxim	EUCAST	0.5	EUCAST	16	
Ceftazidime	EUCAST	2	EUCAST	18	
Fluoroquinolones					
Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST	0.06	EUCAST	18	
Sulfonamides					
Sulfamethoxazol	EU-RL	256	CLSI	12	
Aminoglycosides					
Streptomycin	EUCAST	16	EUCAST	11	
Gentamicin	EUCAST	2	EUCAST	13	
Kanamycin	EU-RL	4	CLSI	13	
Quinolones					
Nalidixic acid	EUCAST	16	CLSI	13	
Polymyxine					
Colistin	EU-RL	2/8 ¹	-	-	
Trimethoprim	EU-RL	2	EUCAST	14	

¹ The EUCAST ECOFF (>2) for colistin was applied for *S. Typhimurium*, but for *S. Enteritidis* the ECOFF >8 was applied as recommended by Agersøe et al, 2011

EU-RL = European Reference Laboratory

Table 19 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* spp. in humans and food (diffusion method, clinical breakpoint; for animals see tables 26-51), 2013

	<i>Salmonella</i> spp.														
	Humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			bovine meat			pig meat		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	1495			100			64			14			4		
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	%r	n
Tetracyclines															
Tetracycline	1,495	18.4	275	100	73	73	64	59.4	38	14	42.9	6	4	25	1
Amphenicols															
Chloramphenicol	1,495	3.8	57	100	0	0	64	1.6	1	14	28.6	4	4	0	0
Penicillins															
Ampicillin	1,495	15.1	226	100	2	2	64	40.6	26	14	42.9	6	4	25	1
Cephalosporins															
Cefotaxim	1,495	0.7	10	100	0	0	64	0	0	14	0	0	4	0	0
Fluoroquinolones															
Ciprofloxacin	1,495	1.0	15	100	2	2	64	3.1	2	14	0	0	4	0	0
Sulfonamides															
Sulfamethoxazol	1,495	17.1	261	100	75	75	64	26.6	17	14	28.6	4	4	25	1
Aminoglycosides															
Streptomycin	1,495	17.8	266	100	72	72	64	28.1	18	14	35.7	5	4	50	2
Gentamicin	1,495	1.9	28	100	3	3	64	6.3	4	14	0	0	4	0	0
Kanamycin	1,495	0.5	7	100	0	0	64	0	0	14	7.1	1	4	0	0
Quinolones															
Nalidixic acid	1,495	17.7	265	100	82	82	64	71.9	46	14	42.9	6	4	0	0
Trimethoprim	1,495	3.0	45	100	3	3	64	3.1	2	14	0	0	4	0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	1,495	65.9	985	100	18	18	64	13	8	14	50	7	4	50	2
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	1,495	14.6	218	100	7	7	64	26.6	17	14	7.1	1	4	25.0	1
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	1,495	1.5	22	100	0	0	64	12.5	8	14	0	0	4	0.0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	1,495	2.9	44	100	5	5	64	23	15	14	14.3	2	4	0.0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	1,495	9.1	136	100	63	63	64	14.1	9	14	0	0	4	25.0	1
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	1,495	6.0	90	100	7	7	64	10.9	7	14	28.6	4	4	0.0	0

Table 20 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* in humans, animals and food (diffusion method, clinical breakpoint; for animals see tables 26-51), 2013

	S. Enteritidis														
	Humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			bovine meat			pig meat		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	650			0			1			0			0		
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n
Tetracyclines															
Tetracycline	650	1.4	9				1	0	0						
Amphenicols															
Chloramphenicol	650	0.2	1				1	0	0						
Penicillins															
Ampicillin	650	1.4	9				1	0	0						
Cephalosporins															
Cefotaxim	650	0.3	2				1	0	0						
Fluoroquinolones															
Ciprofloxacin	650	0	0				1	0	0						
Sulfonamides															
Sulfamethoxazol	650	0.2	1				1	0	0						
Aminoglycosides															
Streptomycin	650	0.0	0				1	0	0						
Gentamicin	650	0.0	0				1	0	0						
Kanamycin	650	0	0				1	0	0						
Quinolones															
Nalidixic acid	650	10.0	65				1	100	1						
Trimethoprim	650	0.3	2				1	0	0						
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	650	87.7	570				1	0	0						
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	650	11.4	74				1	100	1						
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	650	0.6	4				1	0	0						
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	650	0.2	1				1	0	0						
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	650	0.2	1				1	0	0						
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	650	0.0	0				1	0	0						

Table 21 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint; for animals see tables 26-51), 2013

	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>														
	Humans			Broiler meat			Turkey meat			Bovine meat			Pig meat		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	218			1			3			5			2		
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n
Tetracyclines															
Tetracycline	218	40.8	89	1	0	0	3	33.3	1	5	80	4	2	50	1
Amphenicols															
Chloramphenicol	218	18.8	41	1	0	0	3	33.3	1	5	80	4	2	0	0
Penicillins															
Ampicillin	218	37.2	81	1	0	0	3	33.3	1	5	80	4	2	50	1
Cephalosporins															
Cefotaxim	218	0.0	0	1	0	0	3	0	0	5	0	0	2	0	0
Fluoroquinolones															
Ciprofloxacin	218	0	0	1	0	0	3	0	0	5	0	0	2	0	0
Sulfonamides															
Sulfamethoxazol	218	37.2	81	1	0	0	3	33.3	1	5	80	4	2	50	1
Aminoglycosides															
Streptomycin	218	36.2	79	1	0	0	3	33.3	1	5	80	4	2	50	1
Gentamicin	218	1.8	4	1	0	0	3	0	0	5	0	0	2	0	0
Kanamycin	218	0.5	1	1	0	0	3	0	0	5	0	0	2	0	0
Quinolones															
Nalidixic acid	218	4.1	9	1	0	0	3	33.3	1	5	80	4	2	0	0
Trimethoprim	218	5.0	11	1	0	0	3	0	0	5	0	0	2	0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	218	51.4	112	1	100	1	3	66.7	2	5	20	1	2	50	1
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	218	10.1	22	1	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	5	0	0	2	0	0
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	218	1.8	4	1	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	5	0	0	2	0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	218	3.2	7	1	0	0	3	0.0	0	5	0	0	2	0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	218	13.3	29	1	0.0	0	3	0.0	0	5	0	0	2	50	1
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	218	20.2	44	1	0.0	0	3	33.3	1	5	80	4	2	0	0

Table 22 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* monophasic strain in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint; for animals see tables 26-51), 2013

	monophasic <i>S. Group B</i> (1,4,5,12 : i : -)														
	Humans			Broiler meat			Turkey meat			Bovine meat			Pig meat		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	79			0			0			0			0		
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n
Tetracyclines															
Tetracycline	79	86.1	68												
Amphenicols															
Chloramphenicol	79	3.8	3												
Penicillins															
Ampicillin	79	94.9	75												
Cephalosporins															
Cefotaxim	79	3.8	3												
Fluoroquinolones															
Ciprofloxacin	79	0.0	0												
Sulfonamides															
Sulfamethoxazol	79	96.2	76												
Aminoglycosides															
Streptomycin	79	94.9	75												
Gentamicin	79	0.0	0												
Kanamycin	79	2.5	2												
Quinolones															
Nalidixic acid	79	0.0	0												
Trimethoprim															
Trimethoprim	79	6.3	5												
Number of multiresistant isolates															
	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	79	3.8	3												
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	79	0.0	0												
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	79	0.0	0												
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	79	10.1	8												
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	79	75.9	60												
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	79	10.1	8												

Table 23 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Stanley* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint; for animals see tables 26-51), 2013

	<i>S. Stanley</i>														
	Humans			Broiler meat			Turkey meat			Bovine meat			Pig meat		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	101			1			12			0			0		
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n
Tetracyclines															
Tetracycline	101	2.0	2	1	0	0	12	0	0						
Amphenicols															
Chloramphenicol	101	2.0	2	1	0	0	12	0	0						
Penicillins															
Ampicillin	101	12.9	13	1	0	0	12	16.7	2						
Cephalosporins															
Cefotaxim	101	0.0	0	1	0	0	12	0	0						
Fluoroquinolones															
Ciprofloxacin	101	0.0	0	1	0	0	12	0	0						
Sulfonamides															
Sulfamethoxazol	101	5	5	1	0	0	12	0	0						
Aminoglycosides															
Streptomycin	101	2.0	2	1	0	0	12	0	0						
Gentamicin	101	0	0	1	0	0	12	0	0						
Kanamycin	101	0	0	1	0	0	12	0	0						
Quinolones															
Nalidixic acid	101	90.1	91	1	0	0	12	0	0						
Trimethoprim	101	1.0	1	1	100	1	12	100	12						
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	101	7.9	8	1	0	0	12	0.0	0						
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	101	79.2	80	1	100	1	12	83.3	10						
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	101	7.9	8	1	0	0	12	16.7	2						
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	101	3	3	1	0	0	12	0	0						
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	101	0.0	0	1	0	0	12	0	0						
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	101	2.0	2	1	0	0	12	0	0						

Table 24 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Infantis* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint; for animals see tables 26-51), 2013

	<i>S. Infantis</i>														
	Humans			Broiler meat			Turkey meat			Bovine meat			Pig meat		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	71			78			9			0			0		
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n
Tetracyclines															
Tetracycline	71	62.0	44	78	91	71	9	100	9						
Amphenicols															
Chloramphenicol	71	4.2	3	78	0	0	9	0	0						
Penicillins															
Ampicillin	71	5.6	4	78	1.3	1	9	0	0						
Cephalosporins															
Cefotaxim	71	2.8	2	78	0	0	9	0	0						
Fluoroquinolones															
Ciprofloxacin	71	1.4	1	78	1.3	1	9	0	0						
Sulfonamides															
Sulfamethoxazol	71	63.4	45	78	93.6	73	9	100	9						
Aminoglycosides															
Streptomycin	71	62.0	44	78	89.7	70	9	100	9						
Gentamicin	71	2.8	2	78	2.6	2	9	0	0						
Kanamycin	71	0	0	78	6.4	5	9	0	0						
Quinolones															
Nalidixic acid	71	64.8	46	78	98.7	77	9	100	9						
Trimethoprim															
Trimethoprim	71	4.2	3	78	3.8	3	9	0	0						
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	71	33.8	24	78	1	1	9	0	0						
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	71	1.4	1	78	5.1	4	9	0	0						
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	71	1.4	1	78	0.0	0	9	0	0						
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	71	2.8	2	78	6	5	9	0	0						
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	71	54.9	39	78	79.5	62	9	100	9						
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	71	5.6	4	78	7.7	6	9	0	0						

Table 25 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than Enteritidis, Typhimurium, monophasic S. group B, S. Stanley and S. Infantis in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint; for animals see tables 26-51), 2013

	other serotypes than S. Enteritidis and S. Typhimurium, monophasic S. Group B (1,4,5,12 : i : -), S. Stanley and S. Infantis														
	Humans			Broiler meat			Turkey meat			Bovine meat			Pig meat		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	376			20			39			9			2		
Antimicrobials:	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n	N	r%	n
Tetracyclines															
Tetracycline	376	16.8	63	20	10.0	2	39	72	28	9	22	2	2	0	0
Amphenicols															
Chloramphenicol	376	1.9	7	20	0.0	0	39	0.0	0	9	0	0	2	0	0
Penicillins															
Ampicillin	376	11.7	44	20	5	1	39	59.0	23	9	22	2	2	0	0
Cephalosporins															
Cefotaxim	376	0.8	3	20	0	0	39	0	0	9	0	0	2	0	0
Fluoroquinolones															
Ciprofloxacin	376	3.7	14	20	5.0	1	39	5.1	2	9	0	0	2	0	0
Sulfonamides															
Sulfamethoxazol	376	14.1	53	20	10.0	2	39	17.9	7	9	0	0	2	0	0
Aminoglycosides															
Streptomycin	376	17.6	66	20	10.0	2	39	20.5	8	9	11	1	2	50	1
Gentamicin	376	5.9	22	20	5.0	1	39	10.3	4	9	0	0	2	0	0
Kanamycin	376	1.1	4	20	0	0	39	5.1	2	9	0	0	2	0	0
Quinolones															
Nalidixic acid	376	14.4	54	20	20.0	4	39	59.0	23	9	22	2	2	0	0
Trimethoprim	376	6.1	23	20	0	0	39	5	2	9	0	0	2	0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	376	71.3	268	20	80.0	16	39	15.4	6	9	67	6	2	50	1
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	376	10.9	41	20	10.0	2	39	15.4	6	9	11	1	2	50	1
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	376	1.3	5	20	0	0	39	15.4	6	9	0	0	2	0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	376	6.1	23	20	0.0	0	39	38.5	15	9	22	2	2	0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	376	1.9	7	20	5	1	39	0.0	0	9	0	0	2	0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	376	8.5	32	20	5	1	39	15.4	6	9	0	0	2	0	0

Table 26 Qualitative table: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* serotypes derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method, cut-off values), 2013

	Salmonella spp.		S. Enteritidis		S. Typhimurium		S. Give		S. Mbandaka		S. Senftenberg		all other serovares								
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes		yes		yes		yes		yes		yes		yes								
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	65		15		9		5		9		12		15								
Antimicrobials	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	65	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	12	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	65	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	12	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	65	13.8%	9	15	6.7%	1	9	22.2%	2	5	0.0%	0	9	33.3%	3	12	8.3%	1	15	13.3%	2
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	65	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	12	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	65	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	12	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	65	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	12	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	65	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	12	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	65	7.7%	5	15	0.0%	0	9	44.4%	4	5	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	12	0.0%	0	15	6.7%	1
Penicillins - Ampicillin	65	7.7%	5	15	0.0%	0	9	55.6%	5	5	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	12	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0
Polymyxins - Colistin	65	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	12	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	65	7.7%	5	15	0.0%	0	9	44.4%	4	5	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	12	0.0%	0	15	6.7%	1
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	65	9.2%	6	15	0.0%	0	9	66.7%	6	5	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	12	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	65	10.8%	7	15	6.7%	1	9	11.1%	1	5	0.0%	0	9	44.4%	4	12	0.0%	0	15	6.7%	1
Trimethoprim	65	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	12	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0
Number of multiresistant isolates																					
fully sensitive	65	72.3%	47	15	93.3%	14	9	33.3%	3	5	100.0%	5	9	33.3%	3	12	91.7%	11	15	73.3%	11
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	65	15.4%	10	15	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0	9	55.6%	5	12	8.3%	1	15	26.7%	4
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	65	4.6%	3	15	6.7%	1	9	11.1%	1	5	0.0%	0	9	11.1%	1	12	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	65	6.2%	4	15	0.0%	0	9	44.4%	4	5	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	12	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	65	1.5%	1	15	0.0%	0	9	11.1%	1	5	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	12	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	65	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	12	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0

N = number of isolates tested, r% = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For *Salmonella* this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazole

Table 27 Qualitative table: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* serotypes derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method, cut-off values), 2013

	Salmonella spp.		S. Enteritidis		S. Typhimurium		S. Kottbus		S. Infantis		S. Montevideo		S. Senftenberg		all other serovares									
	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N								
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes		yes		yes		yes		yes		yes		yes		yes									
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	110		2		15		6		37		9		23		18									
Antimicrobials	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	110	0.0%	0	2	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	6	0.0%	0	37	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	23	0.0%	0	18	0.0%	0
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	110	0.0%	0	2	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	6	0.0%	0	37	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	23	0.0%	0	18	0.0%	0
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	110	34.5%	38	2	0.0%	0	15	6.7%	1	6	0.0%	0	37	91.9%	34	9	11.1%	1	23	0.0%	0	18	11.1%	2
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	110	0.9%	1	2	0.0%	0	15	6.7%	1	6	0.0%	0	37	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	23	0.0%	0	18	0.0%	0
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	110	0.9%	1	2	0.0%	0	15	6.7%	1	6	0.0%	0	37	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	23	0.0%	0	18	0.0%	0
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	110	0.0%	0	2	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	6	0.0%	0	37	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	23	0.0%	0	18	0.0%	0
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	110	0.0%	0	2	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	6	0.0%	0	37	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	23	0.0%	0	18	0.0%	0
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	110	39.1%	43	2	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	6	100.0%	6	37	91.9%	34	9	11.1%	1	23	0.0%	0	18	11.1%	2
Penicillins - Ampicillin	110	7.3%	8	2	0.0%	0	15	13.3%	2	6	0.0%	0	37	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	23	26.1%	6	18	0.0%	0
Polymyxins - Colistin	110	0.9%	1	2	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	6	0.0%	0	37	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	23	0.0%	0	18	5.6%	1
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	110	39.1%	43	2	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	6	100.0%	6	37	91.9%	34	9	11.1%	1	23	0.0%	0	18	11.1%	2
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	110	34.5%	38	2	0.0%	0	15	6.7%	1	6	0.0%	0	37	91.9%	34	9	11.1%	1	23	0.0%	0	18	11.1%	2
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	110	37.3%	41	2	0.0%	0	15	6.7%	1	6	0.0%	0	37	91.9%	34	9	11.1%	1	23	0.0%	0	18	27.8%	5
Trimethoprim	110	0.0%	0	2	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	6	0.0%	0	37	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	23	0.0%	0	18	0.0%	0
Number of multiresistant isolates																								
fully sensitive	110	50.9%	56	2	100.0%	2	15	86.7%	13	6	0.0%	0	37	8.1%	3	9	88.9%	8	23	73.9%	17	18	72.2%	13
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	110	14.5%	16	2	0.0%	0	15	6.7%	1	6	100.0%	6	37	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	23	26.1%	6	18	16.7%	3
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	110	0.0%	0	2	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	6	0.0%	0	37	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	23	0.0%	0	18	0.0%	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	110	0.0%	0	2	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	6	0.0%	0	37	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	23	0.0%	0	18	0.0%	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	110	33.6%	37	2	0.0%	0	15	0.0%	0	6	0.0%	0	37	91.9%	34	9	11.1%	1	23	0.0%	0	18	11.1%	2
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	110	0.9%	1	2	0.0%	0	15	6.7%	1	6	0.0%	0	37	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	23	0.0%	0	18	0.0%	0

N = number of isolates tested, r% = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For Salmonella this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazole

Table 28 Qualitative table: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* serotypes derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method, cut-off values), 2013

	Salmonella spp.		S. Enteritidis		S. Typhimurium		S. Infantis		S. Kottbus		S. Mbandaka		S. Stanley		S. Saintpaul		all other serovares										
	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no	yes	no									
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	36		0		1		2		3		13		3		9		5										
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	36		0		1		2		3		13		3		9		5										
Antimicrobials	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	36	0.0%	0	0	0.0%	0	1	0.0%	0	2	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	13	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	36	2.8%	1	0	0.0%	0	1	0.0%	0	2	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	13	7.7%	1	3	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	36	27.8%	10	0	0.0%	0	1	100.0%	1	2	100.0%	2	3	0.0%	0	13	30.8%	4	3	100.0%	3	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	36	0.0%	0	0	0.0%	0	1	0.0%	0	2	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	13	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	36	0.0%	0	0	0.0%	0	1	0.0%	0	2	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	13	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	36	0.0%	0	0	0.0%	0	1	0.0%	0	2	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	13	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	36	0.0%	0	0	0.0%	0	1	0.0%	0	2	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	13	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	36	38.9%	14	0	0.0%	0	1	0.0%	0	2	100.0%	2	3	0.0%	0	13	0.0%	0	3	100.0%	3	9	100.0%	9	5	0.0%	0
Penicillins - Ampicillin	36	11.1%	4	0	0.0%	0	1	100.0%	1	2	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	13	0.0%	0	3	100.0%	3	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0
Polymyxins - Colistin	36	0.0%	0	0	0.0%	0	1	0.0%	0	2	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	13	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	36	38.9%	14	0	0.0%	0	1	0.0%	0	2	100.0%	2	3	0.0%	0	13	0.0%	0	3	100.0%	3	9	100.0%	9	5	0.0%	0
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	36	16.7%	6	0	0.0%	0	1	100.0%	1	2	100.0%	2	3	0.0%	0	13	0.0%	0	3	100.0%	3	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	36	44.4%	16	0	0.0%	0	1	100.0%	1	2	100.0%	2	3	0.0%	0	13	100.0%	13	3	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0
Trimethoprim	36	11.1%	4	0	0.0%	0	1	100.0%	1	2	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	13	0.0%	0	3	100.0%	3	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0
Number of multiresistant isolates																											
fully sensitive	36	22.2%	8	0	0.0%	0	1	0.0%	0	2	0.0%	0	3	100.0%	3	13	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	100.0%	5
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	36	50.0%	18	0	0.0%	0	1	0.0%	0	2	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	13	69.2%	9	3	0.0%	0	9	100.0%	9	5	0.0%	0
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	36	11.1%	4	0	0.0%	0	1	0.0%	0	2	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	13	30.8%	4	3	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	36	0.0%	0	0	0.0%	0	1	0.0%	0	2	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	13	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	36	5.6%	2	0	0.0%	0	1	0.0%	0	2	100.0%	2	3	0.0%	0	13	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	36	11.1%	4	0	0.0%	0	1	100.0%	1	2	0.0%	0	3	0.0%	0	13	0.0%	0	3	100.0%	3	9	0.0%	0	5	0.0%	0

N = number of isolates tested, r% = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For *Salmonella* this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazole

Table 29 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* spp. derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2013

Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		<i>Salmonella</i> spp. layer control program		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
		yes	no	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		65		n																				
Antimicrobials	N	%r	n																					
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	65	0.0%	0					22	37	6														
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	65	0.0%	0									65												
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	65	13.8%	9								3	15	20	18	3	2	3	1						
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	65	0.0%	0									19	46											
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	65	0.0%	0								4	58	3											
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	65	0.0%	0				24	41																
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	65	0.0%	0						36	28	1													
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	65	7.7%	5		13	47		2	3															
Penicillins - Ampicillin	65	7.7%	5								34	26					5							
Polymyxins - Colistin	65	0.0%	0									59	6											
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	65	7.7%	5									56	4					5						
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	65	9.2%	6										1	2	38	17	1						6	
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	65	10.8%	7								15	43					7							
Trimethoprim	65	0.0%	0							65														

Table 30 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Enteritidis derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2013

		S. Enteritidis laying hens, control program		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		15																					
				≤< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
Antimicrobials		N	%r	n	n																		
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin		15	0.0%	0					10	4	1												
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin		15	0.0%	0									15										
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin		15	6.7%	1								3	10	1			1						
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol		15	0.0%	0									11	4									
Amphenicols - Florfenicol		15	0.0%	0								3	12										
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime		15	0.0%	0			6	9															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim		15	0.0%	0					13	2													
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin		15	0.0%	0			15																
Penicillins - Ampicillin		15	0.0%	0							3	12											
Polymyxins - Colistin		15	0.0%	0								9	6										
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid		15	0.0%	0									15										
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol		15	0.0%	0											1	13	1						
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline		15	6.7%	1							8	6						1					
Trimethoprim		15	0.0%	0						15													

Table 31 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Typhimurium derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2013

				S. Typhimurium laying hens, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				9																			
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	9	0.0%	0						3	6													
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	9	0.0%	0										9										
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	9	22.2%	2											3	4		1		1				
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	9	0.0%	0										1	8									
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	9	0.0%	0									1	8										
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	9	0.0%	0				4	5															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	9	0.0%	0						8	1													
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	9	44.4%	4		1	4			1	3													
Penicillins - Ampicillin	9	55.6%	5								1	3					5						
Polymyxins - Colistin	9	0.0%	0									9											
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	9	44.4%	4										5					4					
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	9	66.7%	6													3						6	
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	9	11.1%	1								1	7						1					
Trimethoprim	9	0.0%	0							9													

Table 32 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Give derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2013

				S. Give layer, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				5																			
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
				=<0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
Antimicrobials	N	%r	n	n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	5	0.0%	0						4	1													
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	5	0.0%	0									5											
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	5	0.0%	0										3	2									
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	5	0.0%	0									4	1										
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	5	0.0%	0									5											
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	5	0.0%	0				5																
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	5	0.0%	0					5															
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	5	0.0%	0			5																	
Penicillins - Ampicillin	5	0.0%	0							5													
Polymyxins - Colistin	5	0.0%	0								5												
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	5	0.0%	0									5											
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	5	0.0%	0												3	1	1						
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	5	0.0%	0							3	2												
Trimethoprim	5	0.0%	0						5														

Table 33 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Senftenberg* derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2013

				<i>S. Senftenberg</i> layers, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				12																			
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	12	0.0%	0						3	9													
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	12	0.0%	0										12										
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	12	8.3%	1										3	3	5	1							
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	12	0.0%	0										12										
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	12	0.0%	0										10	2									
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	12	0.0%	0				1	11															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	12	0.0%	0							12													
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	12	0.0%	0		3	9																	
Penicillins - Ampicillin	12	0.0%	0								10	2											
Polymyxins - Colistin	12	0.0%	0									12											
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	12	0.0%	0										11	1									
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	12	0.0%	0													10	2						
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	12	0.0%	0								1	11											
Trimethoprim	12	0.0%	0							12													

Table 34 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Mbandaka* derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2013

				<i>S. Mbandaka</i> layer control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				9																				
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	9	0.0%	0							6	3													
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	9	0.0%	0										9											
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	9	33.3%	3									2	3	1	1				2					
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	9	0.0%	0										9											
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	9	0.0%	0									8	1											
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	9	0.0%	0				2	7																
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	9	0.0%	0						2	7														
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	9	0.0%	0		3	6																		
Penicillins - Ampicillin	9	0.0%	0								6	3												
Polymyxins - Colistin	9	0.0%	0									9												
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	9	0.0%	0										9											
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	9	0.0%	0													3	6							
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	9	44.4%	4									5							4					
Trimethoprim	9	0.0%	0							9														

Table 35 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than Enteritidis, Typhimurium, Senftenberg, GIVE and Mbandaka derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2013

				<i>Salmonella</i> other than Enteritidis, Typhimurium, Infantis, Senftenberg, Agona and Mbandaka (tested isolates: S. Nyborg (3 x), S. Montevideo, S. Tennessee, S. I (Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica) rough (2 x each), S. Agona, S. Thompson, S. Abony, S. Kottbus, S. Worthington, S. monophasic C1-group (1 x each)) laying hens, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	15			Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	15	0.0%	0						6	8	1												
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	15	0.0%	0										15										
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	15	13.3%	2											7	6	1		1					
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	15	0.0%	0										3	12									
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	15	0.0%	0										15										
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	15	0.0%	0				6	9															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	15	0.0%	0						8	6	1												
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	15	6.7%	1		6	8			1														
Penicillins - Ampicillin	15	0.0%	0								9	6											
Polymyxins - Colistin	15	0.0%	0									15											
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	15	6.7%	1										11	3							1		
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	15	0.0%	0											1	1	6	7						
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	15	6.7%	1								2	12									1		
Trimethoprim	15	0.0%	0							15													

Table 36 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* spp. derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2013

				<i>Salmonella</i> spp. broiler, control program																					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				110																					
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048		
				n																					
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	110	0.0%	0						46	63	1														
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	110	0.0%	0											110											
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	110	34.5%	38										6	49	17	28	9	1							
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	110	0.9%	1										23	75	11			1							
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	110	0.9%	1									1	80	25	3	1									
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	110	0.0%	0				36	59	14	1															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	110	0.0%	0						40	60	10														
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	110	39.1%	43		10	56	1		10	26	7														
Penicillins - Ampicillin	110	7.3%	8								42	54	6				8								
Polymyxins - Colistin	110	0.9%	1									109	1												
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	110	39.1%	43										65	2				43							
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	110	34.5%	38											8	23	33	7	1			1		37		
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	110	37.3%	41								30	39				1	8	32							
Trimethoprim	110	0.0%	0							109	1														

Table 37 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2013

Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		S. Enteritidis broiler, control program		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																		
		yes	2	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		N	%r	n	n																	
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin		2	0.0%	0	2																	
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin		2	0.0%	0	2																	
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin		2	0.0%	0	2																	
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol		2	0.0%	0	2																	
Amphenicols - Florfenicol		2	0.0%	0	2																	
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime		2	0.0%	0	2																	
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim		2	0.0%	0	2																	
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin		2	0.0%	0	1	1																
Penicillins - Ampicillin		2	0.0%	0	2																	
Polymyxins - Colistin		2	0.0%	0	2																	
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid		2	0.0%	0	2																	
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol		2	0.0%	0																	1	1
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline		2	0.0%	0	2																	
Trimethoprim		2	0.0%	0	2																	

Table 38 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2013

				<i>S. Typhimurium</i> broiler, control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				15																				
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	15	0.0%	0					3	12															
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	15	0.0%	0										15											
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	15	6.7%	1									2	4	8			1							
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	15	6.7%	1									5	9					1						
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	15	6.7%	1									13	1		1									
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	15	0.0%	0				11	4																
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	15	0.0%	0						13	2														
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	15	0.0%	0		1	14																		
Penicillins - Ampicillin	15	13.3%	2								5	8					2							
Polymyxins - Colistin	15	0.0%	0									15												
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	15	0.0%	0										15											
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	15	6.7%	1											6	7	1							1	
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	15	6.7%	1								4	10				1								
Trimethoprim	15	0.0%	0							15														

Table 39 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Infantis* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2013

<i>S. Infantis</i> broile, control program		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																							
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																								
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	37																								
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=<0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048		
				n																					
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	37	0.0%	0						30	7															
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	37	0.0%	0										37												
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	37	91.9%	34											3		25	8	1							
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	37	0.0%	0										5	21	11										
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	37	0.0%	0										18	16	3										
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	37	0.0%	0				3	20	14																
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	37	0.0%	0						6	25	6														
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	37	91.9%	34		1	2			3	24	7														
Penicillins - Ampicillin	37	0.0%	0								8	24	5												
Polymyxins - Colistin	37	0.0%	0									37													
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	37	91.9%	34										3					34							
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	37	91.9%	34													3						1	33		
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	37	91.9%	34								2	1					7	27							
Trimethoprim	37	0.0%	0							37															

Table 40 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Senftenberg* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2013

<i>S. Senftenberg</i> broiler, control program				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	23																						
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	≤<0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	23	0.0%	0						2	21													
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	23	0.0%	0										23										
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	23	0.0%	0											16	7								
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	23	0.0%	0											23									
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	23	0.0%	0										20	3									
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	23	0.0%	0					23															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	23	0.0%	0						1	20	2												
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	23	0.0%	0		1	22																	
Penicillins - Ampicillin	23	26.1%	6								9	8					6						
Polymyxins - Colistin	23	0.0%	0										23										
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	23	0.0%	0										23										
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	23	0.0%	0												6	15	2						
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	23	0.0%	0								13	10											
Trimethoprim	23	0.0%	0							23													

Table 41 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Montevideo derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2013

S. Montevideo broiler control program				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			=<0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	9			n																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n																					
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	9	0.0%	0					1	8															
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	9	0.0%	0										9											
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	9	11.1%	1											8		1								
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	9	0.0%	0										3	6										
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	9	0.0%	0										7	2										
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	9	0.0%	0				5	4																
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	9	0.0%	0						6	3														
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	9	11.1%	1		1	7				1														
Penicillins - Ampicillin	9	0.0%	0								4	5												
Polymyxins - Colistin	9	0.0%	0									9												
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	9	11.1%	1										8						1					
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	9	11.1%	1											1		6	1							1
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	9	11.1%	1								3	5							1					
Trimethoprim	9	0.0%	0							9														

Table 42 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Kottbus derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2013

S. Kottbus broiler control program				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	6			n																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n																					
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	6	0%	0					2	4															
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	6	0%	0										6											
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	6	0%	0											5	1									
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	6	0%	0									6												
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	6	0%	0								1	5												
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	6	0%	0			6																		
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	6	0%	0					6																
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	6	100%	6					6																
Penicillins - Ampicillin	6	0%	0							5	1													
Polymyxins - Colistin	6	0%	0								6													
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	6	100%	6															6						
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	6	0%	0										1	4	1									
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	6	0%	0							2	4													
Trimethoprim	6	0%	0						6															

Table 43 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than Enteritidis, Typhimurium, Senftenberg, Montevideo, Kottbus and Infantis derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2013

				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
				=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	18	0.0%	0					6	11	1													
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	18	0.0%	0									18											
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	18	11.1%	2									2	13	1	2								
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	18	0.0%	0									2	16										
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	18	0.0%	0									15	3										
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	18	0.0%	0				9	8		1													
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	18	0.0%	0						6	10	2												
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	18	11.1%	2		5	10	1		1	1													
Penicillins - Ampicillin	18	0.0%	0								11	6	1										
Polymyxins - Colistin	18	5.6%	1									17	1										
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	18	11.1%	2										14	2							2		
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	18	11.1%	2												5	6	4	1					2
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	18	27.8%	5								4	9					1	4					
Trimethoprim	18	0.0%	0							17	1												

Table 44 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* spp. derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2013

				<i>Salmonella</i> spp. turkey, control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				36																				
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	36	0.0%	0						12	22	1	1												
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	36	2.8%	1										35	1										
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	36	27.8%	10										1	18	7	2	6	2						
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	36	0.0%	0										11	25										
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	36	0.0%	0										31	5										
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	36	0.0%	0				13	22	1															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	36	0.0%	0						14	22														
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	36	38.9%	14		8	14			12	2														
Penicillins - Ampicillin	36	11.1%	4								24	8					4							
Polymyxins - Colistin	36	0.0%	0									36												
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	36	38.9%	14										19	3					14					
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	36	16.7%	6												1	19	8	2					6	
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	36	44.4%	16								1	19						16						
Trimethoprim	36	11.1%	4							32							4							

Table 45 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Infantis derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2013

S. Infantis turkey, control program		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	1																						
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	= < 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	2	0%	0	2																			
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	2	0%	0	2																			
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	2	100%	2	1 1																			
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	2	0%	0	2																			
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	2	0%	0	2																			
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	2	0%	0	2																			
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	2	0%	0	2																			
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	2	100%	2	2																			
Penicillins - Ampicillin	2	0%	0	2																			
Polymyxins - Colistin	2	0%	0	2																			
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	2	100%	2	2																			
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	2	100%	2	2																			
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	2	100%	2	2																			
Trimethoprim	2	0%	0	2																			

Table 46 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2013

		<i>S. Typhimurium</i> turkey, control program																					
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		1		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
				=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
Antimicrobials:		N	%r	n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	1	0%	0	1																			
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	1	0%	0	1																			
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	1	100%	1	1																			
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	1	0%	0	1																			
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	1	0%	0	1																			
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	1	0%	0	1																			
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	1	0%	0	1																			
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	1	0%	0	1																			
Penicillins - Ampicillin	1	100%	1	1																			
Polymyxins - Colistin	1	0%	0	1																			
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	1	0%	0	1																			
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	1	100%	1	1																			
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	1	100%	1	1																			
Trimethoprim	1	100%	1	1																			

Table 47 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Mbandaka derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2013

				S. Mbandaka turkey, control program																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				13																				
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=<0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	13	0.0%	0							11	1	1												
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	13	7.7%	1										12	1										
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	13	30.8%	4										6	3		2	2							
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	13	0.0%	0										2	11										
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	13	0.0%	0										12	1										
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	13	0.0%	0					13																
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	13	0.0%	0						13															
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	13	0.0%	0		7	6																		
Penicillins - Ampicillin	13	0.0%	0								9	4												
Polymyxins - Colistin	13	0.0%	0									13												
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	13	0.0%	0										12	1										
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	13	0.0%	0												1	7	5							
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	13	100%	13																					13
Trimethoprim	13	0.0%	0							13														

Table 48 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Kottbus derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2013

				S. Kottbus turkey, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				3																			
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=<0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	3	0.0%	0	3																			
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	3	0.0%	0	3																			
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	3	0.0%	0	1 2																			
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	3	0.0%	0	2 1																			
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	3	0.0%	0	3																			
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	3	0.0%	0	2 1																			
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	3	0.0%	0	2 1																			
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	3	0.0%	0	1 2																			
Penicillins - Ampicillin	3	0.0%	0	2 1																			
Polymyxins - Colistin	3	0.0%	0	3																			
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	3	0.0%	0	2 1																			
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	3	0.0%	0	1 2																			
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	3	0.0%	0	3																			
Trimethoprim	3	0.0%	0	3																			

Table 49 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Stanley derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2013

		<i>S. Stanley</i> turkey control program																						
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		9		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	9	0%	0						6	3														
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	9	0%	0										9											
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	9	0%	0											8	1									
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	9	0%	0										6	3										
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	9	0%	0										9											
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	9	0%	0				9																	
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	9	0%	0						9															
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	9	100%	9						9															
Penicillins - Ampicillin	9	0%	0								9													
Polymyxins - Colistin	9	0%	0									9												
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	9	100%	9																9					
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	9	0%	0													9								
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	9	0%	0								1	8												
Trimethoprim	9	0%	0							9														

Table 50 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Saintpaul* derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2013

<i>S. Saintpaul</i> turkey control program				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																							
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	3																							
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=<0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	3	0%	0						1	2														
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	3	0%	0										3											
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	3	100%	3													1	2							
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	3	0%	0										3											
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	3	0%	0									3												
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	3	0%	0				1	2																
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	3	0%	0						1	2														
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	3	100%	3						3															
Penicillins - Ampicillin	3	100%	3														3							
Polymyxins - Colistin	3	0%	0									3												
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	3	100%	3															3						
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	3	100%	3																				3	
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	3	0%	0									3												
Trimethoprim	3	100%	3														3							

Table 51 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than S. Enteritidis (n =0), S. Typhimurium, S. Stanley, S. Infantis, S. Kottbus, S. Mbandaka and S. Saintpaul derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2013

				<i>Salmonella</i> other than S. Enteritidis (n = 0), S. Typhimurium, S. Stanley, S. Infantis, S. Kottbus, S. Mbandaka and S. Saintpaul (tested serotypes: S. Montevideo, S. Bovismorbificans, S. Agona, S. Nyborg, S. Tennessee, one isolate each) turkey, control program																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)				yes																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory				8																			
				Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%r	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	5	0.0%	0						3	2													
Aminoglycosides - Kanamycin	5	0.0%	0										5										
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	5	0.0%	0										1	3	1								
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	5	0.0%	0										1	4									
Amphenicols - Florfenicol	5	0.0%	0										3	2									
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	5	0.0%	0				1	4															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	5	0.0%	0						2	3													
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	5	0.0%	0			5																	
Penicillins - Ampicillin	5	0.0%	0								4	1											
Polymyxins - Colistin	5	0.0%	0									5											
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	5	0.0%	0										4	1									
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	5	0.0%	0													2	1	2					
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	5	0.0%	0									5											
Trimethoprim	5	0.0%	0							5													

4.2. Campylobacteriosis

4.2.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2006, the number of notified human campylobacteriosis cases exceeded for the first time the number of notified salmonellosis cases in Austria. Since then, the gap between the number of human campylobacter cases and salmonella cases has been widening.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In recent years, the number of notified cases of campylobacteriosis – with the exception of 2003 – steadily increased, reaching a new peak of 6,132 cases in 2007. The number of *Campylobacter* cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to EMS, n = 5,726 cases.

The sources of infection are still unclear. The few published outbreaks in Austria were due to contaminated cow's raw milk or chicken meat. Pets may be considered another possible source.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Feedings stuff has no obvious relevance. Animals are diversly infected: broiler flocks around 50%, cattle approx. 25%. The actual source of infection in human cases is unknown, chicken meat may account for approx. 40% of human infections.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

On January 1st, 2006, the Federal Zoonoses Act (128. Bundesgesetz: Zoonosengesetz, published on 18th November 2005) was implemented. The subject of this Act is to ensure that zoonoses, zoonotic agents and related antimicrobial resistance are properly monitored, that food-borne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation to enable the collection of the information necessary in the EU. According to this Zoonoses Act, to survey and combat the zoonoses in Austria, a Federal Commission for Zoonoses (Zoonoses Commission) has been founded to advise the Federal Minister. The first meeting took place on May 3rd, 2006. The tasks of this Zoonoses Commission are

- Securing of effective and continuous teamwork of special fields concerned
- Cooperation based on free exchange of general information and where necessary, of specific data
- Determination of measures in case of Austrian-wide food borne outbreaks (concerning several provinces by one outbreak)
- Issues the annually report on trends and sources of zoonoses in Austria
- Preparation of risk based, integrated monitoring and surveillance programmes

The Austria-wide monitoring program on the trends of campylobacter prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of campylobacter in broiler was continued according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council and the Federal Zoonoses Act. The sampling was carried out from January to December 2013, and follow up programs will be implemented in the forthcoming years. In 2012, the monitoring program was suspended in pigs and cattle due to low relevance for human infections.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Continue to work for harmonization of monitoring programs

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.2.2. Campylobacteriosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Campylobacter cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following three symptoms:

- Diarrhoea
- Abdominal pain
- Fever

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of Campylobacter spp. from stool or blood
- Differentiation of Campylobacter spp. should be performed if possible

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Stool samples are plated on selective media and incubated in microaerobic atmosphere at 37 - 42 °C for a minimum of 36 hours (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 13). Campylobacter is confirmed by observing the typical colony morphology and characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope. For typing and differentiation of isolates to species level biochemical and/or molecular methods as well as matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF) were applied. The differentiation to species level is not performed in each laboratory.

Notification system in place

Notification of Campylobacteriosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2006, the number of notified human campylobacteriosis cases in Austria for the first time exceeded the number of notified salmonellosis cases. Since that year campylobacteriosis has remained the most frequently reported bacterial enteritis in humans in Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2013 campylobacteriosis (n = 5,726) was the most frequently notified food borne enteric disease. It seems that the main sources of infection are chicken meat and raw milk (Feierl G. 2007. Jahresbericht 2006 der Nationalen Referenzzentrale für Campylobacter. Mitteilungen der Sanitätsverwaltung 4/2007).

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In 2013, campylobacteriosis remained the most frequently notified food borne disease in Austria.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via reports published by the Federal Ministry of Health (FMH) on a monthly and yearly basis and the annual report of the National Reference Centre. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 52 Campylobacteriosis in humans - species distribution (EMS/NRL), 2013

	Cases				
	N	Incidence/100,000 population	autochthonous cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
Campylobacteriosis	5,726	67.7	5,194	532	0
<i>C. jejuni</i>	4,431	52.4	4,019	412	0
<i>C. coli</i>	486	5.8	433	53	0
<i>C. concisus</i>	1	0.0	1	0	0
<i>C. fetus</i>	1	0.0	1	0	0
<i>C. gracilis</i>	1	0.0	1	0	0
<i>C. helveticus</i>	1	0.0	1	0	0
<i>C. hyointestinalis</i>	3	0.0	3	0	0
<i>C. lari</i>	2	0.0	2	0	0
<i>C. sputorum</i>	5	0.1	5	0	0
<i>C. upsaliensis</i>	4	0.0	3	1	0
Campylobacter not specified	791	9.4	725	66	0

Data source: EMS/NRL as of April 23, 2014

Table 53 Campylobacteriosis in humans - age and gender distribution (EMS/NRL), 2013

age groups	<i>Campylobacter</i> spp.			<i>C. jejuni</i>			<i>C. coli</i>			<i>Campylobacter</i> not specified			other species		
	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f
< 1 year	96	50	46	77	41	36	5	3	2	14	6	8	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	426	253	173	349	207	142	27	13	14	49	32	17	1	1	0
15 to 24 years	544	331	213	441	268	173	40	24	16	63	39	24	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	1,109	613	496	856	475	381	87	43	44	165	94	71	1	1	0
45 to 64 years	1,587	840	747	1,227	641	586	133	73	60	220	123	97	7	3	4
5 to 14 years	1,111	622	489	859	486	373	98	48	50	152	87	65	2	1	1
65 years and older	853	431	422	622	328	294	96	42	54	128	59	69	7	2	5
All age groups	5,726	3,140	2,586	4,431	2,446	1,985	486	246	240	791	440	351	18	8	10

Data source: EMS/NRL as of April 23, 2014

Table 54 Campylobacteriosis in humans - seasonal distribution (EMS/NRL), 2013

Month	<i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<i>C. jejuni</i>	<i>C. coli</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> not specified	other species
	cases	cases	cases		cases
January	388	248	17	121	2
February	275	174	14	86	1
March	300	177	18	105	
April	372	238	18	112	4
May	414	294	19	100	1
June	581	498	37	45	1
July	777	642	91	42	2
August	577	463	72	38	4
September	599	480	71	47	1
October	521	445	41	34	1
November	427	363	41	22	1
December	495	409	47	39	
Total	5,726	4,431	486	791	18

Data source: EMS/NRL as of April 23, 2014

4.2.3. *Campylobacter* spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2013 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2013“ (BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2012) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2013, approximately 26,000 samples were planned (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that has to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail or at the producer.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for specific food items (about 60-65 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2013, 8 food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2013 BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2012). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002. (e. g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must

be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). Therefore food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures.

Frequency of the sampling

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Type of specimen taken

Fresh meat and meat preparations from poultry and other foodstuffs.

Definition of positive finding

Isolation of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* from the sample independent of the microbiological method (quantitative or qualitative) used.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriological method: ISO 10272-1:2006 and 10272-2:2006

All isolates were sent to the National Reference Centre. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were differentiated into *Campylobacter jejuni* or *Campylobacter coli* with matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF). All other species were identified by additional biochemical and molecular methods including 16S rDNA sequencing. Pulsed field gel electrophoresis (PFGE) is available for outbreak detection and all isolates are stored for epidemiological investigations.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The *Campylobacter* platform called “*Campylobacter – a concern to everyone*” was closed in June 2013. Experts in the fields of human and veterinary medicine, food as well as representatives from industry, several authorities, poultry health service, trade organizations, etc. were assembled to ventilate on possible and plausible strategies against *Campylobacter* in the Austrian broiler production chain, including the impact of *Campylobacter* on human health in Austria. The result of this platform has been published in: “Konsensuspapier der bundesweiten Plattform *Campylobacter*, 17.1.2014” (German only).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

At the sampling stage “processing plant” 61 fresh broiler meat samples have been tested for *Campylobacter*, with 54 positive results (40 x *C. jejuni*, 14 x *C. coli*), revealing a prevalence for *C. jejuni/coli* of 88.5 % (CI: 78-94 %). At the sampling stage “retail” 67 out of 107 samples of fresh broiler meat and products thereof have been tested positive for *Campylobacter* (62.6 %, CI: 53-71 %; 38 x *C. jejuni*, 24 x *C. coli*, 6 x thermotolerant *Campylobacter*; in one sample two different species have been found). In poultry meat other than broilers (e.g. from turkey, goose, duck) *Campylobacter* was found in 47 % (CI: 36-59 %; 32 positive samples out of 68).

In total, 46 samples of meat (non-poultry meat, meat preparations and meat products) were tested for *Campylobacter*. *Campylobacter* spp. was detected in 3 meat samples, 2 isolates were identified as *C. coli* and 1 as *C. jejuni*. No *Campylobacter* was detected in 29 samples of raw milk, cheeses and dairy products as well as in 84 other food samples from several food categories.

A campaign (A-802-13) on fresh broiler meat was conducted to compare the results with a previous campaign from 2012 (campaign A-805-12: focus on atmosphere packaged fresh broiler meat). The prevalence of *Campylobacter* (75 %) was in accordance with the previous campaign in 2012, where 74 % of the tested samples (only modified atmosphere packaging selected) were positive for *Campylobacter*. Noteworthy, quantitative results indicate a statistically significant higher number of *Campylobacter* in products without special packaging than in products with modified atmosphere.

In one AGES laboratory 74 (out of the 107) routinely tested fresh broiler meat samples and 79 (out of the 111) samples from the special campaign (both taken at retail) have been tested quantitatively (n=153). Five of the tested samples (3.3 % ; CI: 1-7 %) showed a very high contamination with *Campylobacter* > 1,000 CFU/g.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-041-13: *Campylobacter* spp. in food - Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat - at retail - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail, in this campaign at “takeaway” facilities by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September - October

Type of specimen taken

Several ready to eat dishes containing noodles, vegetables, different kind of sauces (including meat from different species)

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* spp. in 25 g

Results of the investigation

Campylobacter spp. not detected in 62 samples tested

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *L. monocytogenes* and *Salmonella*

Campaign A-802-13: *Campylobacter* spp. in food - Meat from broilers (*Gallus gallus*) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked – chilled - at retail - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September - November

Type of specimen taken

Meat from poultry, packaged in not modified atmosphere

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* spp. in 25 g

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up monitoring programs

Results of the investigation

Campylobacter spp. detected in 83 out of 111 (75 %) samples tested

Quantitative results of 79 samples: *Campylobacter* spp. < 10 CFU/g in 49 samples (detection limit = 10 CFU/g), *Campylobacter* spp. 10 - 100 CFU/g in 11 samples, *Campylobacter* spp. 100 – 1,000 CFU/g in 15 samples, *Campylobacter* spp. >1,000 CFU/g in 4 samples.

Table 55 Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* spp. in poultry meat, 2013

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<i>Campylobacter</i> - <i>C. coli</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> - <i>C. jejuni</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> - <i>Campylobacter</i> spp., unspecified	<i>Campylobacter</i> - Thermophilic <i>Campylobacter</i> spp., unspecified	
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	3	1	1	1	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	61	54	14	40	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	70	51	16	31	5	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	6	1	4	1	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	20	4	1	3	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	4	4	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	6	6	0	0	0	
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked - chilled	campaign A-802-13	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	90	69	22	33	0	14	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	12	3	6	0	3	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	2	0	0	0	2	
Meat from duck - fresh		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	1	0	0	
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	1	0	0	
Meat from duck - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from geese - carcase - chilled		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from geese - fresh		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	1	0	0	
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	1	0	0	
Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	9	2	7	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	2	1	1	0	0	
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	1	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	30	13	4	9	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from turkey - fresh		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	2	1	1	0	0	
Meat from turkey - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0		

Table 56 Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* spp. in food, 2013

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<i>Campylobacter</i> - <i>C. coli</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> - <i>C. jejuni</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> - Thermophilic <i>Campylobacter</i> spp., unspecified
Bakery products - pastry		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
Crustaceans		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Fish		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Fish - raw		Catering	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Fruits		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - fresh		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	1	1	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	1	0
Meat from pig - fresh		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	1	0	0
Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Meat from sheep - fresh		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - raw milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Milk, cows ¹ - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0
Milk, cows - pasteurised milk		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Milk, cows - raw milk		Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0
Milk, cows - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Milk, goats - raw milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Milk, sheeps - raw milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Mushrooms		Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods	campaign A-041-13	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	60	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Ready-to-eat salads		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Sauce and dressings		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0

4.2.4. *Campylobacter* spp. in animals

A. *Campylobacter* spp. in animal – broiler - at slaughterhouse –official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2013 the monitoring on the prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* spp. was continued in broiler slaughter batches. The period of sampling was randomized over the whole year. Sampling was performed in the 5 broiler slaughter facilities with slaughter batches consisting of >2000 animals in Austria in 2012.

Frequency of the sampling

Rearing period: no program

Before slaughter at farm: no program

At slaughter: according to the randomized sampling plan

Type of specimen taken

Intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Rearing period: no program

Before slaughter at farm: no program

At slaughter: The sampling was performed by official veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration the whole intestines of 10 animals were taken and wrapped in a sterile plastic bag. Using a polystyrene box cooled samples (4 °C) were sent to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz. In the laboratory a caecum of each intestinal convolute was identified, some content of each caecum pooled and cultured by direct plating onto selective medium suitable for *Campylobacter jejuni/coli*.

Case definition

At slaughter: A slaughter batch is considered to be infected with thermotolerant *Campylobacter* following isolation of *Campylobacter jejuni* or *C. coli* from the pooled caecal content.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

At slaughter: The pooled samples were examined by direct inoculation on modified Charcoal Cefoperazone Deoxycholate agar plates (mCCDA) being incubated in a micro-aerobic atmosphere at 42 ± 1 °C for 48 hours. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were subcultured on blood agar plates and incubated for another 48 hours in a micro-aerobic atmosphere at 37 ± 1 °C. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were identified by observing their characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope and the production of catalase and oxidase and gram staining. For typing and differentiating of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates a PCR as described by Menard et al. (2005) was performed. All *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates were frozen in proteose peptone solution containing 10 % glycerol or thioglycolat-broth at -70 °C. For quality control *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 and internal control isolates *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* were used. Data analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel 2010.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not performed in Austria.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Different strategies are in discussion, e.g. a quick test for identification of campylobacter infected flocks at farm.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A Campylobacter platform called “Campylobacter – a concern to everyone” was launched in June 2012. Experts in the fields of human and veterinary medicine, food as well as representatives from industry, several authorities, poultry health service, trade organizations, etc. are assembled to ventilate on possible and plausible strategies against Campylobacter in the Austrian broiler production chain, including the impact of Campylobacter on human health in Austria.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Emphasis should be placed on education of the people for a better care in kitchen hygiene.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None.

Notification system in place

Findings of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* in animals do not need to be reported to authorities in Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the course of this monitoring thermotolerant Campylobacter were detected in 183 out of 328 (55.8 %) of the tested slaughter batches. *C. jejuni* was found in 44.2 % of samples, *C. coli* in 11.6 %. Poultry meat combined with mistakes in kitchen hygiene seems to be the most risky food for humans acquiring an infection with *C. jejuni/coli*.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 57 Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* in animals, 2013

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive	Campylobacter jejuni	Campylobacter coli
Broiler flocks	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	10 intestines per slaughter batch	VEMI Graz*	slaughter batch	328	183	145	38

*VEMI Graz: AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz

4.2.5. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter* spp.

A. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in humans, 2013

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

A sentinel surveillance program for *Campylobacter* isolates from human infections was installed in October 2006. On a monthly basis, the first 10 isolates collected at each of four designated diagnostic laboratories serving different provinces in Austria are sent to the National Reference Laboratory for *Campylobacter* for speciation analysis and antimicrobial resistance testing.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Stool specimens were plated on *Campylobacter* blood-free selective agar at 37°C or 42°C for 48 hours under microaerobic conditions, and organisms were identified as *Campylobacter* spp. by oxidase testing and cell morphology. Isolates were speciated by biochemical methods and/or molecular methods as well as matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF). Broth microdilution susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter* spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility microtitre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex, UK). Briefly, *Campylobacter* spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of approximately 500,000 cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560 was used as control.

The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for *Campylobacter* includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin, gentamicin, and streptomycin!

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2013, 458 isolates of *Campylobacter* (410 *C. jejuni*, 48 *C. coli*) were tested for their antimicrobial susceptibility using micro-dilution method. In contrast to previous years, no increase in resistance to ciprofloxacin was observed, the resistance rate remained at a high level (> 60 %). Resistance to tetracyclin decreased to 22.5 % (2012: > 30 %), and resistance to erythromycin was not observed.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

The sentinel surveillance system will be continued. Results are published annually in the Report of the National Reference Centre and in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

B. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in broiler meat

Sampling strategy used in monitoring**Frequency of the sampling**

Isolates from broiler meat isolated in the course of the national food surveillance programs that were sent to the National Reference Laboratory for Campylobacter were tested for antimicrobial susceptibility.

Type of specimen taken

Food surveillance programs

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in food

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was performed at the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene in Graz. *Campylobacter* isolates from poultry meat were tested.

Methods used for collecting data

All informations concerning the tested food and results of the antimicrobial testing were analysed using Microsoft® Excel2010.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Described in chapter thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers.

Broth microdilution susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter* spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility micro titre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex UK). Briefly, *Campylobacter* spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of approximately 500,000 cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560 was used as control.

The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for *Campylobacter* includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin, gentamicin, and streptomycin.

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms**The control program/strategies in place**

Samples from food animals were monitored for antimicrobial residues according to a randomized sampling scheme (BMGF-74320/0003-IV/B/7/2010, Rückstandsuntersuchung-Durchführungserlass 2007).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A project has been started to assess the appropriate method for collecting data on antimicrobial usage in animals. Results of this study are expected for 2014.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Nil

Notification system in place

No notification system for resistant isolates in place.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2013, *C. jejuni* isolated from broiler meat and broiler flocks showed high resistance rates for ciprofloxacin, ampicillin, nalidixic acid and tetracycline.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)**Additional information**

Results are published annually in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

C. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in broiler slaughter batches

Sampling strategy used in monitoring**Frequency of the sampling**

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers

Type of specimen taken

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of all isolates was performed at the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene in Graz. A randomized sampling plan was calculated to obtain approximately 170 thermotolerant *Campylobacter* isolates per animal species. If less than 170 isolates were obtained, all isolates were tested. If more than 170 thermotolerant *Campylobacter* were isolated 170 were randomly chosen.

Methods used for collecting data

All information concerning the tested animals, sampled slaughterhouses and results of the antimicrobial testing were analysed using Microsoft® Excel 2010.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Described in chapter thermotolerant campylobacter in broilers.

Broth microdilution susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter* spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility micro titre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex UK). Briefly, *Campylobacter* spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of approximately 500,000 cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560 was used as control.

The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for *Campylobacter* includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin, gentamicin, and streptomycin.

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Samples from food animals were monitored for antimicrobial residues according to a randomized sampling scheme (BMGF-74320/0003-IV/B/7/2012, Rückstandsuntersuchung-Durchführungserlass 2007).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Nil

Notification system in place

No notification system for resistant isolates in place.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2013, *C. jejuni* isolated from broiler meat and broiler flocks showed high resistance rates to ciprofloxacin, ampicillin, nalidixic acid and tetracycline (as in previous years).

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Additional information

The results are published annually in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

Table 58 Breakpoints used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni*, 2013

Test method used: Broth dilution		Number of reporting laboratory: 1			
Standards used for testing EUCAST		The methods are used for investigation of isolates from			
		Animals	x		
		Food	x		
		Humans	x		
		Dilution method			
		Standard for cut-off	Cut-off concentration (µg/ml)	Range tested	
<i>Campylobacter jejuni</i>			Resistant >	lowest	highest
Aminoglycosides					
	Gentamicin	EUCAST	> 2	0.125	16
	Neomycin	EUCAST	-	0.125	8
	Streptomycin	EUCAST	> 4	0.5	32
Quinolones und quinoxalines					
	Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST	> 0.5	0.06	32
	Nalidixic acid	EUCAST	> 16	2	256
Macrolides					
	Erythromycin	EUCAST	> 4	0.25	128
Penicillines					
	Ampicillin	EUCAST	> 8	1	64
Phenicoles					
	Chloramphenicol	EUCAST	> 16	2	64
Carbapenemes					
	Imipenem	EUCAST	-	0.06	16
Tetracyclines					
	Tetracycline	EUCAST	> 1	0.125	64

Table 59 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni*, qualitative data, 2013

<i>C. jejuni</i>									
	human			broiler meat			Gallus gallus		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	410			144			122		
Antimicrobials:	N	% r	n	N	% r	n	N	% r	n
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	410	0.0%	0	144	0.0%	0	122	0.0%	0
Aminoglycosides - Neomycin	410	-	-	144	-	-	122	-	-
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	410	1.5%	6	144	0.7%	1	122	2.5%	3
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	410	0.0%	0	144	0.0%	0	122	0.0%	0
Carbapenems - Imipenem	410	-	-	144	-	-	122	-	-
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	410	63.2%	259	144	71.5%	103	122	73.0%	89
Macrolides - Erythromycin	410	0.0%	0	144	0.0%	0	122	0.0%	0
Penicillins - Ampicillin	410	28.3%	116	144	30.6%	44	122	34.4%	42
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	410	62.2%	255	144	68.8%	99	122	70.5%	86
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	410	21.5%	88	144	29.9%	43	122	24.6%	30
Number of multiresistant isolates									
fully sensitive	410	33.4%	137	144	25.7%	37	122	26.2%	32
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	410	48.5%	199	144	47.2%	68	122	49.2%	60
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	410	16.6%	68	144	26.4%	38	122	23.0%	28
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	410	1.5%	6	144	0.7%	1	122	1.6%	2
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	410	0.0%	0	144	0.0%	0	122	0.0%	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	410	0.0%	0	144	0.0%	0	122	0.0%	0

Table 60 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in humans, quantitative data, 2013

<i>C. jejuni</i> human		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	345																					
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0.007	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>256	
				n																		
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	410	0.0%	0						219	165	26											
Aminoglycosides - Neomycin	410	-	-						18	180	197	14					1					
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	410	1.5%	6								342	60	1	1	5	1						
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	410	0.0%	0										275	85	41	9						
Carbapenems - Imipenem	410	-	-					397	12	1												
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	410	63.2%	259				87	52	8	4	1			7	160	51	30	10				
Macrolides - Erythromycin	410	0.0%	0							38	182	155	32	3								
Penicillins - Ampicillin	410	28.3%	116								1	57	74	102	60	19	28	45	24			
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	410	62.2%	255										39	98	16	2		2	39	197	17	
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	410	21.5%	88					88	157	45	32	3			1	1	7	23	53			

Table 61 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in broiler meat, quantitative data, 2013

		<i>C. jejuni</i> broiler meat		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		144																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0.007	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>256	
				n																		
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	144	0.0%	0						78	65	1											
Aminoglycosides - Neomycin	144	-	-						6	71	65	2										
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	144	0.7%	1								128	15			1							
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	144	0.0%	0										110	23	11							
Carbapenems - Imipenem	144	-	-					136	5	2		1										
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	144	71.5%	103					24	14	3				12	70	14	6	1				
Macrolides - Erythromycin	144	0.0%	0							21	71	46	6									
Penicillins - Ampicillin	144	30.6%	44									11	25	46	18	5	19	11	9			
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	144	68.8%	99										14	28	2	1	1	1	26	68	3	
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	144	29.9%	43						24	59	11	7				2	4	11	26			

Table 62 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in broiler flocks - at slaughter - quantitative data, 2013

		<i>C. jejuni</i> Gallus gallus		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		108																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0.007	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>256	
				n																		
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	122	0.0%	0						53	66	3											
Aminoglycosides - Neomycin	122	-	-						5	48	69											
Aminoglycosides – Streptomycin	122	2.5%	3								96	21		2	3							
Amphenicols – Chloramphenicol	122	0.0%	0										78	24	16	4						
Carbapenems - Imipenem	122	-	-					116	6													
Fluoroquinolones – Ciprofloxacin	122	73.0%	89					15	15	2	1			2	54	21	8	4				
Macrolides – Erythromycin	122	0.0%	0						6	62	43	9	2									
Penicillins – Ampicillin	122	34.4%	42									8	15	32	25	7	15	16	4			
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	122	70.5%	86										10	17	8	1			12	67	7	
Tetracyclines – Tetracycline	122	24.6%	30						14	53	12	13	1	1		1		11	16			

Table 63 Breakpoints used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli*, 2013

Test method used	Broth dilution	x	Number of reporting laboratory			1
Standards used for testing	EUCAST		The methods are used for investigation of isolates from			
			Animals	x		
			Food	x		
			Humans	x		
<i>Campylobacter coli</i>	Standard for breakpoint	Dilution method	Breakpoint Resistant >	Range tested		
				concentration (µg/ml)	lowest	highest
Aminoglycosides						
	Gentamicin	EUCAST	> 2	0.125		16
	Neomycin	EUCAST	> 4	0.125		8
	Streptomycin	EUCAST	> 4	0.5		32
Quinolones und quinoxalines						
	Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST	> 0.5	0.06		32
	Nalidixic acid	EUCAST	> 16	2		256
Macrolides						
	Erythromycin	EUCAST	> 8	0.25		128
Penicillines						
	Ampicillin	EUCAST	> 8	1		64
Phenicoles						
	Chloramphenicol	EUCAST	> 16	2		64
Carbapenemes						
	Imipenem	EUCAST	-	0.06		16
Tetracyclines						
	Tetracycline	EUCAST	> 2	0.125		64

Table 64 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli*, qualitative data, 2013

<i>C. coli</i>									
	humans			broiler meat			<i>Gallus gallus</i>		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	48			99			31		
Antimicrobials:	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	48	0.0%	0	99	0.0%	0	31	0.0%	0
Aminoglycosides - Neomycin	48	2.1%	1	99	0.0%	0	31	0.0%	0
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	48	6.3%	3	99	11.1%	11	31	9.7%	3
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	48	0.0%	0	99	0.0%	0	31	0.0%	0
Carbapenems - Imipenem	48	-	-	99	-	-	31	-	-
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	48	66.7%	32	99	69.7%	69	31	48.4%	15
Macrolides - Erythromycin	48	0.0%	0	99	3.0%	3	31	3.2%	1
Penicillins - Ampicillin	48	41.7%	20	99	36.4%	36	31	32.3%	10
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	48	66.7%	32	99	68.7%	68	31	48.4%	15
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	48	37.5%	18	99	53.5%	53	31	83.9%	26
Number of multiresistant isolates									
fully sensitive	48	29.2%	14	99	7.1%	7	31	3.2%	1
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	48	37.5%	18	99	56.6%	56	31	61.3%	19
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	48	27.1%	13	99	29.3%	29	31	22.6%	7
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	48	6.3%	3	99	6.1%	6	31	12.9%	4
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	48	0.0%	0	99	1.0%	1	31	0.0%	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	48	0.0%	0	99	0.0%	0	31	0.0%	0

Table 65 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in humans, quantitative data, 2013

		<i>C. coli</i> human																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		48																				
		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0.007	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>256	
				n																		
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	48	0.0%	0						4	24	20											
Aminoglycosides - Neomycin	48	2.1%	1							4	36	7				1						
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	48	6.3%	3								9	36				2		1				
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	48	0.0%	0										12	22	13	1						
Carbapenems - Imipenem	48	-	-						13	34	1											
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	48	66.7%	32				9	4	3					8	13	9	1	1				
Macrolides - Erythromycin	48	0.0%	0						3	19	11	12	3									
Penicillins - Ampicillin	48	41.7%	20									1	3	9	15	9	1	3	7			
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	48	66.7%	32										2	8	5	1		1	24	7		
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	48	37.5%	18					5	12	10	2	1			1		1	16				

Table 66 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in broiler meat - quantitative data, 2013

		<i>C. coli</i> broiler meat																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	99	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0.007	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>256
				n																	
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	99	0.0%	0						5	68	26										
Aminoglycosides - Neomycin	99	0.0%	0							9	75	14		1							
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	99	11.1%	11								24	60	4			5	3	3			
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	99	0.0%	0										27	55	17						
Carbapenems - Imipenem	99	-	-					5	50	44											
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	99	69.7%	69					11	15	4			1	24	32	9	3				
Macrolides - Erythromycin	99	3.0%	3							15	43	16	15	5	2						3
Penicillins - Ampicillin	99	36.4%	36									3	2	18	40	29	1	3	3		
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	99	68.7%	68											15	15	1		5	56	7	
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	99	53.5%	53						8	27	8	3						4	49		

Table 67 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in broiler slaughter batches - quantitative data, 2013

		<i>C. coli</i> <i>Gallus gallus</i>																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	31	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	<=0,0039	0.007	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	>256	
				n																		
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	31	0.0%	0						3	22	6											
Aminoglycosides - Neomycin	31	0.0%	0							3	25	2	1									
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	31	9.7%	3								10	17	1			1		2				
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	31	0.0%	0										3	22	6							
Carbapenems - Imipenem	31	-	-						15	16												
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	31	48.4%	15				5	8	3					5	5	4	1					
Macrolides - Erythromycin	31	3.2%	1							3	9	6	11	1								1
Penicillins - Ampicillin	31	32.3%	10										1	9	11	9					1	
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	31	48.4%	15											12	4			1	12	2		
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	31	83.9%	26						1	3	1							1	25			

4.3. Listeriosis

4.3.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Listeriosis can be regarded as a relatively rare infectious disease in Austria with an annual incidence between 0.1 and 0.25 cases per 100,000 inhabitants in the years 1996 to 2007. In 2008 a total of 31 culturally verified human cases of listeriosis were recorded for Austria (incidence 0.38 per 100,000 inhabitants), four of them were associated with pregnancy. In 2009 a further increase had to be assessed, 46 cases what corresponds to an incidence of 0.6. Two cases were associated with pregnancy. In 2010, a reduction to 34 cases could be observed and also in 2011, n = 24 (incidence of 0.29). In 2013, 36 cases were notified (EMS). The incidences are similar to those of most other western European countries (0.2-0.9). In 2013, lethality was reported in 3 cases (8 % of cases, EMS). Due to the fact that an isolate is not sent to the NRC-L for each notified case, the case numbers may differ. EMS data correlate with the notification data of the medicating physician and the diagnosing laboratory. According to the NRC-L, isolates from 33 cases were typed, the 28-day lethality was 24 % (8 cases). This high fatality rate and the sometimes severe permanent disabilities demand every effort to ascertain potential food-associated outbreaks as early as possible.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease.

The number of listeriosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases reported to the EMS.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Listeriosis is a rare disease, but not a rare bacterium, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, including pregnancy and immunosuppression. Although dairy products and salmon are likely candidates, the source of an infection often remains unclear.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A monthly report is sent to the Ministry of Health by the National Reference Center, whereas outbreaks are reported immediately.

Restrictions tightened to sell unpasteurised milk in remote areas (Alps).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

More widespread information for pregnant and immunocompromised persons should be provided.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send those strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.3.2. Listeriosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Listeriosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following three symptoms:

- Listeriosis of newborns defined as Stillbirth or at least one of the following five in the first month of life:
 - Granulomatosis infantiseptica
 - Meningitis or meningoencephalitis
 - Septicaemia
 - Dyspnoea
 - Lesions on skin, mucosal membranes or conjunctivae
- Listeriosis in pregnancy defined as at least one of the following three:
 - Abortion, miscarriage, stillbirth or premature birth
 - Fever
 - Influenza-like symptoms
- Other form of listeriosis defined as at least one of the following four:
 - Fever
 - Meningitis or meningoencephalitis
 - Septicaemia
 - Localised infections such as arthritis, endocarditis, and abscesses

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Isolation of *Listeria monocytogenes* from a normally sterile site
- Isolation of *Listeria monocytogenes* from a normally non-sterile site in a foetus, stillborn, newborn or the mother at or within 24 hours of birth

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the laboratory criteria

or

- Any mother with a laboratory confirmed listeriosis infection in her foetus, stillborn or newborn

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples are Gram stained. Specimen from normally sterile sites are inoculated in blood culture broth or thioglycollate broth and Columbia blood agar plates, vaginal swabs are plated only directly on Columbia blood and colistin-nalidixic acid (CNA) agar. *L. monocytogenes* is identified by catalase and Api Listeria test.

Stool samples were examined after cold enrichment in Fraser enrichment broth and streaked onto selective chromogenic agar plate and Columbia blood-agar. All isolates obtained in Austria are sent to the National Reference Center for confirmation, subtyping by PCR and PFGE and comparison.

Notification system in place

Notification of listeriosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

History of the disease in chapter general evaluation.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the EMS, 36 cases of listeriosis were notified (as of April 22, 2014); due to the fact that an isolate is not sent to the NRC-L for each notified case, the case numbers may differ. EMS data correlate with the notification data of the medicating physician and the diagnosing laboratory. In the NRC-L, isolates from 33 cases were typed.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Listeriosis is a rare disease, but not a rare bacterium, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, including pregnancy and immunosuppression. Although dairy products and salmon are likely candidates, the source of an infection often remains unclear.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 68 Listeriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2013

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population
Listeriosis	36	0.43
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2a*</i>	17	0.20
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2b*</i>	3	0.04
<i>L. monocytogenes 4b</i>	9	0.11
<i>L. monocytogenes 1/2c</i>	2	0.02
<i>L. monocytogenes unknow SG</i>	5	0.06
deaths caused by listeriosis	3	0,04
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2a</i>	3	0.04
Congenital cases*	2	
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2a**</i>	1	
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2b**</i>	1	

* cases without newborns

** isolates from newborns

Data source: EMS as of April 22, 2014

Table 69 Listeriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (NRC-L), 2013

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population
Listeriosis	33	0.40
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2a</i>	17	0.20
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2b</i>	5	0.06
<i>L. monocytogenes 4b</i>	9	0.11
<i>L. monocytogenes 1/2c</i>	2	0.02
Deaths	8	0.04
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2a</i>	6	0.07
<i>L. monocytogenes 1,2b</i>	1	0.01
<i>L. monocytogenes 4b</i>	1	0.01
Congenital cases	2	0.02

Data source: National Reference Centre for Listeria as of April 7, 2014

Table 70 Listeriosis in humans - age distribution (EMS), 2013

Age group	Listeriosis			<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1,2a			<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1,2b			<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b			<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2c			unknown SG		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year**	2**	-	2**	1**	-	1**	1**	-	1**	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1 to 4 years	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5 to 14 years	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15 to 24 years	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-
25 to 44 years	2	-	2	2	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
45 to 64 years	7	5	2	2	2	-	-	-	-	3	1	2	-	-	-	2	2	-
65 years and older	24	11	13	13	7	6	2	-	2	5	4	1	2	-	2	2	-	2
Age unknown***	1***	-	1***	-	-	-	1***	-	1***	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
All age groups*	36	18	18	17	9	8	3	0	3	9	6	3	2	0	2	5	3	2

* cases without newborns

** isolates from newborns (not counted, only the mother counted)

*** mother of one congenital case (age not known)

Data source: EMS as of April 22, 2014

4.3.3. *Listeria* spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2013 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2013“ (BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2012) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2013, approximately 26,000 samples were planned (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that has to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail or at the producer.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for specific food items (about 60-65 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2013, 8 food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2013 BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2012). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002. (e. g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). Therefore food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures. Therefore Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs indicates the quantity of sampling (number of sample units and size of the analytical unit) regarding to specific microbiological hazards at the stage of products placed on the market within their shelflife and at a specific stage of production (e.g. before and/or after chilling).

Frequency of the sampling

At the production plant

The producer is responsible for the process hygiene. The frequency of sampling therefore depends on the critical control points of the specific product.

At retail

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Diagnostic/analytical methods used at the production plant or at retail

Bacteriological method ISO 11290-1:2004 and ISO 11290-2:2005

For further investigations all isolates from foodstuffs are sent to the National Reference Laboratory for *Listeria* in Graz. This includes the isolates from process hygiene controls at the production plant, self monitoring as well as all isolates from regularly testing at retail.

In a first step the species *Listeria monocytogenes* is confirmed by different selective media (e. g. Palcam agar, Ottoviani Agosti agar, Rapid L.mono agar) and/or API. A serogroup-specific PCR according to Doumith et al., 2004. Differentiation of the Major *Listeria monocytogenes* Serovars by

Multiplex PCR. J Clin Microbiol 51, 3819-22 is performed routinely. Finally typing is realized with PFGE. For further questions Matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time of flight (MALDI TOF) is available.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

All isolates from foodstuffs and process hygiene controls from any laboratories within Austria are gathered and typed at the National Reference Laboratory for Listeria. In the case of an outbreak the data of the outbreak strain are compared with the existing data base.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs; a folder was created by the AGES in cooperation with the Austrian Medical Chamber: Pregnancy – infections transmitted via food (Schwangerschaft – Infektionen durch

Nahrungsmittel, http://www.ages.at/uploads/media/AGES_Folder_Schwangerschaft_Web.pdf). This folder was distributed to all gynaecologists. The folder contains advices to prevent food-borne infections during pregnancy, including listeriosis, toxoplasmosis, campylobacteriosis and salmonellosis as well as mycotoxicosis. The Federal Ministry of Health published folders on their webpage

(<https://www.verbrauchergesundheit.gv.at/lebensmittel/buch/hygieneleitlinien/hygieneleitlinienell.html>).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

Listeria monocytogenes was not detected in samples of pasteurised cows' milk (0/26), in raw cows' milk (0/30) or any other dairy products (0/276). Concerning pasteurised cows' milk no Listeria has been detected for four years (2010-2013). In total 717 cheeses were tested and *L. monocytogenes* could be detected in 4 samples.

In 7 of 261 (2.7 %) ready-to-eat pig meat product samples (including fermented sausages) and in 4 out of 235 samples (1.7 %) from mixed, minced meat, intended to be eaten cooked *L. monocytogenes* was qualitatively found (all of them below detection limit). 2 out of 105 samples (1.9 %) of red meat products, cooked, ready-to-eat chilled were found positive in 25g and of red meat products, fermented sausages 7 out of 246 (2.9 %).

3.3 % of all samples from fishery products (5/153) revealed a contamination with *L. monocytogenes* (all of them below detection limit). 1 out of 31 smoked fish samples (3.2 %) were found positive for *L. monocytogenes* below detection limit.

Other processed food products, including the samples from campaign A-019-13 and A-041-13, add up to 190 samples, of which 5 samples were found positive, 1-time <100 cfu/g, the others below detection limit.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-017-13: *Listeria monocytogenes* in food – Dairy products (excluding cheeses) – dairy products, not specified - ready-to-eat - made from pasteurised milk – at farm – Surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: April - June

Type of specimen taken

Dairy products - ready-to-eat - made from pasteurised milk

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *L. monocytogenes* in 25g

Results of the investigation

42 samples tested, *Listeria monocytogenes* not detected (neither qualitatively nor quantitatively)

Additional information

None

Campaign A-019-13: *Listeria monocytogenes* in food – other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods – at retail – Surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples were taken at food stalls in front of shopping malls by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: June - August

Type of specimen taken

Several ready to eat snacks, amongst others meat, meat products and sausages from all kind of species, different cheeses and bakery products

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *L. monocytogenes* in 25g or quantitative test

Results of the investigation

62 samples tested for *Listeria monocytogenes*; One sample positive with enumeration method: < 100 CFU/g but negative in qualitative method.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Salmonella* spp.

Campaign A-034-13: *Listeria* spp. in food – fishery products, unspecified – ready-to-eat - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: July - August

Type of specimen taken

fish called „Steckerlfisch“, ready-to-eat, together at least 300g;

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Listeria monocytogenes* in 25 g

Results of the investigation

18 samples tested, *Listeria monocytogenes* not detected (neither qualitatively not quantitatively)

Campaign A-041-13: *Listeria* spp. in food - Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail, in this campaign at “takeaway” facilities by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September - Oktober

Type of specimen taken

Several ready to eat dishes containing pasta (noodles), vegetables, different kind of sauces (including meat from different species)

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25 g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Listeria* spp. in 25 g

Results of the investigation

62 samples tested, *Listeria monocytogenes* not detected (neither qualitatively not quantitatively)

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Salmonella* spp. and *Campylobacter* spp.

Campaign A-801-13: *Listeria monocytogenes* in food – mixed meat and cheese products – at retail – Surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September - October

Type of specimen taken

Meat, red meat – meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat or fermented sausages
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *L. monocytogenes* in 25g

Results of the investigation

104 samples tested, *Listeria monocytogenes* not detected (neither qualitatively nor quantitatively)

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Salmonella* spp. and VTEC

Table 71 *Listeria monocytogenes* in milk and milky products, 2013

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but ≤ 100	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g
Cheeses made from cows milk	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		19	0	19	0	19	0	0
		EU		12	0	12	0	4	0	0
	Retail	EU		12	0	12	0	6	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		6	0	6	0	4	0	0
	Retail	AT		20	0	20	0	18	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - hard	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		11	0	11	0	11	0	0
		EU		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		9	0	9	0	9	0	0
		EU		11	0	11	0	4	0	0
	Retail	EU		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		31	0	31	0	31	0	0
		EU		17	0	17	0	15	0	0
	Retail	EU		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - soft and semi-soft	Catering	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		17	0	17	0	17	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		68	0	68	0	68	0	0
		AT		59	0	59	0	58	0	0
		EU		57	0	57	0	53	0	0
	Retail	XX		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		AT		27	1	27	1	27	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		AT		24	0	24	0	21	0	0
	Retail	XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		EU		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - unspecified	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Wholesale	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	

Table 70 cont.

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L. monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but ≤ 100	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Cheeses made from goats milk	Retail	AT		11	1	11	1	11	0	1
Cheeses made from goats milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
	Retail	AT		10	0	10	0	10	0	0
Cheeses made from goats milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		15	0	15	0	15	0	0
	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
Cheeses made from goats milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		9	0	9	0	9	0	0
	Retail	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
Cheeses made from goats milk - unspecified	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		15	0	15	0	15	0	0
	Retail	AT		3	1	3	1	3	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Retail	AT		13	0	13	0	12	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Border inspection activities	XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		22	0	22	0	22	0	0
	Retail	AT		9	0	9	0	9	0	0
		EU		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
Wholesale	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0	
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
	Retail	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats	Retail	AT	campaign A-801-13	37	0	37	0	0	0	0
		EU	campaign A-801-13	2	0	2	0	0	0	0
		XE	campaign A-801-13	2	0	2	0	0	0	0
		XX	campaign A-801-13	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Retail	AT		4	0	4	0	3	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		EU		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk	Catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		18	0	18	0	18	0	0
	Retail	AT		13	0	13	0	13	0	0
		EU		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0

Table 70 cont.

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L. monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but ≤ 100	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
	Retail	AT		4	0	4	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Retail	AT		2	1	2	1	2	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Retail	XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses)	Processing plant	AT		16	0	16	0	16	0	0
	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		10	0	10	0	10	0	0
	Retail	AT		13	0	13	0	12	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	AT		4	0	4	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - chocolate milk	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	AT		36	0	36	0	2	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	Processing plant	AT		11	0	11	0	11	0	0
	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	AT		24	0	24	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - ready-to-eat	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - ready-to-eat - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	AT	campaign A-017-13	42	0	42	0	42	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products	Catering	AT		4	0	4	0	3	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		9	0	9	0	9	0	0
	Retail	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream	Catering	AT		2	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
	Retail	AT		31	0	8	0	31	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	AT		28	0	28	0	0	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt	Retail	AT		21	0	21	0	19	0	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - raw milk	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Milk, cows - pasteurised milk	Catering	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		14	0	14	0	13	0	0
	Retail	AT		5	0	5	0	1	0	0
Milk, cows - raw milk	Farm	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	Retail	AT		8	0	8	0	7	0	0
Milk, cows - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption	Retail	AT		17	0	17	0	17	0	0
Milk, cows - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Milk, goats - raw milk	Farm	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Milk, sheeps - raw milk	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0

Table 72 *Listeria monocytogenes* in other foods, 2013

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but <= 100	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g
Bakery products - cakes	Catering	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Retail	AT		42	1	42	1	39	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Bakery products - pastry	Catering	AT		21	0	21	0	20	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		103	0	103	0	65	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Crustaceans - shrimps	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Crustaceans - shrimps - cooked	Retail	EU		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Egg products - liquid	Retail	AT		6	0	6	0	0	0	0
		EU		6	0	6	0	0	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		3	0	3	0	0	0	0
		XE		3	0	3	0	0	0	0
Fats and oils (excluding butter) - oils	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Fish - raw	Border inspection activities	XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		5	1	5	1	1	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
XX			1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
Fish - smoked	Retail	AT		23	1	23	1	14	0	0
		EU		6	0	6	0	0	0	0
		XX		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Fish (food)	Retail	AT		25	0	25	0	0	0	0
		XX		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified	Border inspection activities	XE		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	Catering	AT		10	1	10	1	4	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		22	0	22	0	21	0	0
		EU		3	0	3	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		41	1	41	1	40	0	0
		EU		30	3	30	3	29	0	0
		XE		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
		EU		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
XE			2	0	2	0	2	0	0	

Table 71 cont.

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but <= 100	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		EU		3	0	3	0	0	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat	Retail	AT	campaign A-034-13	12	0	12	0	12	0	0
		EU	campaign A-034-13	6	0	6	0	6	0	0
		XX	campaign A-034-13	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Fruits - pre-cut - chilled	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		XX		3	0	3	0	0	0	0
Infant formula	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Infant formula - dried	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - fresh	Catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		3	0	3	0	2	0	0
	Retail	AT		5	1	5	1	5	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
Meat from deer (venison) - fresh	Catering	EU		1	1	1	1	1	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified	Catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		1	1	1	0	1	1	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat from pig - fresh	Wholesale	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		12	0	12	0	8	0	0
	Retail	AT		28	2	28	2	2	0	0
Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	AT			8	0	8	0	8	0	0
	EU			6	0	6	0	6	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	Catering	EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
		AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	

Table 71 cont.

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but <= 100	L. monocytogenes > 100 cfu/g	
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - unspecified, ready-to-eat	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0	
Meat, mixed meat - meat products - pâté	Retail	AT		23	3	23	3	22	0	0	
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	Catering	AT		1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	Processing plant	AT		1	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	Retail	AT		222	2	222	2	19	0	0	
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products	Catering	AT		9	0	9	0	8	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT		24	0	24	0	23	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
	Retail	AT		67	0	67	0	65	0	0	
			campaign A-801-13	24	0	24	0	0	0	0	
		EU		8	0	8	0	8	0	0	
			campaign A-801-13	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	
	XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
		campaign A-801-13	1	0	1	0	0	0	0		
	Wholesale	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Catering	AT		8	0	8	0	8	0	0	
	Processing plant	AT		29	1	29	1	29	0	0	
	Retail	AT		49	0	49	0	48	0	0	
			campaign A-801-13	4	0	4	0	0	0	0	
		EU		8	1	8	1	8	0	0	
		XX		2	0	2	0	2	0	0	
	Wholesale	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0	
XX			1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages	Catering	AT		7	1	7	1	7	0	0	
	Game handling establishment	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
	Processing plant	AT		38	2	38	2	38	0	0	
		XX		2	0	2	0	2	0	0	
	Retail	AT		118	3	118	3	94	0	0	
			campaign A-801-13	30	0	30	0	0	0	0	
		EU		30	0	30	0	30	0	0	
			campaign A-801-13	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	
	XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
		campaign A-801-13	1	0	1	0	0	0	0		
Wholesale	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0		
	EU		13	1	13	1	13	0	0		
	XX		2	0	2	0	2	0	0		

Table 71 cont.

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but <= 100	L. monocytogenes > 100 cfu/g
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - pâté	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	Catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Mushrooms	Catering	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Other food	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		6	0	6	0	4	0	0
	Retail	EU		3	0	3	0	0	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Catering	AT		23	1	23	1	20	0	0
	Catering	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		10	0	10	0	7	0	0
	Retail	AT		17	1	17	1	5	0	0
	Retail	EU		5	0	5	0	1	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - ices and similar frozen desserts	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - noodles	Retail	AT		8	0	8	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods	Retail	AT	campaign A-019-13	54	1	54	0	52	1	0
		AT	campaign A-041-13	60	2	60	2	60	0	0
	EU	campaign A-019-13	4	0	4	0	3	0	0	
		campaign A-041-13	2	0	2	0	2	0	0	
	XX	campaign A-019-13	4	0	4	0	3	0	0	
Ready-to-eat salads	Catering	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		8	0	8	0	4	0	0
	Retail	AT		29	0	29	0	5	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Ready-to-eat salads - containing mayonnaise	Retail	AT		7	0	7	0	0	0	0
Sauce and dressings	Retail	AT		6	0	6	0	0	0	0
Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Sweets	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Vegetables	Processing plant	AT		4	1	4	1	4	0	0
	Retail	AT		2	0	0	0	2	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	1	0	0
Wholesale	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
Vegetables - products	Processing plant	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	0	0	0

4.4. Verotoxic *Escherichia coli*

4.4.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2013, 130 laboratory confirmed cases were notified to the EMS; this number was similar as in 2012 (127 cases and 2011 (129 cases). In the years 2007 to 2010 less cases were reported annually, between 88 to 103 cases. Out of the 130 cases, 17 cases of HUS were notified to the EMS.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease

The number of VTEC cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

In 2013, the prevalence of verocytotoxic *E. coli* isolated from animals remained similar compared to last years. In 33 % of samples from cattle (2012: 35%, 2011: 39%) and in 72 % of samples from sheep (2012: 65 %; 2011: 68 % in) VTEC could be isolated. Concerning the 5 most important VTEC serotypes for humans (O157, O26, O103, O111 and O145), in cattle O157 (2 x), O26 (3 x) and O103 (1 x) were isolated but none from sheep.

The relevance of findings of VTEC in faeces seems to be low because VTEC are found only in a very low prevalence on meat samples from bovines and sheep. Meat samples of game show a higher prevalence of VTEC.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

An Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of VTEC prevalence in bovine animals and sheep was implemented according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 November 2003 in the National Orders. The sampling was carried out throughout 2013 and follow up programs will be implemented in the forthcoming years.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Increased awareness and information should be made available for parents, paediatricians and general practitioners in regard to food safety and the prevention of infection.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.4.2. Verocytotoxic *Escherichia coli* in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of VTEC cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

STEC/VTEC diarrhoea

Any person with at least one of the following two symptoms:

- Diarrhoea
- Abdominal pain

HUS

Any person with acute renal failure and at least one of the following two:

- Microangiopathic haemolytic anaemia
- Thrombocytopenia

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following three:

- Isolation of Shigatoxin/Verotoxin (STEC/VTEC) producing *E. coli*
- Detection of *vtx1* or *vtx2* gene(s) nucleic acid
- Detection of free shigatoxins.

Only for HUS the following can be used as laboratory criterion to confirm STEC/VTEC:

- *E. coli* serogroups specific antibody response

Isolation and additional characterisation by serotype, phage type, *eae* genes, and subtypes of *stx1/stx2* should be performed if possible

Case classification

Possible case of STEC-associated HUS

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria for HUS

Probable case of STEC/VTEC

• Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link or a laboratory confirmed case without clinical criteria

Confirmed case of STEC/VTEC

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

1. Detection of *E. coli* O157 (most prominent serotype in HUS cases):

- Bacteriology: Isolation of O157 colonies on Sorbitol-MacConkey agar (or CT-Sorbitol-MacConkey agar) after incubation for 24 hours at 37 °C (or 41°C). O157 is confirmed via the *E. coli* O157 Latex Test.

- Serology: This method is constantly used at the German HUS-"Konsiliarlabor"; anti-O157 antibodies of IgG and IgM types can be distinguished.

2. Detection of Verotoxin (VTEC)-producing strains (used at the National Reference

Laboratory/Center for EHEC/VTEC/STEC): Stools are enriched overnight in a medium containing mitomycin C (EHEC Direct Medium, Heipha, Heidelberg, Germany). Enriched cultures are plated on selective agar (CT-Sorbitol-MacConkey, Enterohemolysin, and Sorbitol-MacConkey). After incubation for 18-24 hours at 37°C a representative mixture of the viable cells were subjected to PCR reactions analyzing *stx1*, *stx2*, *eae* and *Ehly* (Reischl et al. (2002), Journal of Clinical Microbiology, p. 2555-2565). Isolates are gained via colony picking and pathotyped with the same PCR scheme. Isolate identification is further confirmed by conventional biochemical tests (VITEK or Api 20E, bioMerieux, Marcy-l'Etoile, France).

All EHEC/STEC/VTEC isolates obtained in Austria are to be sent to the National Reference Laboratory for confirmation, subtyping and comparison. All Shiga toxin producing *E. coli* are serotyped with *E. coli* antisera (*E. coli* antisera, Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark). Comparison of the isolates is done by Pulsed-Field-Gel-Electrophoresis and Ribotyping.

Notification system in place

Notification of VTEC according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

See History of the disease

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease

Relevance as a zoonotic disease

HUS is a rare complication of *E. coli* infection; however EHECs themselves are not rare, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, most of which are currently unknown. Although raw or undercooked meat and unpasteurised dairy products are likely candidates to transfer the bacterium to humans, the actual source of infection often remains unclear. The importance of hand hygiene after animal contact should be always considered.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 73 Verocytotoxic *Escherichia coli* infections in human - species/serotype distribution (EMS/NRL), 2013

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	autochthonous cases	Imported cases	unknown
HUS	17	0.20	14	3	0
- caused by O157 (VT+)	4	0.05	3	1	0
- caused by other VTEC	9	0.11	7	2	0
- unknown serovar	4	0.05	4		0
VTEC infection (except HUS)	113	1.34	100	13	0
- caused by O157 (VT+)	35	0.41	33	2	0
- caused by other VTEC	54	0.64	49	5	0
- unknown serovar	24	0.28	18	6	0
HUS status not known	0	0.00	0	0	0
All VTEC	130	1.54	114	16	0

Data source: EMS/NRL as of April 23, 2014

Table 74 Verocytotoxic *Escherichia coli* infections in human - age distribution (EMS/NRL), 2013

age groups	<i>E. coli</i> infection (except HUS)			HUS		
	all	m	f	all	m	f
< 1 year	5	1	4	3	2	1
1 to 4 years	58	29	29	6	2	4
5 to 14 years	16	7	9	1	0	1
15 to 24 years	8	6	2	1	1	0
25 to 44 years	11	6	5	2	0	2
45 to 64 years	7	2	5	2	1	1
65 years and older	8	1	7	2	1	1
Gesamtergebnis	113	52	61	17	7	10

Data source: EMS/NRL as of April 23, 2014

4.4.3. Pathogenic *Escherichia coli* in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2013 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2013“ (BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2012) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2013, approximately 26,000 samples were planned (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that has to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail or at the producer.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for specific food items (about 60-65 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2013, 8 food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2013 BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2012). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002. (e. g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). Therefore food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures.

Frequency of the sampling

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Type of specimen taken

Fresh meat, meat preparations, fruits, vegetables etc.

Defintion of positive finding

Detection of *stx1*- and/or *stx2*-positive *E. coli*.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The sample is preenriched for 18-24 h at 37 °C (e. g. in buffered peptone water, modified trypton-soy broth containing novobiocin,). DNA is extracted and a multiplex PCR for detection of genes encoding Vero/Shigatoxin 1 (*stx1*), Vero/Shigatoxin 2 (*stx2*) is performed (according to ISO 20838). There is no further testing for negative PCR results. If the enrichment is PCR-positive, it is streaked on to solid media. Single colonies are tested for the presence of *stx1* and/or *stx2*, or a colony hybridization-blot for the detection of *stx1* and/or *stx2* is performed. The Shigatoxin producing *E. coli* is sent to the National Reference Center for *Escherichia coli* including verotoxin producing *E. coli* (VTEC) in Graz where the presence of the *stx*-genes, *eae*-genes and additional virulence factors is tested by PCR. Subsequently the VTEC is serotyped conventionally (antisera).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Harmonization of methods with regard to all possible VTEC serotypes.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

In 2013, 701 samples of animal origin, 57 samples of non-animal origin and 18 samples of other processed food products and prepared dishes were tested for VTEC. None of 104 samples from milk, milk products and cheeses (all from cows', sheeps' or goats' milk) were tested positive for VTEC. 116 samples of fresh meat of several animal species were tested for VTEC resulting in 3 positive samples (2.6 %). 465 samples of different meat products, minced meat and meat preparations were tested for the presence of VTEC; 3 samples were found positive (0.6 %).

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-801-13: VTEC in food – mixed meat and cheese products – at retail – Surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September - October

Type of specimen taken

Meat, red meat – meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat or fermented sausages
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of VTEC in 25g

Results of the investigation

105 samples tested for VTEC; not VTEC detected

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Salmonella* spp. and *L. monocytogenes*.

Table 75 Verocytotoxic *Escherichia coli* in food, 2013

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive	VTEC O78:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O21:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive
Cheeses made from cows milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1 Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from goats milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from goats milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					25 Gram	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats	campaign A-801-13	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	37	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					25 Gram	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
					25 Gram	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
					25 Gram	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from pasteurised milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	3 Gram	3 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	5 Gram	5 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					25 Gram	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fruits		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					25 Gram	25 Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					25 Gram	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Fruits - products		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					25 Gram	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Table 74 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive	VTEC O78:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O21:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive
Meat from bovine animals - fresh		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Cutting plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	43	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from deer (venison) - fresh		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			25 Gram	25 Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	3	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Game handling establishment	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	6	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from deer (venison) - fresh - frozen		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from horse - fresh		Catering	XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from other animal species or not specified		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified - fresh		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat preparation		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - fresh		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten raw		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 74 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive	VTECO78:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTECO21:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTECO113:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTECOrough:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTECOrough:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTECOrough:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw		Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from rabbit - fresh		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from sheep - fresh		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from wild boar - fresh		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Game handling establishment	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from wild game - birds - fresh		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Game handling establishment	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	48	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - fresh		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	1	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		campaign A-801-13	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AT	single (food/feed)			25	Gram	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
EU	single (food/feed)			25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		campaign A-801-13	Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 74 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive	VTEC O78:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O21:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Game handling establishment	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	38	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	93	3	1	0	1	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	29	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		campaign A-801-13	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
				XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Milk, cows - raw milk		Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Milk, sheeps - raw milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Mushrooms		Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Other food		Retail	XE	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Other processed food products and prepared dishes		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Spices and herbs		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Vegetables		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Vegetables - products		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

4.4.4. Pathogenic *Escherichia coli* in animals

A. Verotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* in cattle (bovine animals)

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

The monitoring program on the prevalence of VTEC in slaughtered cattle was continued. The sampling was stratified based on the number of processed animals per abattoir in Austria. The date of sampling was randomized over the year 2013. Sampling was performed in the 24 abattoirs which processed more than 80 % of Austria's cattle in 2012.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at slaughter

The sampling was distributed randomly over the period of the study from January to December 2013.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at slaughter

A part of the intestine containing rectum and anus.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Animals at slaughter

The sampling was performed by qualified veterinarians who carry out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration, a part of rectum and anus was sampled. After cooling down to 4 °C, the sample had been sent to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMII) in Graz the same day, in a polystyrene box along with cooling packs. In the laboratory, a swab from the rectum-anal mucosa was incubated in a selective broth.

Case definition

Animals at slaughter

An animal is considered to be infected with VTEC following the isolation of VTEC (verocytotoxic *E. coli* irrespective of intimin) from its recto-anal mucosa.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Animals at slaughter

In a first step the samples were screened for production of verocytotoxins by ELISA, secondly verocytotoxin positive samples were processed for VTEC isolation. At first the swab was enriched using EHEC Direktmedium containing mitomycin C for 18 to 24 hours at 37 °C on a shaker. The process was followed by testing the enrichment for the presence of verocytotoxin in an enzyme linked immuno sorbent assay (ELISA, Premier TM EHEC). Sediment of positive enrichments were plated on sorbitol MacConkey (SMAC) -, on cefixime tellurite sorbitol MAC (CTSMAC) -, and on enterohemolysin agar and incubated for 24 hours at 37 °C. Of these 3 selective agar plates altogether five suspect colonies were cultered on sheep blood agar COS. Afterwards the genomes of pure culteres were investigated in a real time PCR for harboring the genes for Verotoxin 1, Verotoxin 2, Intimin and Enterohemolysin (Reischl U. et al. 2002: Real-Time Fluorescence PCR Assays for Detection and Characterization of Shiga Toxin, Intim and Enterohemolysin Genes from Shiga Toxin-Producing *Escherichia coli*. Journ of Clin Microb, 40, p 2555-2565).

The serotyping of VTEC was carried out by the National Reference Center for VTEC in the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Harmonization of methods with regard to all possible VTEC serotypes.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen

Notification system in place

No notification system in place.

Results of the investigation

See table.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The prevalence of isolated VTEC from bovine remained high (33 %); we hypothesize that this is due to a high sensitivity of the ELISA, the sampling material (recto-anal swabs) and the improvement in the VTEC isolation techniques especially the use of the enterohemolysin-agar. Concerning the 5 most important VTEC serotypes for humans (O157, O26, O103, O111 and O145), those isolates were detected in 4.5 % of samples from cattle (2 x O157, 3 x O26, and 1 x O103).

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance of findings of VTEC in feces seems to be low because VTEC are found only in a very low prevalence on meat samples from bovines.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. Verotoxigenic *E. coli* (VTEC) in animal – Sheep

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Monitoring program on the prevalence of VTEC in sheep at farm:

The monitoring in 2013 was directed towards sheep at farms. 126 sheep (out of 126 different farms) had to be tested, calculated on a population of sheep of 350,000 in Austria in 2012. The sampling had been stratified on the number and size of sheep holdings in Austrian provinces.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at farm:

The sampling was done after blood sampling in course of the *Brucella melitensis* control program.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at farm:

Recto-anal swabs

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Animals at farm:

The swab was sent in transport medium cooled down to 4 °C in a polystyrene box after adding cooling units to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz.

Case definition

Animals at farm

An animal is considered to be infected with VTEC following the isolation of VTEC (verocytotoxic *E. coli* irrespective of intimin) from one of the samples tested.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Animals at farm

In a first step the samples were screened for presence of verotoxins by ELISA, secondly the positive samples were processed for VTEC isolation, see chapter cattle.

The serotyping was carried out by the National Reference Laboratory for VTEC in the AGES-Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Harmonization of methods with regard to all possible VTEC serotypes.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen

Notification system in place

No notification

Results of the investigation

See table.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The prevalence of isolated VTEC from sheep remained high (72 %) but we hypothesize that this is due to a higher sensitivity of the new ELISA, the sampling material (recto-anal swabs) and the improvement in the VTEC isolation techniques especially the use of the enterohemolysin-agar.

Concerning the 5 most important VTEC serotypes for humans (O157, O26, O103, O111 and O145), none of them was isolated from sheep in 2013.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance of findings of VTEC in/on sheep seems to be low because sheep meat is consumed well-done.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 76 Verocytotoxic *Escherichia coli* in animals, 2013

animal species	sampling context	Sampling stage	Source of information	Sampling unit	units tested	Verotoxin ELISA positive	units with VTEC isolated	VTEC O 157	VTEC O1:H20 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O103:H2 - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O107:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O112ab:H2 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O112ab:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O113:H4 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:H4 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O113:H4 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:H4 - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O128abc:H2 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O132:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O146:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O146:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O149:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O149:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O153:H25 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O157:HNM - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O166:H28 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O166:H28 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O168:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O168:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O174:H11 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O174:H2 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive		
Cattle (bovine animals) - adult cattle over 2 years	Monitoring - official sampling - objective	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum- anal)	VEMl Graz	Animal	57	29	18	0							1					1																1	1
Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)	Monitoring - official sampling - objective	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum- anal)	VEMl Graz	Animal	4	2	2	0																												1	1
Cattle (bovine animals) - young cattle (1-2 years)	Monitoring - official sampling - objective	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum- anal)	VEMl Graz	Animal	70	34	23	2	2	1	1													1											2	1	3
Sheep	Monitoring - official sampling - objective	at farm - animal sample - mucosal swab	VEMl Graz	Animal	126	94	91	0				1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	3		1	8	4	2	2	1	1				7	1				

In some samples more than 1 VTEC-isolate could be identified.

Table 75 cont.

animal species	sampling context	Sampling stage	Source of information	Sampling unit	units tested	Verotoxin ELISA positive	units with VTEC isolated	VTEC O 157	VTEC O8:H2 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O81:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O82:H8 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O82:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O87:H16 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O87:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O87:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H10 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H11 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H16 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:H2 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H2 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H28 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:H4 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:Hrough - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	
Cattle (bovine animals) - adult cattle over 2 years	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	VEMI Graz	Animal	57	29	18	0		1					1	1							1		1						1	1	
Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	VEMI Graz	Animal	4	2	2	0																									
Cattle (bovine animals) - young cattle (1-2 years)	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	VEMI Graz	Animal	70	34	23	2	1				1		1	1	1				1				1								
Sheep	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at farm - animal sample - mucosal swab	VEMI Graz	Animal	126	94	91	0		2		1	10	1			3	1			1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	

In some samples more than 1 VTEC-isolate could be identified.

4.5. Tuberculosis

4.5.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Human tuberculosis has steadily declined during the last decades. Commission Decision 1999/467/EC of 15 July 1999 declared bovine herds of Austria officially tuberculosis-free.

In humans the number of tuberculosis cases is decreasing. Cases of *M. bovis* or *M. caprae* are very seldom and reactivations of past infections. All *M. caprae* cases in humans in the last years showed different molecular typing patterns than the *M. caprae* isolated from cattle; therefore no human cases could be attributed to the recently cases in bovines.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Bovine tuberculosis poses no public health problem in Austria. Sheep, goats and pigs are free of bovine tuberculosis. Although in spring 2008 infective lung tuberculosis caused by *M. caprae* was diagnosed in one slaughtered cattle. All cattle of that holding were culled following an intra cutan testing showing several positive reactors. Two more cattle holdings with several reactors were culled and some single reactors in contact holdings. In 21 cattle out of 14 holdings *M. caprae* was isolated in 2008. In 2009 again 6 cattle out of 3 holdings were bacteriologically confirmed and in 2010 eight cattle were identified as infected with *M. caprae* and 2011 three cases were found to be positive for *M. caprae*. In 2013, ten bovines out of five herds were infected with *M. caprae*. Since several years a reservoir of *M. caprae* in red deer in an Austrian region has been confirmed and cattle are exposed to the bacteria in the summertime grazing on contaminated pastures in the Alps.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No findings of *M. bovis* in animals, although *M. caprae* was detected. The two cases of *M. caprae* in humans in 2013 are epidemiologically not linked to the *M. caprae* cases in animals.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

In 2011 a new regulation has been implemented to control *M. caprae* in red deer (BGBl. II Nr. 181/2011). The regulation (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 2008/322) obliges the intracutan testings (using simultaneously bovine and avium tuberculin) of all cattle and goats that are kept together with cattle in given districts due to the epidemiological situation.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Continuation of the existing control programs

Additional information

Nil

4.5.2. Tuberculosis in humans

A. Tuberculosis due to *Mycobacterium bovis* in humans

Case definition

Definite: A case with isolation of *M. tuberculosis* complex (except *M. bovis* BCG) from any clinical specimen.

Other than definite: A case that meets the clinical criteria above but does not meet the laboratory criteria of a definite case.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Definite: Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen, Auramin-Rhodamin stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material
- Culture: After decontamination of the homogenised sample material in NALC-NaOH and centrifugation, the sample material is transferred in parallel on Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing glycerol and PACT and Stonebrink agar containing PACT and MGITmedium. The media are incubated at 37 °C for up to 8 weeks. Confirmation of the species by Amplicor (Roche)
- Other than definite: A skin test and an X-Ray of the thorax are performed.

Notification system in place

The person who diagnoses (laboratory/hospital/general practitioner) has to notify definite (*M. tuberculosis* and *M. bovis*) and other than definite cases (this excludes radiologists) to the local health authority (Federal Law BGBl. 127/1968: Tuberkulosegesetz, as amended; Epidemiegesetz 1950, as amended). *M. bovis* is notifiable since 2004 (National Regulation BGBl. Nr. 254/2004: Anzeigepflichtige übertragbare Krankheiten 2004).

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The National Reference Center for Tuberculosis (NRC-T) has been nominated since 1995. Since 1998 all data are compiled in a national database.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

One case of *M. bovis* and two cases of *M. caprae* were identified; the human *M. caprae* cases were epidemiologically not linked to the cases in cattle; the *M. bovis* case occurred in a person (45-64 years of age) and was maybe a case of reactivation, because in Austria *M. bovis* has not been detected in bovines since years.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

The relevance is inconsiderable.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.
Annual report of the National Reference Center

Table 77 Tuberculosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (NRC), 2013

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	autochthonous cases	Imported cases
Tuberculosis	465	5.50	232	245
<i>M. bovis</i>	1	0.01	1	0
<i>M. tuberculosis</i>	415	4.91	197	215
<i>M. caprae</i>	2	0.02	1	1
<i>M. tuberculosis</i> complex (not differentiated)	26	0.31	19	7
Other species (e.g. <i>M. africanum</i>)	3	0.04	1	2
Reactivation of previous cases	18	0.21	13	20

Data source: National Reference Center for Tuberculosis as of April 15, 2014

Table 78 Tuberculosis in humans - age distribution (NRC), 2013

Age group	Tuberculosis due to <i>M. tuberculosis</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. bovis</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. caprae</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. tuberculosis</i> complex (not differentiated)		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	4	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	6	4	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	68	32	36	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0
25 to 44 years	129	79	50	0	0	0	1	1	0	5	4	1
45 to 64 years	112	77	35	1	0	1	0	0	0	6	2	4
65 years and older	94	52	42	0	0	0	1	0	1	13	9	4
Age unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	415	249	166	1	0	1	2	1	1	26	17	9

Data source: National Reference Center for Tuberculosis as of April 15, 2014

4.5.3. *Mycobacterium* spp. in animals

A. *Mycobacterium bovis* in bovine animals

Status as officially free of bovine tuberculosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

According to Council Directive 64/432/EWG from June 26, 1964, Austria has the status Officially Tuberculosis Free Member State declared in the Commission Decision 1999/467/EC from July 15th, 1999, replaced by Commission Decision 2003/467/EC from June 23rd, 2003. The monitoring programme is based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection in which all cattle and goats originating from an official tuberculosis free holding have to be tested for tuberculous alterations.

A national Regulation has been implemented due to the finding of *M. caprae* in cattle from a certain region (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008). This Regulation includes provisions which apply for all *Mycobacteria* belonging to the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex; therefore also a compulsory notification exists.

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Specimens are taken from carcasses with macroscopically observable alterations, characteristic for tuberculosis. They are sampled in slaughterhouses and sent to the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals.

All cattle in holdings of designated regions according article 1 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 322/2008) and published in the Official Veterinary Bulletin were subjected to simultaneous intracutan testing.

Frequency of the sampling

Continuous post-mortem inspections of each slaughtered bovine and caprine animal.

Intracutan testing: All cattle in holdings of designated regions according article 1 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 322/2008) and published in the Official Veterinary Bulletin.

Type of specimen taken

Organs/tissues: Tissues that are macroscopically altered due to tuberculosis, inclusive lymph nodes (according to Annex 4 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008).

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The alterations and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals.

Case definition

According to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008 idgF - Tuberculosis: Infection with *Mycobacteria* of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex. Results of the intracutan test: A reactor is each animal which is not negative (either doubtful or positive). Doubtful and positive reactions are defined (see Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008 idgF).

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Intracutan testing (simultaneous testing using bovine and avium tuberculin): The test is performed according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964, as amended and the national Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 322/2008).

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material.

Culture performed in the AGES National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals in Mödling -

After decontamination of the homogenised sample material (2g, homogenised, add 10 ml buffer) in NALC-NaOH 1% (25 min), neutralization (Sörens. Buffer sol.) and centrifugation (3500g, 20 min), the sample material is transferred on commercial media (heipha/biotest: Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing antibiotics (PACT) and Stonebrink agar containing pyruvate and PACT). The media are incubated at 37°C ± 1°C up to 12 weeks. MTC species are identified with the GenoType MTBC assay (Hain Lifescience GmbH, Nehren, Germany).

Vaccination policy

Due to the importance of the intracutan tests for diagnostic purposes, vaccinations are prohibited.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered bovine and caprine carcasses originating from official tuberculosis free holding and intracutan tests in animals of given regions according to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

The control programs are based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered bovine and caprine carcasses originating from an official tuberculosis free holding. Intracutan tests are performed in animals in holdings of given regions according to the epidemiological situation, defined in the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A national Regulation has been implemented due to the finding of *M. caprae* in cattle from a certain region (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008). This Regulation includes provisions which apply for all mycobacteria belonging to the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex; therefore also a compulsory notification exists.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The carcass is condemned.

Loss of the status OTF for the holding from which the animal was originated and for contact holdings. It is prohibited to bring bovines and goats in and out of the holding. Slaughtering of cows and goats can only be allowed by the official veterinarian and has to be performed using a special testing and slaughtering frame. Epidemiological investigations have to be done.

Prohibition of keeping these animals together with animals from OTF-holdings on pastures or market places etc.

Regaining the status OTF:

There must be no animals in the holding showing signs of clinical tuberculosis

All animals are recruited from an OTF-holding

Animals have to be tested according to the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl II 322/2008).

No reactors are identified after two intradermal testings of all animals in the holding older than 6 months examined earliest 60 days (first tuberculin test) and earliest 4 months (second tuberculin test) but latest 12 months after elimination of the last reactor.

Notification system in place

A suspected case of tuberculosis must be notified.

Results of the investigation

In 2013 no findings of *M. bovis* in cattle. In total 10 bovines from 5 herds were infected with *M. caprae*.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No findings of *M. bovis* in cattle. In total 10 bovines from 5 herds were infected with *M. caprae*. Due to the fact that *M. caprae* is endemic in wildlife deer in Western parts of Austria (and South-Western parts of Germany), cattle in this areas has been observed with higher sensitivity.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

M. caprae is differentiated in Austria.

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Mycobacterium* spp. in animal - all animals - at slaughter – Control programme - mandatory - official sampling (all slaughtered animals except those mentioned above)

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Samples from suspected swine are taken in slaughterhouses. Sampling is performed when tissue of slaughtered animals is visibly altered, seen by the unaided eye.

Goats in defined regions that are kept together with cattle are subjected to intracutan testing (see chapter *Mycobacterium bovis* bovine animals; Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008).

Frequency of the sampling

Continuous post-mortem inspections of each slaughtered animal

Type of specimen taken

Other: Macroscopic tuberculous alterations and lymphnodes

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The altered tissue and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the laboratory

Case definition

Tubercles pathognomically for tuberculosis detected in course of the post-mortem inspection or *Mycobacteria* of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex isolated from suspected material.

Tuberculosis (for bovines and goats which are kept together with bovines): Infection with *Mycobacteria* of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex.

Results of the intracutan test: A reactor is each animal which is not negative (either doubtful or positive).

Reactions are defined (see Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 322/2008).

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material.

Culture performed in the AGES National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals in Mödling - After decontamination of the homogenised sample material (2g, homogenised, add 10 ml buffer) in NALC-NaOH 1% (25 min), neutralization (Sörens. Buffer sol.) and centrifugation (3500g, 20 min), the sample material is transferred on commercial media (heipha/biotest: Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing antibiotics (PACT) and Stonebrink agar containing pyruvate and PACT). The media are incubated at 37°C ± 1°C up to 12 weeks. MTC species are identified with the GenoType MTBC assay (Hain Lifescience GmbH, Nehren, Germany).

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is prohibited.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

See other chapters.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

The control programs are based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all slaughtered carcasses originating from an official tuberculosis free holding

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No need at the moment

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The carcass is condemned. Further measures are performed according to Tierseuchengesetz RGBI. 1909/177, as amended.

Notification system in place

The detection of tuberculosis is notifiable.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No cases in Austria in 2013. *M. caprae* detected in bovines (see previous chapter).

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

No cases in Austria in 2013.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 79 Bovine tuberculosis in countries and regions that do not receive European Union co-financing for eradication programme, 2013

Member State: Austria..... Date of the report: 16.05.2014..... Year: 2013.....

The official post-mortem examination for all slaughtered bovine animals is implemented: Yes

Region (¹)	Total number of existing bovine		Officially free herds (* <i>M. bovis</i>)		Infected herds (* <i>M. bovis</i>)		Routine tuberculin testing		Number of tuberculin tests carried out before the introduction into the herds (Annex A(1)(2)(c) third indent (¹) of Directive 64/432/EEC)	Number of animals with suspicious lesions of tuberculosis examined and submitted to histopathological and bacteriological examinations	Number of animals detected positive in bacteriological examination (* <i>M. bovis</i>)
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Interval between routine tuberculin tests (²)	Number of animals tested			
Austria	67,496	1,961,479	67,496	100	0	0	a) and g)	41,299	112	42	0
Total	67,496	1,961,479	67,496	100	0	0	a) and g)	41,299	112	42	0

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Use the following letter codes: (a) no routine tests; (b) tests once a year; (c) tests every two years; (d) tests every three years concerning 24 month-old animals; (f) tests every 4 years; (g) others (please give details) Sonderuntersuchungs- bzw. überwachungsgebiet.

*Additional information: Table data for *M. bovis*; In 2013, 10 bovines of 5 herds were infected with *M. caprae* (*M. caprae*: officially free herds: 99,9926 %; infected herds: 0,0074%): The control program is identical to the program to control *M. bovis*.

Table 80 Tuberculosis in other animals, 2013

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Mycobacteriaspp.</i>	<i>M. bovis</i>	<i>M. caprae</i>
Sheep	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection	CVS	animal	140,266	0	0	0
Goats	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection	CVS	animal	5,107	0	0	0
Pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection	CVS	animal	5,396,038	0	0	0
Cattle*	at farm – animal sampling	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - selective sampling	tuberculin testing in special tuberculosis examination and control areas	CVS	animal	41,299	10	0	10

*TBC-Sonderuntersuchungsgebiete sowie TBC-Sonderüberwachungsgebiete

CVS: Central veterinary services

* all cases microbiologically verified as *M. caprae* cases

4.6. Brucellosis

4.6.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In Austria, human brucellosis cases are considered to be an imported infectious disease. The Austrian cattle, sheep and goat population bears the status Officially Brucellosis Free (OBF) and Officially *Brucella melitensis* free (OBmF).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Seven human cases were identified in 2013. The number of Brucellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No findings in Austria, OBF and OBmF

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A national regulation has been implemented. The examination of milk- and bloodsamples in cattle (Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBL II 2007/305).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Continuation of the existing control programs

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.6.2. Brucellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Brucellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with fever

AND at least one of following seven symptoms:

- Sweating (profuse, malodorous, specially nocturnal)
- Chills
- Arthralgia
- Weakness
- Depression
- Headache
- Anorexia

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Isolation of *Brucella* spp. from a clinical specimen
- *Brucella* specific antibody response (Standard Agglutination Test, Complement Fixation, ELISA)

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Serological examination: Serum samples are tested in the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) with reference standard antisera from CVL-Weybridge. Participation in international ring trials: Brucellosis European Ring Trial 2000 and 2002 (VLA Weybridge) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and SAT.

- Bacteriological: Multiple blood samples are inoculated in blood culture broth over several consecutive days. The incubation lasted 4 to 6 weeks, once per week medium is transferred on *Brucella* agar and incubated 5-10 % CO₂ atmosphere (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123- 126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 56).

- The genus is identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using *Brucella* antiserum. The species is identified by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific antisera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.)

Notification system in place

Notification of Brucellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Austria is OBF and OBmF. All cases reported in Austria are epidemiologically linked to travel in endemic countries or to foreign workers from endemic countries.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

This zoonosis has no relevance in Austria.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 81 Brucellosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS/NRL), 2013

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	autochthonous cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
Brucellosis	7	0.08	0	6	1
<i>B. abortus</i>	1	0.01	0	1	0
<i>B. melitensis</i>	4	0.05	0	4	0
<i>B. suis</i>	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Brucella</i> spp.	2	0.02	0	1	1

Data source: EMS/NRL (as of 24.04.2014)

Table 82 Brucellosis in humans - age distribution (EMS/NRL), 2013

Age group	Brucellosis			<i>Brucella melitensis</i>			<i>Brucella abortus</i>		
	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f
< 1 year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1 to 4 years	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5 to 14 years	2	2	-	-	-	-	1	1	-
15 to 24 years	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
25 to 44 years	3	2	1	3	2	1	-	-	-
45 to 64 years	2	1	1	1	-	1	-	-	-
65 years and older	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Age unknown	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
All age groups	7	5	2	4	2	2	1	1	0

Data source: EMS/NRL (as of 24.04.2014)

4.6.3. *Brucella* in foodstuffs

Due to the fact that Austria is OBF and OBmF, food is not investigated for *Brucella* spp.

4.6.4. *Brucella* spp. in animals

A. *Brucella abortus* in bovine Animals

Status as officially free of bovine brucellosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

Upon the request of the Commission Decision of July 15th 1999, CD 1999/466/EC, as amended, by the Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964, Austria achieved the status: officially brucellosis-free for bovine herds.

A national regulation has been implemented concerning the examination of milk- and bloodsamples in cattle (Bangeeuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 305/2007). In the case of dairy herds, the examination of milk samples in accordance with Annex C of Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964 can be performed.

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Nationwide all bovine milk producing holdings were subjected to bulk milk testing. In non-milk producing holdings a risk based blood sampling plan was performed. Abortion or premature birth: Abortive material and blood of the cow is sampled

Frequency of the sampling

Bulk milk sampling: All milk producing holdings had been sampled minimum once per year according to the regulation (§6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBL II 305/2007). In case of not-negative bulk milk samples, blood samples in the affected holding were investigated.

Holdings without milk production: A risk based sampling plan has been calculated stratified according to the different provinces (§6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBL II 2007/305). If blood serology does not show a definitive negative result diagnostic slaughtering of the affected animal has to be carried out.

- Abortion or premature birth: abortion in cattle must be notified to the district veterinarian (§11 Bangseuchengesetz 1957, BGBL 1957/147). Tissues from the aborted fetus and blood from the affected cows are sampled immediately post abortion and tested for brucellosis by microbiological and serological methods.

Type of specimen taken

Bulk milk

Blood samples

Aborted fetus

Diagnostic slaughtering: organs and lymph nodes of the genital tract; udder and accessory lymph nodes; fetus (stomach, lungs); retropharyngeal lymph node.

Abortion or premature birth: Tissue and blood samples from the animal that had an abortion.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Bulk milk sampling: §6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBL II 305/2007.

Holdings without milk production: According to the sampling plan individual blood samples are taken in the holdings and sent to the laboratories (§6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBL II 2007/305).

Diagnostic slaughtering: §6 Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBL II 305/2007.

Abortion or premature birth: Aborted tissue and blood samples sent to a veterinary laboratory.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be positive for *Brucella abortus*, in case of positive blood-serological test result and the epidemiological situation of the herd indicates the possibility that a *Brucella* infection has been introduced to the herd or in case of bacteriological isolation. If a single animal reactor is detected in the holding, tracing back is an important tool to get more information about the animal.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bulk milk: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE.

Blood samples: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE: Routinely single serum samples or serum pools (5 sera in one pool) were tested in the Indirect-ELISA (I-ELISA) using the three OIE ELISA Brucella Standard Sera (OIE ELISAwSS, OIE ELISAspSS, OIE ELISAnSS) and the OIE *Brucella abortus* Positive International Standard Antiserum (OIEISS) to calibrate the method (Commission Regulation 535/2002/EC of 21 March 2002 amending Annex C to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and amending Decision 2000/330/EC). Following a positive or suspected test result in the IELISA single serum samples were tested in the Complement Fixation Test (CFT), Rose Bengal test (RBT) and two ELISAs for verification.

Participation in international ring trials: Participation in international ring trials (AHVLA, ANSES) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and Serum Agglutination Test (SAT). The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for those Austrian Veterinary Institutes which are involved in brucellosis surveillance and diagnosis.

Abortion or premature birth: Aborted material was tested bacteriologically as described above. Bacteriology: Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforth's method. Columbia agar (bioMérieux) and Columbia agar (BD) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media were incubated for 5 days at 37 °C in an atmosphere containing 10% CO₂. The genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using *Brucella* antiserum. The species was differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific antisera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

All serologically inconclusive or positive blood samples were sent to the National Reference Laboratory for confirmation respectively exclusion of serological cross reactions with other bacteria like *Yersinia enterocolitica*.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not allowed (BGBl. 147/1957, Bangseuchengesetz, § 13 Impfung)

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Control programme according to the National Regulation (Bangseuchen-Untersuchungsverordnung 2008, BGBl II 305/2007). Abortion or premature birth: Compulsory notification according BGBl 147/1957, Bangseuchengesetz, as amended, §11 Anzeigepflicht;

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No actions, because OBF

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to BGBl 147/1957, Bangseuchengesetz, as amended, and BGBl 177/1909, Tierseuchengesetz, as amended

Notification system in place

Abortion or premature birth: Notification of abortions: The livestock owner has to notify each abortion within 24 hours to the mayor (Gemeinde). The mayor has to forward the notification to the district veterinarian (Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde) (BGBl. 147/1957, Bangseuchengesetz, § 11 Anzeigepflicht). If the cow is being treated by a veterinarian or the veterinarian has been informed about the abortion, then the veterinarian has to notify to the official authority (Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde).

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

OBF

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. Brucella melitensis in Sheep and Goats

Status as officially free of ovine brucellosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

According to Commission Decision Nr. 93/52/EWG, as amended, Austria has the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free (ObmF).

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

To maintain the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free, according to BGBl. II 184/2002 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002) a representative number of samples were examined with a confidence level of 95 % to detect infected holdings at a target prevalence of 0.2 %. Sampling was performed by the competent authority or under its supervision, by bodies to which it had delegated this responsibility. Samples were taken in the holdings. Aborted material and blood samples from the animal were also investigated.

Frequency of the sampling

Mainly the sampling was performed during the cold season, between November and May when the animals were kept in the stables.

Type of specimen taken

- Monitoring: Blood samples according to a sampling plan.
- Clinical cases: Aborted material and blood samples from the affected animal.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Individual blood samples and aborted material are taken within the holdings and sent to the laboratories.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be infected with *B. melitensis* in case of bacteriological isolation or positive serological test result.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Routinely single serum samples were tested in the Indirect ELISA. Confirmation of suspected or positive results was performed by the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) with reference standard antisera from AHVLA and ANSES. Participation in international ring trials on Brucellosis with ELISA, CFT and RBT. The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all national Veterinary Institutes.

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples were stained by Stableforth's method. Columbia agar (bioMérieux) and Columbia agar (BD) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media were incubated for 5 days at 37 °C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. The genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using *Brucella* antiserum. The species were differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific antisera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

According to BGBl. II 184/2002 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002, § 4, Impfverbot) vaccination is not allowed.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Monitoring program and investigation of abortions

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

To maintain the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free, according to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002) a representative number of samples have to be examined with a confidence level of 95 % to detect infected holdings at a prevalence of 0.2 %. Sampling is performed by the appropriate authority or under its supervision, by bodies to which it has delegated this responsibility. Samples are taken in the holdings.

Notification and clarification of each clinical case by bacteriology and serology.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

ObmF

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002, § 3, Ausmerzung von Reagenten) reactors have to be culled, the carcasses have to be incinerated in an incineration plant.

Notification system in place

Notification of brucellosis or a suspicion of brucellosis according to BGBl. 391/1995 (*Brucellose-Verordnung*).

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

ObmF

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

D. *Brucella suis* in animal – Pigs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

According to Guideline 64/432/EEC as amended.

Frequency of the sampling

Targeted, following abortion and in positive cases contact holdings.

Type of specimen taken

- Monitoring: Blood samples;
- Clinical cases: Abortion material and blood samples from the affected animal; tissues: according to decree 74700/0132-IV/B/5/2008

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Individual blood samples and abortion material are taken from animals in the holdings and sent to the laboratories.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be serologically positive for brucellosis following one/more positive CFT Complement Fixation Test (CFT) and RBT Rose Bengal test (RBT) results (*B. abortus* used antigen). A bacteriological isolation may also be possible as in the case of *B. suis*.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- *Brucella* ELISA and CFT are used.
 - Participation in international ring trials: Brucellosis European Ring Trial 2000 and 2002 (AHVLA and ANSES) with ELISA, CFT and RBT. The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all Veterinary Institutes.
- Bacteriology:
- Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforth's method.
 - Columbia agar (bioMérieux) and Columbia agar (BD) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media were incubated for 5 days at 37 °C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. The genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using *Brucella* antiserum. The species were differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific antisera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No mandatory measures but notification is required.

Notification system in place

B. suis has been a notifiable disease since 1993 according to BGBl 1993/756, Tierseuchen-Anzeigepflichtverordnung, as amended.

Results of the investigation

There was no case of *Brucella suis* in 2013.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Due to the results of the passive monitoring in pigs we conclude that there is no need for an active monitoring program.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 83 Bovine Brucellosis data from countries and regions that do not receive European Union co-financing (non co-financed), 2013

Member State: Austria Date of report: 16.05.2014..... Year: 2013.....

Region ⁽¹⁾	Total number of existing bovine		Officially free herds		Infected herds		Surveillance ⁽²⁾					Investigations of suspect cases									
			Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Serological tests			Examination of bulk milk samples		Information on abortions			Epidemiological investigation						
	Herds	Animals					Number of bovine herds tested	Number of animals tested	Number of infected herds	Number of bovine herds tested	Number of animals or pools tested	Number of infected herds	Number of notified abortions whatever cause	Number of isolations of <i>Brucella</i> infection	Number of abortions due to <i>Brucella abortus</i>	Number of animals tested with serological blood tests	Number of suspended herds	Number of positive animals		Number of animals examined microbiologically	Number of animals positive microbiologically
																	Serologically	BST			
Austria	67,496	1,961,479	67,496	100	0	0	1,328	10,367	0	1,266	1,266	0	810	0	0	442	2	0	0	0	0
Total	67,496	1,961,479	67,496	100	0	0	1,328	10,367	0	1,266	1,266	0	810	0	0	442	2	0	0	0	0

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Please give details.

Table 84 Ovine and caprine brucellosis - data from countries that do not receive co-financing for control or eradication programme, 2013

Member State: Austria..... Date of report: 22.05.2014..... Year: 2013.....

Region (1)	Total number of existing ovine/caprines		Officially free herds		Infected herds		Surveillance (2)			Investigations of suspect cases				
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Number of herds tested	Number of animals tested	Number of infected herds	Number of animals tested with serological blood tests	Number of animals positive serologically	Number of animals examined micro-biologically	Number of animals positive micro-biologically	Number of suspended herds
Austria	23,182	510,015	23,182	100	0	0	1,528	20,611	0	8	0	1	0	6
Total	23,182	510,015	23,182	100	0	0	1,528	20,611	0	8	0	1	0	6

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services, Provincial Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Please give details.

Total number of existing ovine/caprines herds: Number is less than in Table 1 (Susceptible animal populations) because mixed farms are deducted from the sum.

4.7. Yersiniosis

4.7.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Yersiniosis is not considered a major food borne illness in Austria. The incidence of human disease is low when compared to salmonellosis or campylobacteriosis and has been stable over the last years.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of Yersiniosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

The sources of infections are unclear. Neither studies on sporadic cases nor scientific outbreak investigations were performed in Austria so far.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.7.2. Yersiniosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Yersiniosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following five symptoms:

- Fever
- Diarrhoea
- Vomiting
- Abdominal pain (pseudoappendicitis)
- Tenesmus

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of human pathogenic *Yersinia enterocolitica* or *Yersinia pseudotuberculosis* from a clinical specimen

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Sample material is plated directly on cefsulodin-irgasan-novobiocin (CIN) agar and incubated for 18 hours at 30 °C. Suspicious colonies are identified in an Api 20 E reaction and API 50 CHE reaction.

Y. enterocolitica is agglutinated with sera against serogroups O:3; O:5,27; O:9 and O:8. Biovar and pathogenicity are defined.

Notification system in place

Notification of Yersiniosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Yersiniosis is the third most bacterial food borne pathogen in Austria although compared to salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis, the number of notified cases are much lower.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of human cases has been similar in the last years.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In Austria, yersiniosis is much less identified than salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 85 Yersiniosis in human - species/serotype distribution (EMS/NRL), 2013

Yersiniosis	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	autochthonous cases	Imported cases	unknown status
pathogenic types	104	1.23	87	11	6
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:3 biovar 2	1	0.01	0	0	1
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:3 biovar 3	3	0.04	3	0	0
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:3 biovar 4	76	0.90	62	9	5
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:9 biovar 2	20	0.24	18	2	0
<i>Yersinia pseudotuberculosis</i>	4	0.05	4	0	0
unknown/no pathogenicity	57	0.67	46	4	7
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:8 biovar 1A	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> serovar unknown biovar 1A	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> , serovar and biovar unknown	53	0.63	43	3	7
<i>Yersinia</i> spp.	2	0.02	1	1	0

Data source: EMS/NRL as of 23.4.2014

Table 86 Yersiniosis in humans - age distribution (EMS/NRL), 2013

age groups	<i>Yersinia</i> spp.			<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:3 biovar 4			<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:9 biovar 2			<i>Yersinia</i> <i>pseudotuberculosis</i>		
	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f
< 1 year	8	7	1	3	3	0	2	2	0	1	0	1
1 to 4 years	22	13	9	14	9	5	4	2	2	1	1	0
5 to 14 years	32	18	14	18	12	6	1	1	0	1	0	1
15 to 24 years	21	10	11	15	5	10	0	0	0	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	28	11	17	13	6	7	5	1	4	0	0	0
45 to 64 years	30	15	15	11	5	6	5	4	1	0	0	0
65 years and older	20	6	14	2	0	2	3	1	2	1	1	0
Total	161	80	81	76	40	36	20	11	9	4	2	2

Data source: EMS/NRL as of 23.4.2014

4.7.3. *Yersinia* in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Foodstuff was sampled according to the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2013 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2013“ (BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2012) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004.

The Revision-Plan determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be sampled and tested randomly according to the number of food enterprises per province. Every business within Austria has to be sampled at least once per year. The inspection can comprise sampling, hygienic investigations of the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

In 2013, approximately 26,000 samples were planned (surveillance) and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). These planned samples consist of samples of the yearly sampling plan which determines the number of samples of each food category that has to be investigated randomly, e.g. raw meat (fresh or frozen); sausages; cheeses; milk; preserved food etc. There are different sampling stages where food samples are taken: e.g. from retail or at the producer.

In addition there is a monitoring plan for specific food items (about 60-65 campaigns per year). In the course of these programs food items of special interest for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents – are investigated. The sampling takes place during a fixed period of time in order to gain in-depth information. In 2013, 8 food campaign programs were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2013 BMG-75500/0185-II/B/13/2012). Details and results of these campaigns can be found in the respective chapters.

Results

No *Yersinia* isolated from food

Table 87 *Yersinia* in food, 2013

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Yersinia</i>
Bakery products		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - soft and semi-soft		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0

4.7.4. *Yersinia* spp. in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not relevant in Austria therefore no testing.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination.

Other preventative measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

EU wide harmonized monitoring program.

Notification system in place:

Findings of *Yersinia* are not notifiable in animals.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No changes in recent years.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance has not been investigated.

Additional information

Nil

4.8. Trichinellosis

4.8.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

No documented autochthon human infestations since several years.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of Trichinellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of cases reported to the EMS. No documented autochthone human infestations in 2013.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No cases in farmed animals in 2013, one case in a wild boar.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No new measures implemented

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Reconsider the necessity of routine trichinella meat inspection in pig carcasses

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.8.2. Trichinellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Trichinellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least three of the following six symptoms:

- Fever
- Muscle soreness and pain
- Diarrhoea
- Facial oedema
- Eosinophilia
- Subconjunctival, subungual and retinal haemorrhages

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Demonstration of Trichinella larvae in tissue obtained by muscle biopsy
- Trichinella specific antibody response (IFA test, ELISA or Western Blot)

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

ELISA and Westernblot

Notification system in place

Notification of Trichinellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The last autochthonous cases have been reported in 1970

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance as zoonotic disease

No relevance in Austria

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry of Health. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 88 Trichinellosis in human - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2013

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Imported cases	Unkown
Trichinellosis	0	0.00	0	0
Trichinella spiralis	0	0.00	0	0

Data source: EMS as of April 23, 2014

4.8.3. *Trichinella* spp. in animals

A. *Trichinella* spp. in pigs

Number of officially recognised *Trichinella*-free holdings

Categories of holdings officially recognised *Trichinella*-free

Officially recognised regions with negligible *Trichinella* risk

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

General

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered pigs except pigs slaughtered by the farmer for his own consumption; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling**General**

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered pig

Type of specimen taken**General**

Muscles: Diaphragm (crus), tongue, masseter and abdominal muscles.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)**General**

Appropriate muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition**General**

Trichinella spp. detected with one of the given methods

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005

Vaccination policy

Nil

Preventive measures in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms**The control program/strategies in place**

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004, as amended.

The contingency plan in place**Notification system in place****Results of the investigation including description of the positive cases and the verification of the *Trichinella* species****National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection**

No findings of *Trichinella* in farmed animals, one wild boar positive for *Trichinella*.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Trichinella* spp. in horses

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered horses; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme

Frequency of the sampling

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered horse

Type of specimen taken

Muscles from tongue, masseter, diaphragm and neck.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Appropriate muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

Trichinella spp. detected with one of the given methods.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

Results of the investigation

No findings in horses.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No findings in horses.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

C. *Trichinella* spp. in animal - wild boars

Monitoring system**Sampling strategy**

Sampling of all hunted or harvested wild boars; the sampling is performed by hunters with special knowledge about trichinella investigation or by competent authorities; the sampling is stratified by geographical regions depending to the habitats of wild boar in Austria; samples are taken either immediately after shooting the animal or at the cold storage depots; the sampling is part of a monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling

All farmed wild boars are controlled for trichinella.

Type of specimen taken

Diaphragm muscles (crus), tongue, masseter and abdominal muscles.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Appropriate muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

Trichinella spp. detected with one of the given methods.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms**The control program/strategies in place**

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2013, *Trichinella* spp. was detected in one wild boar (not farmed).

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 89 *Trichinella* spp. in animals, 2013

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Trichinella</i> spp.
Pigs							
fattening pigs raised under controlled housing conditions in integrated system							
fattening pigs not raised under controlled housing conditions in integrated system	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	5,396,038	0
breeding animals -unspecified - sows and boars							
Domestic solipeds							
horses	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	1,004	0
Wild boars							
wild	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	21,182	1
farmed	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	547	0
Foxes				CVS	animal	7	0
Badger				CVS	animal	8	0
Dear				CVS	animal	1	0
Rodents							
Rats							

CVS: Central Veterinary Services

4.9. Echinococcosis

4.9.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Austria is a low risk country for both forms of echinococcosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of echinococcosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases reported to the EMS.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Alveolar echinococcosis: Due to the infestation rates of red foxes in Austria (0-40 %) there is a relatively elevated risk for hunters, cat owners and farmers.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Tools for preventive serological screening of hunters (and also other persons) have been established to detect *Echinococcus multilocularis* infections in an early stage. The early detection of the infection is the prerequisite for a successful curative treatment.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.9.2. Echinococcosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Echinococcosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Not relevant for surveillance purposes

Diagnostic criteria

At least one of the following five findings:

- Histopathology or parasitology compatible with *Echinococcus multilocularis* or *granulosus* (e.g. direct visualisation of the protoscolex in cyst fluid)
- Detection of *Echinococcus granulosus* pathognomonic macroscopic morphology of cyst(s) in surgical specimens
- Typical organ lesions detected by imaging techniques (e.g.: computerised tomography, sonography, MRI) AND confirmed by a serological test
- *Echinococcus* spp. specific serum antibodies by high-sensitivity serological test AND confirmed by a high specificity serological test
- Detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* or *granulosus* nucleic acid in a clinical specimen

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- NA

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the diagnostic criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

ELISA and Westernblot technique, participant of the UK National External Quality Assessment Service for Microbiology, National Reference Laboratory for Echinococcosis.

Notification system in place

Notification of echinococcosis according to the Federeal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

- Alveolar echinococcosis has been known in Austria since 1897; annual incidence (1897- 2004): 0-6 cases, mean incidence: 2.4 cases/year (only autochthonous cases); geographic distribution in Austria: mainly in the western provinces (Vorarlberg, Tyrol, Salzburg), but cases have been reported in every province; outbreaks are not known.
- Cystic echinococcosis has been known in Austria at least since 1819; Cases of cystic echinococcosis have been registered in the Clinical Institute of Hygiene and Medical Microbiology (Medical University Vienna) regularly since the beginning of the 1980ies. Annual incidence (1984 - 2006): 20 - 60 cases; mean incidence: 31 cases per year, one third of patients are of Austrian origin; two thirds are from abroad. Geographic distribution in Austria is unknown; a few autochthonous infections could be observed mainly in the eastern and southern provinces (Lower Austria, Burgenland, and Styria); outbreaks are not known.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

- Alveolar echinococcosis: We expect the future incidence to be low; sources of infestation: fox faeces (contaminated hands and fingers, vegetables, water).
- Cystic echinococcosis: We expect the future incidence to be low; sources of infestation: dog faeces, presumably in a very few foci (in or around farmers houses)

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Low incidence of both forms of echinococcosis

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 90 Echinococcosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2013

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	autochthonous cases	imported cases	unknown
Echinococcosis	11	0.13	11	0	0
<i>E. granulosus</i>	2	0.02	2	0	0
<i>E. multilocularis</i>	9	0.11	9	0	0

Data source: EMS as of April 10, 2014

Table 91 Echinococcosis in humans - age distribution (EMS), 2013

Age group	<i>E. multilocularis</i>			<i>E. granulosus</i>		
	all	m	f	all	m	f
< 1 year	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	0	0	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	0	0	0	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	1	0	1	2	2	0
45 to 64 years	6	4	2	0	0	0
65 years and older	2	1	1	0	0	0
Age unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	9	5	4	2	2	0

Data source: EMS as of April 10, 2014

4.9.3. *Echinococcus* spp. in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Targeted sampling of all in abattoirs slaughtered animals; the sampling is performed by competent authorities in course of the post-mortem meat inspection; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered animal

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

All organs and muscles that were used for human consumption

Case definition

Each carcass in which cysts, cystic or alveolar hydatids are detected in muscles or organs

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

All organs and muscles that were used for human consumption were visually inspected, palpated and cuttings were performed

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Post-mortem meat inspection act according to BGBl. 1982/522, Fleischuntersuchungsgesetz, as amended

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Cystic or alveolar echinococcosis in animals that are used for food production do not play a role for the infection of humans; it is primarily a hygienic problem.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 92 *Echinococcus* sp. in animals, 2013

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Echinococcus</i> spp.	<i>E. multilocularis</i>	<i>E. granulosus</i>	<i>Echinococcus</i> spp., unspecified
Cattle*	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	623,272	129			129
Sheep	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	140,266	43			43
Goats	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	5,107	0			0
Pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	5,396,038	0			0

* cattle including calves

All detected cysts are reported as echinococcus but not differentiated (could also be other species than *Echinococcus* spp.).

x: Central Veterinary Services, Statistics Austria

4.10. Toxoplasmosis

4.10.1. General evaluation

Toxoplasmosis in humans is not notifiable. Samples from pregnant women (amniotic liquor) in Austria are tested in the Toxoplasmosis-Laboratory via PCR. If toxoplasma is detected, umbilical cord blood is tested as a kind of quality control. Neonates from infected mothers are controlled as follow-up.

4.10.2. *Toxoplasma* in humans

Toxoplasmosis in humans is not notifiable. Samples from pregnant women (amniotic liquor) in Austria are tested in the Toxoplasmosis-Laboratory via PCR. If toxoplasma is detected, umbilical cord blood is tested as a kind of quality control. Neonates from infected mothers are controlled as follow-up.

4.10.3. *Toxoplasma* in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

There is no official surveillance for *Toxoplasma* spp. in animals. Sampling of cattle, sheep, goats or pigs is performed depending on clinical suspicion of toxoplasmosis and if ordered by the sender in cases after abortion. Other animal species are also occasionally sampled.

Frequency of the sampling

In case of clinical suspicion and abortion and if ordered.

Type of specimen taken

Blood, fetus, organ, faeces

Case definition

A case is defined as an animal that tested positive serologically ($\geq 1:40$) or if the pathogen is detected microscopically. The animal is the epidemiological unit.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The diagnostic methods used for serology is the direct agglutination (DA) test. Organs are tested by real time PCR and/or histology and/or immunohistochemistry (IHC).

Vaccination policy:

No vaccination

Other preventative measures than vaccination in place:

Control programme/ mechanisms:

The control programmes/ strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases:**Notification system in place:**

Toxoplasmosis is not notifiable in animals.

Results of the investigation

see table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection:

Nil

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection):

unknown

Additional information

Nil

Table 93 Toxoplasmosis in animals, 2013

animal species	sampling context	sampling details	Analytical method	sampling unit	Source of information	Units tested	Total units positive for Toxoplasma
cattle	clinical investigation	blood	DA	animal	AGES IVET	6	1
sheep	clinical investigation	blood	DA	animal	AGES IVET	61	23
sheep	clinical investigation	organs	PCR, IHC	animal	AGES IVET	3	0
goat	clinical investigation	blood	DA	animal	AGES IVET	37	6
goat	clinical investigation	organs*	PCR, IHC	animal	AGES IVET	1	0
chamois	hunting	organs*	PCR, IHC	animal	AGES IVET	1	0
hare	hunting	organs*	PCR, IHC	animal	AGES IVET	1	1
cat	clinical investigation	organs*	histology	animal	AGES IVET	1	1

DA - direct agglutination

* Organs are tested by real time PCR and/or histology and/or immunohistochemistry (IHC)

4.11. Rabies

4.11.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Rabies in humans was a major public health issue in the 1960s.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2013, there was no case of rabies detected in animals in Austria.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

In 2013, due to official rabies free status in Austria (since 28.9.2008) oral vaccination of foxes has been suspended; monitoring is carried out on indicator animals (foxes, badgers, racoons, racoon dogs found dead, victims of road traffic or clinical suspect), according to EFSA's recommendation "Development of harmonised schemes for monitoring and reporting of rabies in animals in the European Union" (<http://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/supporting/doc/67e.pdf>).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

Nil

4.11.2. Rabies in humans

Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with an acute encephalomyelitis

AND

At least two of the following seven symptoms:

- Sensory changes referred to the site of a preceding animal bite
- Paresis or paralysis
- Spasms of swallowing muscles
- Hydrophobia
- Delirium
- Convulsions
- Anxiety

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following four:

- Isolation of Lyssa virus from a clinical specimen
- Detection of Lyssa virus nucleic acid in a clinical specimen (e.g. saliva or brain tissue)
- Detection of viral antigens by a DFA in a clinical specimen
- Lyssa virus specific antibody response by virus isneutralisation assay in serum or CSF

Laboratory results need to be interpreted according to the vaccination or immunisation status

Case classification

Possible case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Liquor, smears from pharynx, swab from conjunctivae biopsy at the nape of the neck and serum were examined in the fluorescent antibody test (FAT), immunohistochemistry and RT-PCR (Ito M., Itou T., Sakai T., et al. (2001). Detection of Rabies Virus RNA isolated from several species of animals in Brazil by RT-PCR. Journal of Veterinary medicine Science 63(12): 1309-1313.).

Notification system in place

Notification of rabies according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Nil

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Nil

Table 94 Rabies in humans, 2013

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases
Rabies	0	0	0	0
Human exposure	0	0	0	0

Data source: EMS as of April 23, 2014

4.11.3. Lyssavirus (rabies) in animals**A. Rabies virus in animal - Wildlife****Monitoring system****Sampling strategy**

According to the degree Überwachung der Tollwut 2013 (BMG-74600/0309-II/B/11/2012) monitoring is carried out on indicator animals (foxes, badgers, racoons, racoon dogs found dead, victims of road traffic or clinical suspect).

Frequency of the sampling

Monitoring is carried out on indicator animals (foxes, badgers, racoons, racoon dogs found dead, victims of road traffic or clinical suspect), according to EFSA's recommendation "Development of harmonised schemes for monitoring and reporting of rabies in animals in the European Union".

Type of specimen taken

Brain (brain stem and/or hippocampus)

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Whole animals or heads of the dead animals are sent to the laboratories; sometimes brain tissue (derived from other laboratories). Brain tissue (e.g. 1 cm²) is examined.

Case definition

An animal is considered positive if the fluorescent antibody test (FAT) shows a positive signal.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The routine test was the fluorescent antibody test (FAT).

RTCIT (rabies tissue culture infection test) was performed on mouse neuroblastoma cells.

MIT (mouse inoculation test) will be only performed on demand, not for routine confirmation

Vaccination policy

Due to official status rabies free no vaccination of foxes.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Fuchs-Tollwutbekämpfungsverordnung 2010 BGBl II 2010/329, Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42, Tierseuchengesetz-Durchführungsverordnung 1909/178 as amended: BGBl 1955/76 TSG-DVO zum IV. Abschnitt Wutkrankheiten; degree Überwachung der Tollwut 2013 (BMG-74600/0309-II/B/11/2012).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Probably the reduction of the number of the animals (foxes) for investigation.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42, and vaccination of the fox population.

Notification system in place

According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Austria is declared as rabies free since 28.9.2008.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

B. Rabies virus in animal - all animals except foxes

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Sampling is targeted when animals are observed with central neural symptoms or after biting a person. The suspicious animal is killed or euthanized and the carcass or head is sent to the laboratory.

Frequency of the sampling

If a case is suspected

Type of specimen taken

Brain (hippocampus and brain stem)

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Routinely 2 parts from the brain will be taken: hippocampus and brain stem.

Case definition

An animal is considered positive if the fluorescent antibody tests (FAT) or the rabies tissue culture infection test or the mouse inoculation test show a positive result.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The routine test was the fluorescent antibody test (FAT).

RTCIT (rabies tissue culture infection test) was performed on mouse neuroblastoma cells.

MIT (mouse inoculation test) will be only performed on demand, not for routine confirmation

Vaccination policy

Voluntary vaccination of pets.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place is the Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBI I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42; Tierseuchengesetz-Durchführungsverordnung 1909/178 as amended: BGBI 1955/76.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBI I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42. If a rabies suspicious pet bites a person, the person is treated.

Notification system in place

According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBI I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

On 28th of September 2008, Austria has been declared free of rabies.
2013 oral vaccination of foxes was suspended all over Austria.

Table 95 Rabies in animals, 2013

Animal species	Source of information	Sampling strategy	Sampler	Sample type	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for Lyssa virus (rabies)
Cattle	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	5	0
Sheep	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	1	0
Goats	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	0	0
Domestic solipeds	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	1	0
Dogs	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	35	0
Cats	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	39	0
Wildlife							
Bats-wild, passive surveillance	NRL	Found dead	not applicable	brain	Animal	17	0
Foxes- wild, monitoring	NRL	monitoring	official sampling	brain	Animal	181	0
Foxes	NRL	clinical suspect	not applicable	brain	Animal	224	0
Other farm, wild or pet animals (please add the relevant species)							
Badgers	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	9	0
Badgers	NRL	monitoring	official sampling	brain	Animal	41	0
Martens	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	22	0
other mustelide	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	7	0
Wild boar	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	4	0
Deer	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	0	0
Chamois	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	0	0
Others (e.g. squirrels, mice, rats)	NRL	clinical suspect	official sampling	brain	Animal	13	0

Immunofluorescence antibody test (IFAT)

Data source: NRL Rabies as of 25.04.2014

4.12. Q-Fever

4.12.1. General evaluation of the situation

No information

4.12.2. Q-fever in humans

Not notifiable in Austria, therefore no data available

4.12.3. *Coxiella burnetii* in animals

Not notifiable in Austria

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

There is no official surveillance for *Coxiella burnetii* in animals.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The diagnostic method is the complement fixation reaction, detecting phase 1 and phase 2 antigens. Organs are tested by real time PCR or immunohistochemistry (IHC) and swabs by real time PCR.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination.

Other preventative measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control programme/ mechanisms

The control programmes/ strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Notification system in place

Q-fever in animals is not a notifiable disease

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Q-fever in humans is not a notifiable disease. In Austria the number of sheep per holding is low (3.9 animals per holding in average) compared to countries that have a problem with Q-fever; therefore no change of the epidemiological situation in Austria is expected.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

Nil

Table 96 Q-fever in animals, 2013

Animal species		Source of information	Sampling strategy	Sampler	Sample type	Analytical method	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Coxiella</i> (Q-fever)
Cattle									
	Cattle, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES	suspect sampling	official sampling	blood	KBR	animal	447	6
	Cattle, at farm, surveillance (pre-export checks)	AGES	Census sampling	official sampling	blood	KBR	animal	98	0
	Cattle, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES	suspect sampling	official sampling	swabs, organs	PCR, IHC	animal	18	1
Sheep									
	Sheep, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES	suspect sampling	official sampling	blood	KBR	animal	36	0
	Sheep, at farm, surveillance (pre-export checks)	AGES	Census sampling	official sampling	blood	KBR	animal	395	3
	Sheep, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES	suspect sampling	official sampling	swabs, organs	PCR, IHC	animal	7	3
Goats									
	Goats, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES	suspect sampling	official sampling	blood	KBR	animal	43	5
	Goats, at farm, surveillance (pre-export checks)	AGES	Census sampling	official sampling	blood	KBR	animal	476	0
	Goats, at farm, clinical investigation	AGES	suspect sampling	official sampling	swabs, organs	PCR, IHC	animal	10	1

PCR, IHC: Organs are tested by real time PCR or immunohistochemistry (IHC) and swabs by real time PCR

5. Information on Specific Indicators of Antimicrobial Resistance

5.1. *E. coli* Indicators

5.1.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from slaughtered animals was started in Austria in 2004 and has been continued annually.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of antimicrobial resistance of *E. coli* in broiler slaughter batches, bovine animals and pigs has been implemented according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 November 2003 in the National Order Überwachungsprogramme-Verordnung (as amended). The sampling was carried out from January to December 2013 in slaughterhouses.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Europe wide harmonized standards for antimicrobial resistance monitoring are be highly welcome.

Additional information

The results are published annually in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

5.1.2. Antimicrobial resistance in *Escherichia coli* isolates

A. Antimicrobial resistance of *E. coli* in animal - All animals - farmed - at slaughterhouse - Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

A sampling plan was created according to the federal monitoring program „ Durchführungserlass Zoonosenmonitoring 2012 - Überwachung ausgewählter Zoonosen und Antibiotikaresistenzen (BMG-74600/0314-II/B/10/2012)“. The sampling plan for *E. coli* included cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches. In 2013 again after 2012 three unique sampling plans were calculated for each of three age groups of cattle: one for calves, one for young cattle and one for cattle older than 2 years.

Type of specimen taken

E. coli was isolated from the caecum of slaughtered cattle (one sampling plan for each age group), pigs and broiler. The caecum from one bovine or pig or the whole intestines from ten slaughtered broilers within a single slaughter batch at each slaughterhouse were collected.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The intestines were refrigerated to 4 °C and samples were sent to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz, where each pathogen was isolated and further characterized. The national Reference Lab for antimicrobial resistance in the Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz performed the antimicrobial susceptibility testing for all strains.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

The number of samples was calculated by experts of the Division for Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment of the AGES based on the expected prevalence of *E. coli* among the different animal species or age groups (cattle-calves, young cattle, cattle older than 2 years; pigs, broiler flocks). All isolated strains of *E. coli* were sent to the IMED Graz for antimicrobial susceptibility testing.

Methods used for collecting data

All information concerning the tested animals and the sampled slaughterhouses were recorded in a questionnaire. In the laboratory, the data were entered into a database and later analysed in Microsoft® Excel tables.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The intestinal contents are streaked onto the MacConkey-agar plates (Merck Nr. 1.05465) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. The process is repeated for colonies which are suspected for *E. coli*. These colonies are streaked onto a blood-agar (Oxoid Nr. CM0055, 5% Sheep blood) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. The confirmation of the identification of *E. coli* is done with an oxidase- (Merck Nr. 1.13300.0001) and spot indol test (Remel, Nr. R8309002).

Laboratory used for detection for resistance

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

E. coli samples isolated from cattle, pigs and broiler slaughter batches are tested for antimicrobial susceptibility against gentamicin, kanamycin, streptomycin, ceftotaxim, sulfamethoxazol, trimethoprim, ciprofloxacin, nalidixic acid, ampicillin, chloramphenicol and tetracycline.

Breakpoints used in testing

EUCAST

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

None

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

None

Notification system in place

None

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation

Resistance rates in *E. coli* from broiler are high for some antimicrobials, e.g. fluroquinolones, streptomycin, ampicillin, nalidixic acid, sulfamethoxazol, tetracycline and trimethoprim and from pigs for streptomycin and tetracycline. In cattle low resistance rates a found. A census on the use of antimicrobials in veterinary medicine is planed.

Additional information

The results are published annually in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

Table 97 Breakpoints used for antibiotic resistance testing of *E. coli* in animals, 2013

Test method used: Broth dilution		Number of reporting laboratory: 1		
Standards used for testing		The methods are used for investigation of isolates from		
	CLSI	Feedingstuff	-	
	EUCAST	Animals	x	
		Food	-	
		Humans	-	
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Standard	Dilution method Cut-off value concentration (µg/ml) Resistant >	Diffusion method Cut-off value Zone diameter (mm) Resistant <=	
Aminoglycosides				
	Gentamicin	EUCAST	2	-
	Streptomycin	EUCAST	16	-
Amphenicol				
	Chloramphenicol	EUCAST	16	-
Cephalosporins				
	Cefotaxim	EUCAST	0.25	-
	Ceftazidime	EUCAST	0.5	-
Fluroquinolones				
	Ciprofloxacin	EUCAST	0.06	-
Penicillins				
	Ampicillin	EUCAST	8	-
Quinolones				
	Nalidixic acid	EUCAST	16	-
Sulfonamides				
		EUCAST	64	-
Tetracyclines				
	Tetracycline	EUCAST	8	-
Trimethoprim				
		EUCAST	2	-
Carbapeneme				
	Meropenem	EUCAST	0.12	-

Table 98 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. coli* in animals (qualitative tables), 2013

<i>E. coli</i>															
	Gallus Gallus			Calves			young cattle (1-2 years)			cattle > 2 years			Pigs		
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes			yes			yes			yes			yes		
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	146			151			73			86			150		
Antimicrobials:	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	146	2.1%	3	151	0.7%	1	73	0.0%	0	86	0.0%	0	150	2.0%	3
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	146	34.9%	51	151	21.2%	32	73	5.5%	4	86	4.7%	4	150	56.7%	85
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	146	5.5%	8	151	4.6%	7	73	1.4%	1	86	2.3%	2	150	5.3%	8
Carbapenems - Meropenem	146	0.0%	0	151	0.0%	0	73	0.0%	0	86	0.0%	0	150	0.0%	0
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	146	2.1%	3	151	0.7%	1	73	0.0%	0	86	0.0%	0	150	1.3%	2
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	146	2.7%	4	151	0.7%	1	73	0.0%	0	86	1.2%	1	150	1.3%	2
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	146	65.1%	95	151	2.6%	4	73	0.0%	0	86	2.3%	2	150	4.0%	6
Penicillins - Ampicillin	146	38.4%	56	151	10.6%	16	73	1.4%	1	86	2.3%	2	150	17.3%	26
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	146	62.3%	91	151	2.6%	4	73	0.0%	0	86	2.3%	2	150	2.0%	3
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	146	38.4%	56	151	22.5%	34	73	4.1%	3	86	5.8%	5	150	28.7%	43
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	146	22.6%	33	151	25.8%	39	73	6.8%	5	86	9.3%	8	150	52.7%	79
Trimethoprim	146	20.5%	30	151	5.3%	8	73	1.4%	1	86	2.3%	2	150	14.7%	22
Number of multiresistant isolates															
fully sensitive	146	15.8%	23	151	69.5%	105	73	93.2%	68	86	88.4%	76	150	30.0%	45
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	146	25.3%	37	151	6.6%	10	73	1.4%	1	86	5.8%	5	150	21.3%	32
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	146	21.9%	32	151	2.6%	4	73	1.4%	1	86	2.3%	2	150	18.7%	28
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	146	8.9%	13	151	11.9%	18	73	2.7%	2	86	1.2%	1	150	10.7%	16
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	146	13.0%	19	151	2.6%	4	73	0.0%	0	86	0.0%	0	150	8.7%	13
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	146	15.1%	22	151	6.6%	10	73	1.4%	1	86	2.3%	2	150	10.7%	16

N = number of isolates tested

n = number of resistant isolates

r% = % isolates resistant

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For *E. coli* this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, streptomycin, gentamicin, tetracycline, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazol

Table 99 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. coli* in broiler - at slaughter - monitoring programme – active monitoring (slaughter batch) - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2013

		<i>E.coli</i> Gallus gallus, broiler		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																						
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		146																						
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	146	2.1%	3							99	42	2		2		1								
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	146	34.9%	51											30	56	9	7	17	12	8	7			
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	146	5.5%	8									1	27	95	15	1	2	1	4					
Carbapenems - Meropenem	146	0.0%	0	2	105	39																		
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	146	2.1%	3				115	25	3		1				1	1								
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	146	2.7%	4					84	54	4	2				1	1								
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	146	65.1%	95		35	16		4	36	20	12	5	5	9	4									
Penicillins - Ampicillin	146	38.4%	56								3	29	52	6				56						
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	146	62.3%	91									29	20	5	1	2	15	22	16	36				
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	146	38.4%	56											20	44	22	4				1	55		
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	146	22.6%	33								12	87	14		1		5	27						
Trimethoprim	146	20.5%	30						35	70	9	2			1	29								

Table 100 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. coli* in Calves (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2013

<i>E.coli</i> Calves		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)	yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	151																					
Antimicrobials:	N	n	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	151	0.7%	1					6	124	19	1											1
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	151	21.2%	32										52	65	2	5	13	5	7	2		
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	151	4.6%	7								1	30	109	4		1	1	5				
Carbapenems - Meropenem	151	0.0%	0	90	61																	
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	151	0.7%	1			140	8	2							1							
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	151	0.7%	1				106	43	1	1												
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	151	2.6%	4	15	113	19		3						1								
Penicillins - Ampicillin	151	10.6%	16							4	25	98	8			1	15					
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	151	2.6%	4								90	56	1				1	2	1			
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	151	22.5%	34										32	72	13						34	
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	151	25.8%	39							4	90	18			1	13	25					
Trimethoprim	151	5.3%	8					56	66	19	2				8							

Table 101 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. coli* in Cattle 1-2 years (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2013

		<i>E. coli</i> Cattle 1-2 years		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		73																					
Antimicrobials:	N	n	=<0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
	N	%R	n	n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	73	0.0%	0						66	7													
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	73	5.5%	4									27	42			2	1	1					
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	73	1.4%	1									12	56	4									
Carbapenems - Meropenem	73	0.0%	0	1	43	29																	
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	73	0.0%	0				62	10	1														
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	73	0.0%	0					48	22	3													
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	73	0.0%	0	8	50	14	1																
Penicillins - Ampicillin	73	1.4%	1								12	55	5				1						
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	73	0.0%	0								42	31											
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	73	4.1%	3										24	37	8	1						3	
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	73	6.8%	5							3	51	14			1	1	3						
Trimethoprim	73	1.4%	1					30	33	9					1								

Table 102 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. coli* in Cattle > 2 years (bovine animals) - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2013

		<i>E. coli</i> Cattle > 2 years		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
		yes	86	=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
Antimicrobials:	N	%R	n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	86	0.0%	0					5	67	13	1												
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	86	4.7%	4										34	46	2		2		2				
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	86	2.3%	2									3	13	60	8			1	1				
Carbapenems - Meropenem	86	0.0%	0	3	41	42																	
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	86	0.0%	0				74	12															
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	86	1.2%	1					56	28	1	1												
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	86	2.3%	2	10	63	10	1		1					1									
Penicillins - Ampicillin	86	2.3%	2								4	17	52	11				2					
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	86	2.3%	2									47	35	2					2				
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	86	5.8%	5											19	41	19	2					5	
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	86	9.3%	8								5	60	13			2	2	4					
Trimethoprim	86	2.3%	2					35	43	5	1					2							

Table 103 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. coli* in Pigs - at slaughter - monitoring programme - active monitoring - quantitative data [Dilution method], 2013

		<i>E.coli</i> Pigs		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
Isolates out of a monitoring programme (Yes / no)		yes																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		150																					
Antimicrobials:				=< 0.008	0.015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n	n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	150	2.0%	3						1	113	32	1				1	2						
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	150	56.7%	85											29	33	3	13	31	25	13	3		
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	150	5.3%	8									1	35	100	6	3	1		4				
Carbapenems - Meropenem	150	0.0%	0	3	86	59	2																
Cephalosporins - Cefotaxime	150	1.3%	2				129	19								1	1						
Cephalosporins - Ceftazidim	150	1.3%	2					101	44	3	1	1											
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	150	4.0%	6	8	100	35	1			3	1			1	1								
Penicillins - Ampicillin	150	17.3%	26								3	51	67	3				26					
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	150	2.0%	3									73	70	1	3	1					2		
Sulfonamides - Sulfamethoxazol	150	28.7%	43											39	54	13	1					43	
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	150	52.7%	79								6	58	7		1	1	16	61					
Trimethoprim	150	14.7%	22						49	67	12		1			21							

5.2. *Enterococcus* Indicators

5.2.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from slaughtered animals was started in Austria from 2004 to 2012 but that program was suspended in 2013.

6. Food-borne outbreaks

Food-borne outbreaks are defined as two or more human cases of the same disease or infection where the cases are linked or are probably linked to the same food source. A situation in which the observed human cases exceed the expected number of cases and where a same food source is suspected, is also indicative of a food-borne outbreak.

A. Food-borne outbreaks

System in place for identification, epidemiological investigations and reporting of food-borne outbreaks

Presently, every district (n = 95) is responsible for outbreak investigation. However, food-borne outbreaks affecting more than one district or even more than one province (Austria = 9 provinces) are regulated by the Federal Zoonoses Act (Zoonosengesetz, BGBl. I, 128/2005 entered into force on 1. January 2006). The Federal Zoonoses Commission was founded to advise the Federal Minister to survey and combat the zoonoses in Austria. One target of the Zoonoses Act is to ensure that food-borne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation. It regulates, in case of food-borne outbreaks affecting more than one province that the governors of the affected provinces provide operative units to investigate possible or confirmed food-borne outbreaks. Data concerning epidemiological criteria, potential implicated food items and the source of an outbreak must be collected and adequate epidemiological and microbiological examinations must be conducted. Short reports summarize each outbreak and must be communicated to the Federal Commission for Zoonoses and to AGES.

Description of the types of outbreaks covered by the reporting:

Since there has not been a coordinated approach for outbreak investigation in most provinces, the large majority (100 of 133) of food-borne outbreaks are classified as household outbreaks. Coordinated investigation of outbreaks affecting more than one province - unhampered by district limits - could decrease the total number of outbreaks.

National evaluation of the reported outbreaks in the country:

In 2013, 133 food-borne outbreaks affecting 568 persons were reported. 108 persons were hospitalized and 0 person died. The total number of food-borne outbreaks increased by 9 % compared to 2012. The average number of cases affected by an outbreak was 4.3 persons, ranging from two to 71 persons per outbreak. 16 % (14 % in 2012) of the reported outbreaks were acquired abroad. 46 % of all food-borne outbreaks acquired in Austria were caused by *Campylobacter* spp. (n=51), 31 % by *Salmonella* spp. (n=35) and 63 % thereof by serotype Enteritidis (n=22) compared to (51 %) in 2012.

Relevance of the different causative agents, food categories and the agent/food category combinations

Campylobacter and *Salmonella* pose the most important agents causing 77 % of all food borne outbreaks (93 % in 2012). The data quality does presently not allow conclusions on the relevance of different food categories.

Relevance of the different type of places of food production and preparation in outbreaks

The data quality does presently not allow conclusions on the relevance of different food categories.

Evaluation of the severity and clinical picture of the human cases

19 % of patients affected by these food-borne outbreaks are reported as hospitalized (17,3% in 2012); like in 2011 and 2012, no deaths occurred in association with outbreaks.

Control measures or other actions taken to improve the situation

Improvement due to the implementation of the Federal Zoonoses Act e.g. the chain of command in terms of investigation of food-borne outbreaks affecting more than one province was implemented.

Additional information

The situation of foodborne outbreaks are published in the National Zoonoses Brochure.

Table 104 Food-borne outbreaks with food vehicle identified and strong evidence (EMS), 2013

FBO Code	Causative agent	Number of outbreaks	Number of human cases	Number of hospitalisations	Number of deaths	Food Vehicle	Nature of evidence linking the outbreak with food	Type of outbreak	Setting	Place of origin of problem	Origin of Food Vehicle	Contributory factors
2916/ 2921	Bacteria - Other Bacterial agents	1	71	2	0	Bovine meat and products thereof, Cereal products including rice and seeds/pulses (nuts, almonds)	Analytical epidemiological evidence	General	Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XX	
2969	Bacteria - Other Bacterial agents	1	14	3	0	Vegetables and juices and other products thereof	Analytical epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	General	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	AT	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient, Cross-contamination, Inadequate heat treatment
3063	Bacteria - Other Bacterial agents	1	11	7	0	Mixed food	Analytical epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	General	Canteen or workplace catering	Canteen or workplace catering	AT	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient, Cross-contamination, Inadequate heat treatment
2832/ 2668	Calicivirus - norovirus (Norwalk-like virus)	1	40	0	0	Fish and fish products	Analytical epidemiological evidence	General	Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XX	
2854	Calicivirus - norovirus (Norwalk-like virus)	1	11	0	0	Other foods	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	General	Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	EU	
2880	Calicivirus - norovirus (Norwalk-like virus)	1	30	5	0	Mixed food	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	General	institution (nursing home or prison or boarding school)	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XX	Infected food handler
2976	Calicivirus - norovirus (Norwalk-like virus)	1	6	1	0	Mixed food	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	General	Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XX	Infected food handler
3039	Calicivirus - norovirus (Norwalk-like virus)	1	8	0	0	Fruit, berries and juices and other products thereof	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	General	Hospital or medical care facility	Canteen or workplace catering	AT	Infected food handler
3146	Calicivirus - norovirus (Norwalk-like virus)	1	34	3	0	Vegetables and juices and other products thereof	Analytical epidemiological evidence	General	Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XX	
3031	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Other, mixed or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	EU	
3043	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	1	0	Other, mixed or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Household / domestic kitchen	Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	EU	
3072	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	1	0	Other, mixed or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	EU	
3108	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Other, mixed or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	General	Household	Travel abroad	EU	
3145	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	2	0	Milk	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	
3165	Verotoxigenic E. coli (VTEC) - VTEC O128:H-	1	2	1	0	Tap water, including well water	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	AT	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient
3037	Hepatitis virus - Hepatitis A virus	1	6	4	0	Fruit, berries and juices and other products thereof	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	General	Household	Household	AT	
3118	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 2	1	2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	General	Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Unknown	AT	
2917	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 4	1	3	2	0	Eggs and egg products	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	domestic kitchen	Household	Household	AT	
3049	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 5	1	2	0	0	Other, mixed or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	EU	
3125	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 21	1	2	0	0	Milk	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	domestic kitchen	Household	Household	AT	
2904	Salmonella - S. Infantis	1	2	0	0	Eggs and egg products	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	
2911	Salmonella - S. Newport	1	4	2	0	Eggs and egg products	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	treatment
3026	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 120	1	2	0	0	Dairy products (other than cheeses)	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Household / domestic kitchen	Others	Travel abroad	EU	
3018	Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 4/O:3	1	2	0	0	Meat and meat products	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Household / domestic kitchen	Others	Others	XX	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient

Data source: EMS as of April 16, 2014

Table 105 Food-borne outbreaks with no food vehicle identified or weak evidence, 2013

		Outbreaks with no food vehicle identified or weak evidence			
		Number of Outbreaks	Number of Human Cases	Number of Hospitalised	Number of Deaths
Agents categories	Causative agents				
<i>Salmonella</i>	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	7	16	2	0
	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	23	86	34	0
	Other serovars	7	16	2	0
<i>Campylobacter</i>		53	118	19	0
<i>Listeria</i>	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	2	7	7	0
	Other <i>Listeria</i>				
<i>Yersinia</i>					
<i>Escherichia coli</i> , pathogenic	Verotoxigenic <i>E. coli</i> (VTEC)	8	23	6	0
<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>B. cereus</i>				
	Other <i>Bacillus</i>				
Staphylococcal enterotoxins					
<i>Clostridium</i>	<i>Cl. botulinum</i>				
	<i>Cl. perfringens</i>				
	Other Clostridia				
Other Bacterial agents	<i>Brucella</i>				
	<i>Shigella</i>	2	4	0	0
	Other Bacterial agents				
Parasites	<i>Trichinella</i>				
	<i>Giardia</i>				
	<i>Cryptosporidium</i>				
	<i>Anisakis</i>				
	Other Parasites				
Viruses	Norovirus	4	30	0	0
	Hepatitis viruses	2	4	3	0
	Other Viruses	1	2	1	0
Other agents	Histamine				
	Marine biotoxins				
	Other Agents				
Unknown agent					

Data source: EMS as of April 16, 2014

7. Information on specific microbiological agents

7.1. Staphylococcal Enterotoxins

7.1.1. Staphylococcal enterotoxins general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Not available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Food samples are not directly tested for staphylococcal enterotoxins. The analysis consists of two steps, a prescreening to identify samples harbouring > 100,000 coagulase-positive staphylococci CFU per gram and a screening step using staphylococcal isolates from samples > 100,000 CFU/g. Because it is not known how many and which samples were tested for coagulase-positive staphylococci the results cannot be reported.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Not available

Additional information

Not available

7.1.2. Staphylococcal enterotoxins in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Not available

Type of specimen taken

Not available

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Not available

Definition of positive finding

Detection of staphylococcal enterotoxins in food with coagulase-positive staphylococci exceeding 100,000 CFU/g

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Food samples are not directly tested for staphylococcal enterotoxins.

Prescreening: Several food (e. g. icecream, meat, cheese, etc.) is tested for coagulase-positive staphylococci. If the number of detected staphylococci exceeds 100,000 CFU/g, the food is further tested for staphylococcal enterotoxins.

Screening: isolates from samples > 100,000 CFU staphylococci per gram of tested foodstuffs: A screening ELISA for staphylococcal enterotoxins A-E is performed (commercially available Sandwich ELISA). For a positive screening result another ELISA reveals the toxin group with the detection limit of at least 10 µg/kg.

All isolates are sent to the National Reference Laboratory in Graz, where the Enterotoxins A, B, C1, C2, C3, D, E are identified via an ELFA (enzyme linked fluorescent assay). RPLA (reverse passive latexagglutination) and ELISAs for further investigations on the enterotoxins may complete the analysis.

Preventive measures in place

Not available

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the hazard

Not available

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Not available

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Notification system in place

Not available

Results of the investigation

Because it is not known how many and which samples were tested for coagulase-positive staphylococci the results cannot be reported.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

7.2. *Cronobacter sakazakii*

7.2.1. *Cronobacter sakazakii* in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Not available

Type of specimen taken

Not available

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Not available

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriological method ISO 22964:2006

Preventive measures in place

Not available

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the hazard

Not available

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Not available

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Notification system in place

Not available

Results of the investigation

See table below

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Campaign A-012-13: *Cronobacter sakazakii* in food – infant formula – dried – at retail – Surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system**Sampling strategy**

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: March - April

Type of specimen taken

Infant formula dried

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive findingDetection of *Cronobacter* in 25 g**Diagnostic/analytical methods used**

Bacteriological method ISO 22964:2006

Results of the investigation34 samples tested for *Cronobacter sakazakii*: 0-times positive**Additional information**Samples were also tested for *Salmonella* spp.**Table 106 *Cronobacter sakazakii* in food, 2013**

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Cronobacter sakazakii</i>
Infant formula		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	100	Gram	1	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	100	Gram	6	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	100	Gram	4	0
Infant formula - dried	campaign A-012-13	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	21	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0

7.3. Histamine

7.3.1. Histamine general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Not available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Not available

Additional information

Not available

7.3.2. Histamine in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Not available

Type of specimen taken

Fish, fishery products, cheese

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Not available

Definition of positive finding

>200 mg histamine per kg fish - fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured

>400 mg histamine per kg fish - fishery products which have undergone enzyme maturation treatment in brine

>400 mg histamine per kg cheese

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

High performance liquid chromatography with UV detection; (HPLC-UV)

Preventive measures in place

Not available

Control program/mechanisms

Not available

The control program/strategies in place

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the hazard

Not available

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Not available

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Notification system in place

Not available

Results of the investigation

See table below

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Campaign A-024-13: Histamine in food – Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured – at catering – Surveillance – official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at catering by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: May - July

Type of specimen taken

Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine (tuna in open cans, collected in restaurants)

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 10g

Definition of positive finding

>200 mg histamine per kg fish - fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured

>400 mg histamine per kg fish - fishery products which have undergone enzyme maturation treatment in brine

>400 mg histamine per kg cheese

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

High performance liquid chromatography with UV detection; (HPLC-UV)

Results of the investigation

99 samples tested for histamine: 2-times positive >400 mg/kg, 1-time positive >100 to ≤200 mg/kg

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Salmonella* spp.

Table 107 Histamine in food, 2013

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units in non-conformity	≤100 mg/kg	>100 to ≤200 mg/kg	>400 mg/kg
Beverages, alcoholic		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from cows' milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	6	0	6	0	0
Fish - raw		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	1	0	1	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	9	0	9	0	0
Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured	campaign A-024-13	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	10	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	19	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	57	1	0	0	1
			XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	13	2	0	1	1
Fishery products, unspecified		Catering	XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	6	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	4	0	4	0	0
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	12	0	7	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	4	0	3	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	1	0	0
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Fruits - products		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	3	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	4	0	3	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0

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